

UNIVERSIDAD DE CASTILLA-LA MANCHA

Facultad de Educación de Ciudad Real

**Intervenciones educativas basadas en el
modelo de Educación Deportiva:
evaluando los efectos sobre
competencias socioemocionales en
población escolar**

TESIS DOCTORAL

Doctorando: Pablo Luna Nogales

Director: Dr. Javier Cejudo Prado

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Dr. Javier Cejudo Prado, Profesor Contratado Doctor y Vicedecano de Prácticas y Ordenación Académica en la Facultad de Educación en Ciudad Real de la Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha,

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Que **D. Pablo Luna Nogales** ha realizado, bajo su dirección, el trabajo de investigación titulado: "**Intervenciones educativas basadas en el modelo de Educación Deportiva: evaluando los efectos sobre competencias socioemocionales en población escolar**". Asimismo, certifica que este trabajo ha sido realizado bajo su tutela en el Departamento de Psicología de la Facultad de Educación de Ciudad Real (Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha). Se trata de un trabajo original, que cumple todas las condiciones exigidas por normativa vigente, y es apto para ser presentado en público para obtener el grado de Doctor en Investigación en Humanidades, Artes y Educación por la Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha.

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*A mi mujer y director:
los trenes que han hecho posible
que este proyecto siga caminando.*

En un lugar de la Mancha...

«Don Quijote de la Mancha»

(Miguel de Cervantes Saavedra, 1605)

Don Belianís de Grecia a don Quijote de La Mancha

Soneto

*Rompí, corté, abollé, y dije, e hice
más que en el orbe caballero andante;
fui diestro, fui valiente, fui arrogante;
mil agravios vengué, cien mil deshice.*

*Hazañas di a la fama que eternice;
fui comedido y regalado amante;
fue enano para mí todo gigante;
y el duelo en cualquier punto satisfice.*

*Tuve a mis pies postrada la fortuna;
y trajo del copete mi cordura
a la calva ocasión al estricote.*

*Mas, aunque sobre el cuerno de la luna
siempre se vio encumbrada mi ventura;
tus proezas envidio, ¡oh gran Quijote!*

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Abreviaciones/Acrónimos

- afPE: Association for Physical Education.
- [AHA: American Heart Association].
- [AMSC-Q: Adolescent Multidimensional Social Competence Questionnaire].
- ANCOVA: Análisis de covarianza.
- ANOVA: Análisis de varianza.
- [APA: American Psychological Association].
- ASE: Aprendizaje Social y Emocional.
- [BASC: Behavior Assessment System for Children and Adolescents].
- [CASEL: Collaborative Academic Social Emotional Learning].
- EF: Educación Física.
- EFC: Educación Física de Calidad.
- EP: Educación Primaria.
- ESO: Educación Secundaria Obligatoria.
- GC: Grupo control.
- GE: Grupo experimental.
- [GW4: Guess Who Questionnaire].
- [JCR: Journal Citation Reports].
- MANCOVA: Análisis multivariante de la covarianza.
- MANOVA: Análisis multivariante de la varianza.
- MED: Modelo de Educación Deportiva.
- MT-ID: Modelo Tradicional de Instrucción Directa.
- [NASPE: National Association for Sport and Physical Education].
- OE: Objetivos específicos.
- OG: Objetivos generales.
- OMS: Organización Mundial de la Salud.
- [PANAS: Positive and Negative Affect Schedule].
- PANASN: Escalas Panas de afecto positivo y negativo para niños y adolescentes.
- [QPE: Quality Physical Education].
- [SAS-A: Social Anxiety Scale for Adolescents].
- [SAS-T: Global Index of Social Anxiety].
- [SEL: Social and Emotional Learning].

- [SEM: Sport Education Model].
- [SHAPE: Society of Health and Physical Educators America].
- [SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences].
- [TEIQue-ASF: Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire Adolescents Short Form].
- UDD: Unidades Didácticas.
- [UNESCO: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization].
- [WHO: World Health Organization].

1. PRESENTACIÓN

*“¡Nos ladran Sancho!, señal de que avanzamos”
(Don Quijote de Orson Wells)*

La educación de calidad requiere un componente afectivo y social bien planificado (Eisner, 2004a, 2004b) que facilite y favorezca en el alumnado una garantía cognitiva, física, afectiva y psicosocial positiva del entorno educativo (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2015). Del mismo modo, una educación efectiva para los estudiantes del siglo XXI, no solo debería atender a sus finalidades, sino también a los procesos y formas de enseñanza y aprendizaje, así como, al desarrollo de sus competencias socioemocionales (UNESCO, 2015). El Informe Delors (Delors, 1996) proponía una visión integral y equilibrada de la educación basada en dos conceptos esenciales: (a) aprender a lo largo de toda la vida; (b) y fomentar cuatro pilares esenciales de la educación: aprender a conocer, a hacer, a ser y a vivir juntos. En este sentido, vivimos en una sociedad dinámica, con frecuentes y diligentes cambios, afectando a todos los entornos de la vida y contextos sociales (e.g., educativo) y que se caracterizan por niveles nuevos de complejidad y contradicción. Estos cambios generan tensiones para los que la educación debería preparar a los individuos, instituciones y comunidades educativas, capacitándoles con estrategias y metodologías de prevención, adaptación y respuesta significativas, que impulsen un positivo desarrollo integral, personal y social del alumnado infantil y adolescente. Hayat et al. (2018) señalan que los procesos de enseñanza y aprendizaje podrían ser un procedimiento complejo, en el que los factores socioemocionales son decisivos.

La importancia de la dimensión afectivo-social para el éxito en el aprendizaje, en el contexto escolar, son temas que despiertan gran interés en la investigación (e.g., Domitrovich et al., 2017; Durlak et al., 2011, 2015; Taylor et al., 2017; UNESCO, 2015; Weissberg et al., 2015). En este sentido, el procedimiento de enseñanza y aprendizaje es un proceso individual complejo, pero también social (Franco et al., 2017) donde la búsqueda de objetivos sociales y afectivos puede impulsar el éxito escolar (Cecchini Estrada et al., 2011; Elliot et al., 2006). Asimismo, para impulsar positivamente dicho logro educativo, no solo es necesario favorecer habilidades cognitivas, sino también promover competencias socioemocionales (Domitrovich et al., 2017; Greenberg et al., 2003; Payton, 2008; Taylor et al., 2017). Por tanto, es relevante impulsar en los contextos educativos, climas óptimos y motivacionales que favorezcan un ajuste psicosocial y afectivo significativo, así como un desarrollo integral del alumnado (Bisquerra et al., 2015).

La Organización Mundial de la salud (OMS) (World Health Organization [WHO], 2000) señaló la relevancia de fomentar el bienestar social y emocional en el contexto educativo. En este sentido, es probable que el desarrollo de intervenciones físicas y deportivas, en entornos escolares, podrían ayudar a prevenir el desarrollo de comportamientos inadaptativos en los jóvenes y, por ende, proteger su bienestar personal y social (Halliday et al., 2019; McMahon et al., 2017). En este sentido, la OMS (WHO, 2000; 2007) recomienda que las escuelas funcionen como un entorno de prevención, intervención y apoyo para la salud mental de los estudiantes, impulsando el desarrollo de habilidades o competencias socioemocionales de los niños en edad escolar (Cefai et al., 2018; Rougeaux et al., 2020). Del mismo modo, se están promocionando intervenciones en el contexto escolar, donde las competencias sociales y afectivas juegan un papel clave en los diferentes niveles educativos (Durlak et al., 2015). Diferentes estudios muestran que dichas competencias son significativas para la mejora del clima escolar (Ortega-Ruiz & Zych, 2016) y son clave para una educación de calidad (Oberle et al., 2016).

Por otro lado, un objetivo clave dentro del contexto educativo debería ser promocionar hábitos de vida saludables de forma activa y participativa (WHO, 2016). En esta línea, la Educación Física (EF), desde enfoques organizativos como el Aprendizaje Social y Emocional (ASE) y el marco pedagógico de la Educación Física de Calidad (EFC) reforzadora de prácticas prosociales (UNESCO, 2015), se instrumentaliza como una disciplina académica eficaz para favorecer un compromiso integral del alumnado (Escalié et al., 2017; Whitehead, 2010) al desarrollar positivamente sus esferas cognitivas, afectivas, físicas y sociales (Bessa et al., 2019, 2021; Evangelio et al., 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2018; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). Bessa et al. (2021) resaltan que, dentro del entorno escolar, la EF es reconocida como una disciplina académica relevante para promover el desarrollo personal y social del alumnado, favorecedora de metodológicas cooperativas y de experiencias socioemocionales positivas para el alumnado. Asimismo, estas actividades físicas y deportivas dentro de la EF, son beneficiosas desde una perspectiva integral en la niñez (Amado-Alonso et al., 2019; Bessa et al., 2019).

En este sentido, sería primordial para el sistema educativo configurar un camino de renovación metodológica que evolucione, como establece la UNESCO (UNESCO, 2015), hacia una EFC para la interrelación de enseñanzas y aprendizajes inclusivos,

activos y participativos, frente a una Educación Física tradicional basada en metodologías caracterizadas por procesos repetitivos, memorísticos y habilidades motoras mecanizadas y específicas (González-Víllora et al., 2009). Se busca, por tanto, experiencias metodológicas que impulsen prácticas pedagógicas positivas con intervenciones basadas en modelos didácticos de enseñanza o basados en la práctica activa y participativa. Estos modelos pedagógicos desarrollados de manera segura y contextualizada frente a modelos educativos tradicionales descontextualizados serán más motivantes para el alumnado. Entre los modelos pedagógicos más idóneos (Iserbyt et al., 2016) para desarrollar la dimensión socioemocional del alumnado se encuentra el modelo de Educación Deportiva (en adelante, MED) (Bessa et al., 2019, 2021; Evangelio et al., 2018; Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019, 2020; Luna, Rodríguez-Donaire, et al., 2020; Siedentop et al., 2020). En otras palabras, una disciplina académica (EF) constructiva que promueva intervenciones motivantes (Shields et al., 2018) dentro de un marco de aprendizaje socioemocional que evolucione con eficaces modelos pedagógicos, como el MED (Siedentop, 1994; Siedentop et al., 2020).

Por lo tanto, la presente tesis doctoral presenta de forma general los siguientes objetivos: (1) diseñar dos programas educativos, basados en el MED: uno para alumnado de Educación Primaria y otro para alumnado de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria; (2) desarrollar dichos programas de intervención en el alumnado citado en diferentes centros educativos; y (3) evaluar la eficacia de estos programas, basados en el MED, sobre diferentes variables socioemocionales en alumnado de Educación Primaria y de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria.

Para finalizar, este trabajo de tesis doctoral queda constituido como un proyecto original, elaborado a partir de un conjunto de tres manuscritos científicos, publicados en revistas indexadas en las principales bases de datos, tales como [Journal Citation Reports] (JCR). Estos estudios se presentan en formato original de envío, en el epígrafe “Contribuciones científicas de la tesis”. Del mismo modo, la tesis doctoral fue diseñada por el Dr. Javier Cejudo Prado y el doctorando Pablo Luna Nogales. El doctorando ha recibido para la realización de esta tesis doctoral un contrato predoctoral como personal investigador en formación (orgánica **01105PR181**), en el marco del Plan Propio de I+D+i (cofinanciado por el Fondo Social Europeo; 2018/12504) por parte del gobierno regional de Castilla-La Mancha (Código de Contrato: **2018-CUPCLM-8030**).

2. INTRODUCCIÓN

“Yo, como don Quijote, me invento pasiones para ejercitarme”

(Voltaire)

2.1. Educación Física de Calidad y Aprendizaje Social y Emocional

En el ámbito educativo, una asignatura que puede contribuir a la mejora del bienestar y salud de la población infantil y adolescente es la EF. En esta línea, la EFC debe considerarse como un marco teórico y organizativo clave para el contexto escolar (UNESCO, 2015). La EFC tiene entre otros, el objetivo de impulsar procesos de enseñanza y aprendizaje significativos, dirigidos de forma activa, inclusiva y cooperativa, favoreciendo las habilidades afectivas y sociales del alumnado (UNESCO, 2015) (ver **Figura 1**).

Figura 1. *Objetivos clave en la Educación Física de Calidad (EFC) [QPE: Quality Physical Education]* (Fuente: UNESCO, 2015).

Los programas educativos que tiene como enfoque la EFC, impulsan en los estudiantes el desarrollo de habilidades físicas, afectivas y sociales, definiéndolos seguros de sí mismos y socialmente responsables. Del mismo modo, la EFC se considera como una experiencia de enseñanza y aprendizaje físicamente activa, que puede favorecer en el alumnado, habilidades psicomotrices, comprensión cognitiva y aptitudes afectivas y sociales (Association for Physical Education, 2015).

En esta línea, la EF, desde el marco organizativo de la EFC, reforzadora de prácticas prosociales (UNESCO, 2015), se instrumentaliza como una disciplina académica eficaz para favorecer un compromiso integral del alumnado (Escalié et al., 2017; Whitehead, 2010) al desarrollar positivamente sus dominios cognitivos, afectivos, físicos y sociales (Bessa et al., 2021; Evangelio et al., 2018; Sierra-Díaz

et al., 2019). The Association for Physical Education (2015) establece que la EFC podría actuar como punto de partida para un compromiso con la actividad física y el deporte a lo largo de la vida de los estudiantes. En este sentido, esta asignatura dota al alumnado de recursos activos, cooperativos y prácticos (Girard et al., 2019) que hacen mejorar sus experiencias en el entorno escolar (Kohl & Cook, 2013; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). Del mismo modo, fomenta en el alumnado la posibilidad de desarrollar en un entorno real, competencias personales y sociales que en otras asignaturas les resultaría más complejo de aprender (Hellison, 2011).

Por otro lado, creemos que otro aspecto relevante para una EFC, debería ser promocionar y promover en el sistema educativo el ASE. The Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning [CASEL] (2021) define el ASE [SEL: Social and Emotional Learning] como un proceso a través del cual los estudiantes adquieren e implementan de forma efectiva los conocimientos, actitudes y habilidades necesarias para comprender y aplicar significativamente: (a) competencias socioemocionales; (b) objetivos y metas relevantes; (c) habilidades intra e interpersonales (e.g., empatía); (d) actitudes positivas; (e) relaciones y tomas de decisiones responsables (consultar **Figura 2**).

Figura 2. Aprendizaje Social y Emocional (ASE) [SEL]: ¿Cuáles son las áreas de competencias y dónde se promueven? (Fuente: CASEL. Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning, 2021).

Domitrovich et al. (2017) señalan que el ASE es: (a) un proceso pedagógico a través del cual se desarrollan las competencias socioemocionales; (b) un constructo multidimensional fundamental en el éxito de las escuelas; (c) y un marco organizativo que actúa como un factor protector ante el desarrollo de posibles conductas desadaptativas del alumnado. Por tanto, el aprendizaje eficaz, instrumentalizado con enfoques como el ASE (SEL), implica procesos de enseñanza y aprendizaje de competencias socioemocionales en las interacciones intra e interpersonales, favoreciendo una estructura escolar significativa que impulsa un desarrollo equilibrado e integral de los estudiantes (Oberle et al., 2016). En este sentido, el ASE podría ser un componente esencial para el éxito vital (Weissberg et al., 2015) que, al implementarlo en las escuelas, fomenta políticas y prácticas que ayudan a los estudiantes a adquirir y aplicar positivamente conocimientos, habilidades y actitudes intrapersonales e interpersonales, así como mejoran su bienestar personal y social, protegiéndose contra resultados educativos negativos (Taylor et al., 2017). Del mismo modo, el enfoque ASE es entendido por la OMS (2013) como un conjunto heterogéneo de habilidades para la vida y, por ende, es visto como un potencial factor de protección educativo, así como un significativo impulsor de salud mental.

Desde estos planteamientos, creemos que un clima escolar positivo debería organizarse desde los enfoques pedagógicos de la EFC (Le Masurier & Corbin, 2006; UNESCO, 2015; Whitehead, 2010) y el ASE (CASEL, 2021; Domitrovich et al., 2017; Durlak et al., 2015; Taylor et al., 2017; Weissberg et al., 2015). Además, es clave para la niñez y adolescencia configurar un camino pedagógico de renovación metodológica que evolucione, como establece la UNESCO (2015) hacia una educación de calidad de interrelación de enseñanzas y aprendizajes inclusivos, activos y cooperativos. En esta línea, la EFC se considera como una experiencia de enseñanza y aprendizaje físicamente activa, que puede favorecer en el alumnado beneficiosas habilidades psicomotrices, comprensión cognitiva y aptitudes afectivas y sociales (Le Masurier & Corbin, 2006; UNESCO, 2015; Whitehead, 2010). Asimismo, diferentes expertos en la materia (UNESCO, 2015) apuntan que la EFC genera un clima de aula beneficioso para el desarrollo positivo del alumnado en sus diferentes competencias motrices y socioemocionales.

Ren et al. (2020) muestran la importancia de promover en los contextos educativos competencias socioemocionales mediante eficaces prácticas activas. En

esta línea, la presente tesis doctoral es congruente con las intervenciones educativas o prácticas físico-deportivas escolares que promocionan el desarrollo equilibrado del alumnado y pretenden mejorar su desarrollo evolutivo en sus diferentes dimensiones físicas, sociales y afectivas (Bessa et al., 2021; Metzler, 2017). Del mismo modo, evaluar en el contexto de la Educación Física, diferentes variables socioemocionales (objeto de estudio de la vigente tesis doctoral), desde los enfoques de la EFC y el ASE, es determinante y fundamental tanto para mejorar el desarrollo personal y social de la población infantil y adolescentes, como para impulsar y soportar empíricamente una educación de calidad.

2.2. El modelo de Educación Deportiva en el contexto educativo

Escalié et al. (2017) enfatizan la importancia del desarrollo equilibrado de los estudiantes. El sistema educativo tiene la necesidad de fomentar entornos motivantes y competentes que sean significativos para un ajuste psicosocial positivo y, por ende, para el desarrollo integral de la personalidad del alumnado (Bisquerra et al., 2015). Del mismo modo, es importante promocionar en el contexto escolar intervenciones físicas y deportivas de forma inclusiva, activa y participativa (Shields et al., 2018) y que a su vez estén impulsadas por modelos pedagógicos efectivos (Iserbyt et al., 2016). Son varios los modelos de enseñanza que podrían compartir dichas premisas, tales como el MED (Metzler, 2017). Se busca, por tanto, experiencias metodológicas que impulsen prácticas pedagógicas constructivas y positivas con intervenciones basadas en modelos didácticos de enseñanza (Metzler, 2017) o basados en la práctica activa ([MsBP: Models-Based Practice]) (Casey, 2014). Estos modelos pedagógicos desarrollados de manera segura y contextualizada (MED) (Casey & MacPhail, 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2018; Siedentop et al., 2020) frente a modelos educativos tradicionales y descontextualizados (e.g., MT-ID: modelo tradicional de Instrucción Directa) (Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019) serán más motivantes para el alumnado y mejorarán significativamente la práctica de los contenidos físicos y deportivos, así como, las relaciones intra e interpersonales de los estudiantes (Gil-Arias et al., 2017).

El MED establece que, frente a prácticas deportivas competitivas desarrolladas de forma negativa por el alumnado (e.g., en la que solo unos pocos adquieren el aprendizaje deportivo), se debería impulsar experiencias deportivas reales y plenas que incluyeran a todo el alumnado de forma inclusiva (Siedentop, 1994). Asimismo,

autores como Contreras et al. (2017) apuntan que con el vigente modelo de enseñanza (MED) los estudiantes podrán vivenciar y comprender el deporte educativo de una forma más beneficiosa pedagógicamente (e.g., con aprendizajes cooperativos) y en todas sus dimensiones (e.g., uso de roles de responsabilidad de forma individual: jugador; y de forma colectiva o grupal: árbitro, entrenador personal, periodista, etc.). La UNESCO (2015) informa que las prácticas de actividades físicas y deportivas saludables y activas, con el juego o deporte organizado y contextualizado, como las planificadas y desarrolladas en el MED e instrumentalizadas con la EFC, muestran un impacto positivo en el ajuste psicosocial del alumnado, así como, en su dimensión emocional, física y cognitiva. Por tanto, el MED es un modelo pedagógico favorable para el desarrollo social proactivo, la responsabilidad positiva y aprendizajes más equitativos e inclusivos (Farias et al., 2019). Además, este modelo de enseñanza está respaldado por la literatura científica, apoyando la idea de que tiene un enfoque valioso y motivador para brindar experiencias activas y positivas al alumnado, desde los primeros cursos académicos hasta los años universitarios (Bessa et al., 2019, 2021; Evangelio et al., 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2018; Hastie et al., 2011; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019).

Por otro lado, el MED se presenta como un modelo de enseñanza curricular centrado en un proceso de enseñanza y aprendizaje donde el alumnado adquiere un rol protagonista (Bessa et al., 2021; Kirk, 2013). Es decir, los estudiantes adquieren un papel activo y participativo, implicándose cooperativamente en el aprendizaje, a través de metodologías motivantes (e.g., aprendizajes constructivos, significativos y cooperativos). El MED favorece que el alumnado se implique activamente en el proceso de aprendizaje (Kirk, 2013), con la utilización de diferentes roles deportivos de responsabilidades y con el uso de las tomas de decisiones autónomas y/o grupales (González-Víllora et al., 2009).

Diferentes autores (Bessa et al., 2021; Siedentop et al., 2020) señalan que el MED pretende impulsar en el alumnado diferentes aspectos, tales como: (a) habilidades competentes (e.g., habilidades técnico-tácticas que capaciten a la participación efectiva del juego deportivo); (b) la alfabetización física (e.g., ser conscientes de las reglamentación y tradición deportiva, así como de las positivas y negativas prácticas deportivas, para un juego limpio, respetuoso y tolerante); (c) ser deportistas entusiastas (e.g., motivación para preservar una significativa cultura

educativa y deportiva). En este sentido, con la implementación de modelos de enseñanzas positivas (e.g., el MED), se promueven en el contexto escolar, sinergias significativas entre prácticas física-deportivas y la salud física y psicosocial, aspecto clave que en el ámbito de la investigación educativa actual viene despertando gran interés (Bessa et al., 2021; Eime et al., 2013; O'Reilly et al., 2018; Rodríguez-Ayllon et al., 2019).

2.2.1. Conceptualización del modelo de Educación Deportiva

El MED fue diseñado en Ohio (Estados Unidos) por Daryl Siedentop en los años ochenta y publicado formalmente en la siguiente década (Siedentop, 1994). Tal y como exponen Contreras et al. (2017), se diseñó un modelo de enseñanza que permitiría al alumnado, independientemente de su nivel de competencia, vivenciar experiencias deportivas auténticas y plenas, desarrollando diferentes estrategias y metodologías pedagógicas, constituyendo un todo didáctico con un relevante potencial educativo.

El MED es un modelo curricular y de enseñanza, que se entiende dentro de un marco pedagógico e inclusivo, cuyos principales objetivos en el alumnado son: (1) vivenciar experiencias físicas y deportivas reales, simulando una auténtica estructura y organización del deporte, es decir, practicar de forma real e inclusiva un deporte contextualizado (e.g., contexto deportivo institucionalizado y reglamentado). Todo ello, adaptado al contenido curricular y educativo de la materia de Educación Física; (2) adquirir competencia, entusiasmo y cultura físico-deportiva (Siedentop et al., 2020). Es decir, el MED (Siedentop, 1994) pretende desarrollar un alumnado deportista competente, entusiasta y alfabetizado físicamente (Whitehead, 2010) y deportivamente (Kolovelonis & Goudas, 2018).

En este sentido, el MED promueve una pedagogía constructiva, motivante y cooperativa centrada en el alumnado como sujeto activo (Kirk, 2013), en contraposición a las experiencias deportivas repetitivas, automatizadas y memorísticas, desarrolladas en una Educación Física basada en modelos Tradicionales de Instrucción Directa (MT-ID) (Metzler, 2017; Pan et al., 2019), donde el profesorado (con un rol activo, unidireccional y expositivo) realiza una enseñanza directiva, dibujando un escenario educativo de aplicación práctica centrado en él. Autores como Siedentop et al. (2020) indican que el MED es un modelo pedagógico

basado en la organización de grupos de trabajo colaborativo o equipos de juego mixtos y homogéneos. Estos equipos de trabajo, que serán permanentes o constantes en el proceso de aprendizaje, con el fin de favorecer la identidad o afiliación de equipo, trabajarán cooperativamente para la obtención de objetivos comunes. Asimismo, los alumnos/as trabajaran los contenidos conceptuales, procedimentales y actitudinales curriculares con Unidades Didácticas (en adelante UUDD) de mayor duración que en los MT-ID, denominadas por el MED como Temporadas. Todo ello, mediante diferentes roles de responsabilidad deportiva, creándose climas de aula significativos y positivos para los procesos de enseñanza y aprendizaje.

En general, el MED fue diseñado para vivenciar y simular en el entorno escolar las características esenciales del contexto deportivo institucionalizado. Del mismo modo, y de forma más concreta, los contenidos teóricos y prácticos de aprendizaje en el MED, se estructuran metódicamente para resaltar procesos pedagógicos que promueven un aprendizaje y sociabilización eficaz del alumnado, tales como: aprendizaje cooperativo; resolución de problemas; reflexión crítica; e interdependencia positiva del alumnado (Siedentop et al., 2020). Por otro lado, debido a la variedad y complejidad de los contenidos y actividades de aprendizaje aplicados en las sesiones, desde un punto de vista estructural, este modelo necesita desarrollar UUDD o Temporadas de larga duración (e.g., programas o intervenciones con un rango de duración entre 16-18 sesiones). En este sentido, la implementación de experiencias físicas y deportivas instrumentalizadas con el MED, ofrece a la población infantil y adolescente una Educación Deportiva con una positiva visión pedagógica en diferentes aspectos, tales como: (1) recreación real y auténtica del contexto deportivo reglamentado (e.g., pretemporadas, partidos amistosos, actas e informes de partidos, liga deportiva formal, reglamento deportivo, equipos, etc.); (2) competición regular y formal (formato Round Robin: enfrentamientos en liga por equipos), simulando un proceso y sistema de competición real deportivo, que se aplica como un recurso educativo funcional permitiendo un desarrollo personal (e.g., conocimiento táctico y del rendimiento del juego deportivo) y social (e.g., enfatizar entre equipos el juego limpio y tolerante, así como, ser respetuoso con el oponente); (3) juegos deportivos inclusivos, fomentando valores como la igualdad de oportunidades, donde el alumnado desarrollará los deportes con participación equilibrada en equipos mixtos mediante la construcción de formas de juego competitivas auténticas y significativas;

(4) el alumno/a como un sujeto educativo activo con un rol protagonista en el proceso de enseñanza y aprendizaje, favorecido por el trabajo grupal y cooperativo que, a su vez, promueve el desarrollo de competencias socioemocionales.

2.2.2. Finalidades del modelo de Educación Deportiva

Siedentop (1994) presenta en el MED tres metas fundamentales para lograr un alumnado deportista en todas sus dimensiones:

- **Competente:** se refiere a que el alumno/a tiene una plena habilidad para poder participar en los juegos deportivos de forma significativa, comprensiva y reflexiva, llevando a cabo estrategias adecuadas según la complejidad del deporte. Se obtiene un deportista con capacidad para desarrollar el juego de forma completa, exitosa y con un nivel de desarrollo eficaz, llevando a cabo positivamente estrategias y habilidades técnicas y tácticas.
- **Culto:** es el alumno/a que valora y comprende el deporte en todos sus dominios, tanto estructurales referido a la reglamentación deportiva (e.g., distinguir entre prácticas deportivas positiva o negativa; juego limpio y respetuoso con el oponente; etc.), como culturales (tradición y rituales deportivos). Del mismo modo, el alumnado llega a ser un espectador o aficionado que vive y disfruta la experiencia deportiva de forma activa y participativa.
- **Entusiasta:** se refiere a la vivencia deportiva del alumnado dentro de la comunidad educativa de forma significativa, fomentando un respetuosa y tolerante cultura basada en el juego limpio en un contexto educativo integral (comunidad, centro, aula). En este sentido, los estudiantes se comprometen con los valores positivos del deporte: (a) promoviendo una visión significativa de la cultura deportiva; (b) generalizando la experiencia físico-deportiva de forma inclusiva a otros contextos socioculturales.

En definitiva, el MED plantea en el contexto educativo la finalidad de experimentar de forma significativa una experiencia física y deportiva real y educativa, pretendiendo enganchar y motivar al alumnado en el proceso de enseñanza y aprendizaje mediante estrategias, recursos y metodologías pedagógicas positivas centradas en intra e intergrupos, tales como: (1) aprendizaje cooperativo; (2) interdependencia positiva; (3) toma de decisiones de forma responsable; (4)

habilidades intra e interpersonales; (5) autogestión y autonomía; (6) role-playing con el desarrollo de roles de responsabilidad individuales y grupales, facilitando vivenciar la experiencia deportiva desde diferentes dimensiones o puntos de vista; (7) utilización de técnicas de modificación de conductas como refuerzos positivos y negativos; (8) una competición regular, formal, saludable y significativa (e.g., juego limpio, respeto y tolerancia hacia el equipo oponente); (9) autoconstrucción por parte del alumnado de sus propios recursos o materiales didácticos (e.g., aros móviles de juego, premios, medallas, diplomas, trofeos, etc.) (Antonio Méndez-Giménez et al., 2016); (10) sesiones festivas como el evento final, que hacen más significativo el desarrollo personal y social de los adolescentes (Bessa et al., 2019); etc.

Imagen 1. Sesiones de autoconstrucción de materiales didácticos para el desarrollo de los programas basados en el MED (Fuente: fotografía de elaboración propia; Luna, P.).

2.2.3. Características esenciales del modelo de Educación Deportiva

Autores como Contreras et al. (2017) señalan tres características claves del MED “preservación de la esencia del deporte, adaptación del contenido deportivo y favorecimiento de estrategias educativas que promueven el aprendizaje social y significativo” (p. 216). Del mismo modo, para obtener experiencias deportivas auténticas y educativas, es primordial impulsar el diseño, desarrollo y evaluación de modelos pedagógicos (e.g., MED) que fomenten características significativas, convirtiendo las prácticas físico-deportivas en manifestaciones activas, positivas, motivantes y participativas en el alumnado. En este sentido, Siedentop (1994) expone seis rasgos esenciales que el MED debe considerar:

- **Temporada.** En el MED las UDD curriculares de Educación Deportiva son designadas como *temporadas*, en relación con las UDD curriculares tradicionales de EF. Estas temporadas tienen la característica de desarrollarse como UDD curriculares de larga o mayor duración (e.g., implementación en la presente tesis doctoral de programas o intervenciones con 16-18 sesiones) con respecto a las UDD curriculares habituales en EF. Asimismo, la temporada se estructura en las siguientes fases: (1) inicial (fase previa de organización); (2) pretemporada (fase de preparación de la competición); (3) fase de competición (regular y formal); y (4) fase final. En este sentido, las sesiones se diseñaron y desarrollaron siguiendo una organización deportiva de competitividad positiva y educativa, basada en una competición regular, formal, saludable y significativa (i.e., juego limpio, respeto y tolerancia hacia el equipo o jugadores oponentes).
- **Afiliación.** Consiste en organizar al alumnado en grupos de trabajo cooperativo y sociabilizador; con un aprendizaje participativo; y la administración de un juego positivo en equipo, mantenidos a lo largo de toda la temporada. Se impulsa el valor deportivo de pertenencia de equipo, adquiriendo el alumnado una significativa identidad de grupo y positiva cooperación interpersonal. En este sentido, los grupos de aula o equipos de trabajo se seleccionan y agrupan de forma heterogénea (en relación al género y habilidades motrices), en función de metodologías de aprendizaje cooperativo y colaborativo. Estos equipos cooperativos se mantendrán constantes a lo largo de toda la temporada para favorecer el desarrollo de objetivos y/o metas comunes, potenciando en el contexto escolar el sentimiento de identidad o pertenencia de grupo.
- **Competición formal.** como un rasgo relevante para la experiencia práctica y conocimiento técnico-táctico de la actividad física y deportiva. En el MED la competición es real y se desarrolla como una auténtica experiencia deportiva donde se introducen aspectos relevantes, funcionales y motivantes de una

Imagen 2. Ejemplo de un equipo o grupo de trabajo cooperativo, organizado para desarrollar las sesiones de uno de los programas educativos basado en el MED. (Fuente: fotografía de elaboración propia; Luna, P.).

temporada deportiva y competición formal para el alumnado. Contreras et al. (2017) exponen que en el MED la competición se utiliza “con finalidad de vivencia auténtica del deporte, pero también por su alto potencial motivador y promoción del aprendizaje. La competición es también un contexto de gran riqueza en interacciones sociales, por lo que proporciona numerosos momentos de enseñanza” (p. 217).

- *Registro de datos.* Se trata de la recogida de información y análisis del proceso de aprendizaje, es decir, proceso de evaluación y anotación del rendimiento y conocimiento deportivo, así como de las conductas o comportamientos relacionadas con las metas perseguidas, ayudando positivamente al profesorado y alumnado en la evaluación continua y formativa del proceso de enseñanza y aprendizaje. En el MED estos registros se desarrollan a través de elementos, tales como: retroalimentaciones positivas; recursos o plataformas virtuales educativas o webs sociales (e.g., blog educativo o edublog); paneles o tabloneros en las aulas; pizarras virtuales; etc.
- *Festividad.* Ambiente festivo a través de simbología educativa (e.g., canciones, himnos, etc.); rituales (e.g., darse la mano, fotos grupales, etc.); y celebración deportiva (e.g., entrega de premios, trofeos, diplomas autoconstruidos, etc.). En esta línea, el MED evoluciona hacia un óptimo clima de aula festivo y didáctico, mediante un ambiente de celebración de los logros individuales y colectivos con la entrega de diferentes refuerzos (positivos o negativos) o premios educativos. En los programas de la vigente tesis, los premios (e.g., trofeos, diplomas, medallas) son fabricados de forma autoconstruida por los estudiantes. Por tanto, los rituales mostrados en el MED, como la utilización de mascotas, himnos, cánticos de apoyo, colores de equipo, customización de materiales, son algunas evidencias de esta festividad (Contreras et al., 2017; Siedentop et al., 2020).
- *Eventos culminantes.* Incluye el evento final, entrega de premios y una celebración final, así como el desarrollo de los objetivos finales con carácter festivo y motivante. En la presente tesis, los programas desarrollaron eventos culminantes con celebraciones organizadas por el propio alumnado (i.e., eventos finales desarrollados por el alumnado con el rol de responsabilidad denominado comité de fiesta). Contreras et al. (2017) apuntan que el MED se

estructura de esta forma para que “el alumnado sepa que todo el proceso acabará en una fiesta en la que todos participaran” (p. 217).

Otra característica relevante de los programas educativos implementados en la presente tesis doctoral, es la asignación y utilización de roles rotatorios de responsabilidad. El alumnado tenía siempre asignado dos roles de responsabilidad dentro del equipo: uno común a todos (rol de *jugador* activo y participativo) y otros específicos, tales como: (a) rol de *árbitro*: responsable del registro del tiempo, las actas e informes de partido, además de cumplimentar la normativa reglamentaria del juego (poniendo énfasis en el juego limpio, así como en el respeto y tolerancia con el oponente). La función arbitral constituía un rol rotatorio de responsabilidad de equipo, desarrollado al menos una vez por cada equipo durante la fase de competición formal. Este rol jugó un papel clave en el alumnado mejorando la comprensión del juego limpio y fomentando la empatía del estudiante con el equipo arbitral cuando actuaban como jugadores; (b) rol de *manager*: es el capitán de equipo, cuyas funciones son la de coordinador y mediador del grupo, además de actuar como nexo comunicativo entre profesorado-alumnado y viceversa; (c) rol de *periodista*: encargado de las estadísticas, información deportiva, registro de datos y de gestionar junto con el profesorado la comunicación virtual o digital (e.g., blog educativo o edublog); (d) rol de *preparador físico*: función de diseñar, dirigir y controlar los calentamientos físico-deportivos previos y finales en las sesiones prácticas, además de ser responsable del material deportivo utilizado; y (e) rol de *comité de festejo*: responsable de los materiales autoconstruidos, coordinador y encargado de los eventos festivos finales.

Imagen 3. Desarrollo de una sesión activa de estiramientos, dirigida por una alumna que tiene designado el rol de responsabilidad de preparadora física (Fuente: fotografía de elaboración propia; Luna, P.).

Esta estrategia educativa de juego de roles rotatorios, pretende favorecer en el alumnado el desarrollo de habilidades sociales como la empatía, dotándoles de funciones y visiones diferentes.

Por otro lado, en el diseño, validación y descripción de los programas aplicados en los manuscritos de la presente tesis, así como para la aplicación eficaz del MED, las intervenciones educativas implementadas en alumnado de Educación Primaria y de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria siguieron de manera precisa y adecuada las recomendaciones de Hastie & Casey (2014): (a) elementos curriculares significativamente detallados; (b) validación detallada de la implementación del modelo; y (c) una pormenorizada explicación del contexto del programa.

2.2.4. Programas educativos para alumnado de Educación Primaria y Educación Secundaria Obligatoria: intervenciones aplicadas en el contexto educativo

Los programas educativos (físico-deportivos) implementado en la presente tesis doctoral, fueron desarrollados como contenido curricular de Educación Deportiva en la asignatura de EF, para alumnado de Educación Primaria (EP) y Secundaria (ESO) (rango de edad del alumnado entre 10-15 años). El trabajo de investigación se desarrolló con intervenciones educativas sobre niños/as y adolescentes, organizados en: (a) grupo experimental (GE), se aplicó intervenciones basadas en el MED (Siedentop et al., 2020); y (b) grupo control (GC), intervenciones fundamentadas en el MT-ID (Metzler, 2017). Los programas fueron aplicados en las clases de EF de forma simultánea por docentes tutores y por especialistas en Educación Física y Educación Deportiva. Se utilizó un deporte de equipo de cancha dividida o red (denominado Ringo polaco) para los grupos de intervención (Méndez-Giménez et al., 2011). Este deporte modificado, fue novedoso para el alumnado participante, favoreciendo una práctica igualitaria en el desarrollo de sus habilidades técnicas y tácticas deportivas. Asimismo, este deporte alternativo se juega por equipos en una cancha deportiva dividida en dos por una red central de voleibol. Los jugadores deben lanzar, recepcionar y pasar un aro móvil (denominado aro de ringo) por encima de la red, consiguiendo puntuar cuando el aro cae en el suelo del terreno contrario (**Figura 3**).

Figura 3. Modalidad del deporte Ringo (polaco) en formación 2 vs. 2 (Fuente: Méndez Giménez, 2005).

A continuación, se muestra secuenciaciones de los contenidos y actividades de las sesiones en las intervenciones o programas educativos para niños/as y adolescentes, aplicados a los diferentes grupos participantes (GE: grupo experimental; y GC: grupo control) por niveles educativos y edades (consultar **Figuras 4-6**):

- **Programa educativo aplicado en alumnado de Educación Primaria (EP) (participantes de 10-12 años):**

SESSION	Intervention with Sport Education Model (SEM) (Experimental Group)	Intervention with Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) (Control Group)
1-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of the SEM, the sport developed by teams (Polskie ringo), and the roles of responsibility, with digital and audiovisual support (ICT). • Explanation and delivery to the students of the teaching material that will be used (e.g., personalized folders with educational themes, party minutes, contingency contracts, party reports, etc.). • Organization and division of teams in a random way. The working groups were permanent with the assignment of team names following a didactic and transversal theme (e.g., characters from the Quixotic literature). • Designation and random distribution of responsibility roles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation and explanation by the teachers of the teaching unit implemented with the Polskie ringo. • General explanation of the educational intervention to students: objectives, content, and evaluation of the teaching unit. • Distribution of students individually, in pairs, and in small groups (no permanent working groups are established).
3-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theoretical explanation with a digital whiteboard (audiovisual) of how the students will carry out the self-construction of the materials applied in the intervention (e.g., Polskie ringo rings, trophies, medals, etc.). • Practical explanation from the faculty on how to make such materials (e.g., Polskie ringo rings, certificates, etc.). • Construction by the students (self-construction) of the materials in a cooperative way (permanent groups/work teams). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instructional and direct introduction and explanation by teachers of: (a) the general and specific characteristics of the operation of the game (Polskie ringo); (b) the regulations of the Polskie ringo; and (c) sport equipment used and provided by the school. • Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and rote): displacement I-II.

5-8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial warm-up and final stretching in each session (directed by the students with the coach role). These tasks should be applied through reduced and modified physical activity and sport games. Practical team sessions to learn essential technical-tactical skills in the game of the Polskie ringo (displacement, coordination, pass, reception, serve, etc.). Functional application of roles in the different active, participative, and cooperative tasks carried out by the teams (e.g., captain: in the game of attack and defense; referee: in the rules of the game). Sessions ended with interactive assemblies for reflection and understanding (teacher-students and vice versa), to work, for example, positive feedback, active listening and error-learning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher-directed technical warm-up and stretching. Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and memoiristic): coordination I-II. Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and memoiristic): pass and reception I and II. Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and memoiristic): catch, serve, and throw. The teachers, during the development of the practical activities, gave instructions to the participants on how to correct and improve motor behavior.
9-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training team sessions with friendly Polskie ringo games through educational competition (emphasis on fair play and respect for the opponent). Responsibility role training (e.g., referee). Development of authentic sport elements (e.g., match minutes; interviews; etc.). Formal competition: 5 vs. 5 league format (Round Robin). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Warm-ups and stretches directed by the teachers. Tactical skill practice session 1 vs. 1 Tactical skill practice session 2 vs. 2. Throw and reception activities between rotating pairs. Simultaneous Polskie ringo games by rotating pairs.
16-17	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formal competition (semifinal and final): 5 vs. 5 league format (Round Robin). Continuous and formative evaluation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual practical evaluation (technical-tactical learning acquired).
18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Celebration of the final event (organized by the role of celebration committee). Educational prizes, trophies, certificates, and medals were presented, made by the students themselves. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theoretical individual evaluation.

Figura 4. Tabla con la estructura y organización de las sesiones (UDD de larga duración: 18 sesiones) y contenidos en las intervenciones físico-deportivas para alumnado de Educación Primaria, implementadas en ambos grupos participantes (GE: intervención basada en el MED; y GC: intervención basada en el MT-ID) (Fuente: Luna, Rodríguez-Donaire, et al., 2020).

- Programas educativos aplicados en alumnado de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria (ESO) (participantes de 12-15 años):

Stage	Session	Sport Education Model
Initial (Theoretical Sessions)	1-2	Introduction and presentation of the Sport Education Model with digital and audio-visual support (ICT). Presentation and distribution of learning resources. Division and organisation of classroom groups in teams (assignment of team names with a didactic and cross curricular theme). Distribution and selection of responsibility roles.
	3	Explanation for the self-design of learning resources on digital format (ICT). Selection and assignment of anthems, badges, mascots and t-shirts representing a team.
Intermediate (Practical Sessions)	4-7	Practical implementation of the roles of each member of the teams. Learning of technical-tactical elements and abilities: kicking-off, catching, moving, throwing, defence and attack. Learning game rules.
	8-9	Warming-up, training and friendly matches. Meetings for comprehension and reflection with intervention of the responsibility roles.
	10-14	Regular stage competition (Round Robin).
Final (Practical Sessions)	15-16	Inter-class groups final competitions (final matches with class groups), final event, giving awards and diplomas.

Figura 5. Tabla con la estructura y organización de las fases, sesiones (UDD de larga duración: 16 sesiones) y actividades de la intervención físico-deportiva basada en el MED, para alumnado adolescente de ESO, implementada en el grupo experimental (GE) (Fuente: Luna et al., 2019).

Session	SEM (experimental group)	TM-DI (control group)
1	Theoretical explanation of SEM and Polskie ringo. Delivery of teaching material (folders; match records; reports; game rules; contingency contract, etc.).	Theoretical explanation of Polskie ringo (regulatory aspects).
2–3	Training and organization of teams (choice of thematic names, hymns/emblems, identifying colors, etc.). Designation of rotating responsibility roles. Self-construction of material by student art (e.g., Polskie ringo ring).	Organization of students individually or in pairs (no persistent work groups are formed). Presentation of sports equipment provided by the school. Technical development activities (pass, launch and reception I).
4–7	Warm-up and stretching with modified sports games, directed by the teacher and students (role of physical trainer). Activities (by teams and using rotating roles of responsibility) aimed at learning technical and tactical skills of Polskie ringo (pass, serve, reception, throwing, displacements). Reflective-comprehensive meetings (positive feedback; active listening; learning-error). Knowledge of rules through the real game (fair play = sport key element). Pre-season or training for the championship (educational competition).	Warm-up sessions led by the teacher. Activities to develop technical skills repetitively (pass and reception II). Technical development activities (serve). Technical development activities (throwing). Technical development activities (displacement). Completion with stretching exercises, led by the teacher. Also, the teacher instructs the students for the improvement of the movements developed.
8–14	Friendly team matches and educational competition (fair play) through a formal and regular league (Round Robin). Development of responsibility roles (e.g., referee, journalist, captain. . .). Use of real sports elements (minutes, interviews, etc.).	Sports warm-up. Tactical development activities 1 vs. 1. Tactical development activities 2 vs. 2. Tactical development activities 3 vs. 3. Simultaneous Polskie ringo games. Final stretching exercises led by the teacher.
15–16	Semi-final and final competition between classes. Event with final festival (organized by the role of committee): delivery of trophies, diplomas and medals (self-built materials). Summative or final evaluation.	Individual theoretical assessment of Polskie ringo (regulatory aspects). Individual practical evaluation of Polskie ringo (technical elements).

Figura 6. Tabla con sesiones (UDD de larga duración: 16 sesiones) y contenidos en las intervenciones educativas basadas en el MED (grupo experimental) y en el MT-ID (grupo control), aplicadas en alumnado adolescentes de ESO (Fuente: Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2020).

Imagen 4. Materiales curriculares desarrollados por el alumnado participante en las intervenciones educativas, basadas en el MED, con temática inspirada en la literatura de Don Quijote de la Mancha (e.g., carpetas y documentación personalizadas con temática quijotesca; libros de don Quijote de la Mancha adaptados a las edades de los escolares) (Fuente: fotografía de elaboración propia; Luna, P.).

Los programas de intervención fueron supervisados, gestionados y controlados por un equipo de investigadores externos, en línea con las sugerencias de Sinelnikov (2009): (1) contacto personal y comunicación virtual (síncrona y asíncrona) para examinar y subsanar posibles problemas surgidos durante el proceso de investigación psicoeducativa; (2) inspecciones aleatorias y regulares al centro educativo; y (3) análisis y verificación semanal del proceso de investigación. Por otro lado, en la fase pretest o inicial, antes de iniciar el proyecto de investigación con los programas de intervención en niños/as y adolescentes, se mantuvo (equipo de investigación) diferentes reuniones con el Equipo Directivo en los diferentes centros escolares participantes de la comunidad de Castilla-La Mancha, así como con el profesorado tutor y especialista de EF, responsables de las intervenciones. Todo ello, para establecer los principales objetivos, hipótesis y demás elementos curriculares y didácticos implementados en las sesiones de las intervenciones educativas. Del mismo modo, los docentes responsables del departamento de EF acordaron seleccionar el Ringo (polaco) como el deporte de equipo a implementar en los grupos de intervención: (a) grupos experimentales (aplicación de intervenciones basadas en el MED); y (b) grupos controles activos (aplicación de intervenciones basadas en el MT-ID).

Imagen 4. Grupo experimental practicando el deporte Ringo (polaco), desarrollando una sesión del programa basado en el MED (Fuente: fotografía de elaboración propia; Luna, P.).

2.3. Efectos del modelo de Educación Deportiva en el contexto educativo

El MED ha suscitado un relevante interés en los últimos años por parte de los investigadores y de los profesionales educativos. Muestra de ello son las diferentes revisiones sistemáticas publicadas en la literatura científica (e. g., Hastie et al., 2011; Wallhead & O'sullivan, 2005). En este sentido, en la revisión de Hastie et al. (2011) se confirmaron mejoras del modelo de enseñanza (MED) en: aptitud física, conocimiento, comprensión y habilidad técnico-táctica. En otras palabras, las mejoras incluían un aprendizaje efectivo en el juego deportivo, el desarrollo personal y social, las actitudes positivas y atractivas hacia la EF (e.g., el entusiasmo y el disfrute por la actividad físico-deportiva) y en valores educativos (e.g., respeto, afinidad, equidad, juego limpio, etc.). De igual forma, otras revisiones más recientes evidenciaron un impacto positivo del MED: (a) en el desarrollo cognitivo, físico, afectivo y social (Araújo et al., 2014; Bessa et al., 2019, 2021; Evangelio et al., 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2018); (b) en el desarrollo ético (Harvey et al., 2014); y (c) en indicadores motivacionales (Chu & Zhang, 2018). Más aún, autores como Sierra-Díaz et al. (2019) en su metaanálisis, muestran mejoras significativas del MED en motivación hacia la actividad física y deportiva, pertenencia y responsabilidad social, autonomía y organización deportiva.

Una revisión de la literatura científica muestra la escasez de estudios sobre intervenciones educativas en Educación Física, basadas en el MED, que evalúen los efectos de las variables objeto de estudio en la presente tesis doctoral. No obstante, el interés mostrado por la investigación en esta materia, plantea que sería lógico analizar los posibles efectos positivos o impacto del MED sobre estas variables. Partiendo de trabajos previos, a partir de una eficaz y eficiente implementación del modelo (González-Víllora et al., 2019; Hastie & Casey, 2014), se evidencian mejoras en diferentes niveles, tales como:

- **Dominio cognitivo, físico-motor o conductas motoras** (Araújo et al., 2019; Hastie, Sinelnikov, et al., 2009; Luna, Rodríguez-Donaire, et al., 2019; Pereira et al., 2015; Wahl-Alexander & Chomentowski, 2018). Asimismo, en este nivel específico, Bessa et al. (2021) en una reciente revisión sistemática, muestran un modelo pedagógico (MED) con efectos significativos en: (a) actividad motriz (e.g., Rocamora et al., 2019); (b) rendimiento técnico (e.g., Hastie et al., 2013;

Pereira et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2019); (c) rendimiento táctico o del juego (e.g., Pritchard et al., 2008); y (d) razonamiento y comprensión del contenido deportivo (e.g., Browne et al., 2004; Pereira et al., 2016).

- **Dominio afectivo o emocional** (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019; Luna, Rodríguez-Donaire, et al., 2020).
- **Dominio social** (Araújo et al., 2014; Kao, 2019; Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016; Pan et al., 2019; Perlman, 2010; Wallhead et al., 2013, 2014).
- **Dominio educativo o académico** (Kinchin et al., 2004; Puente-Maxera et al., 2018). Del mismo modo, el MED se ha revelado en el contexto escolar como un modelo de enseñanza significativo capaz de originar efectos positivos en indicadores sociopersonales (cooperación, empatía y autodisciplina) (Hastie et al., 2011), así como en indicadores de conocimiento académico físico (Farias et al., 2015; Ward et al., 2017) y deportivo (Browne et al., 2004; Pereira et al., 2015). Por tanto, la Educación Deportiva (en el contexto educativo) desde este eficaz modelo pedagógico, impulsa un entorno de aprendizaje beneficioso que fomenta en el alumnado un compromiso, tanto con los principales objetivos de la EF (Bessa et al., 2021; MacPhail et al., 2008), como con aspectos claves de enseñanza-aprendizaje físicos y deportivos, tales como: (a) aptitud deportiva (Hastie et al., 2011); (b) procesos de aprendizaje significativos (Araújo et al., 2014); (c) competencia, alfabetización y entusiasmo deportivo (Hastie & Wallhead, 2016); (d) resultados positivos en el aprendizaje físico-deportivo (Evangelio et al., 2018); (e) desarrollo personal y social en alumnado de EF (Bessa et al., 2019, 2021); y (d) espíritu deportivo o deportividad (Burgueño & Medina-Casabón, 2020).
- **Variables sociodemográficas:**
 - a) *Nivel género*: es necesario señalar que existen una preconcepción estereotipada y/o discriminación deportiva en función del género (Leaper, 2011; Parker & Curtner-Smith, 2012). En esta línea, estudios previos sobre intervenciones basadas en el MED no han mostrado diferencias en su impacto, en función del género, en habilidades físicas (Araújo et al., 2019) y en habilidades socioemocionales (Evangelio et al., 2018). Por el contrario, otras investigaciones han evidenciado

diferencias en el impacto del MED, en función del género, donde algunos estudios concluyen que los chicos presentan mejoras más elevadas que las chicas en interacciones sociales (Brock et al., 2009; Hastie, Sinelnikov, et al., 2009). Mientras que otras investigaciones confirman mejoras más significativas en chicas que en chicos en conocimientos deportivos técnico-tácticos (Mesquita et al., 2012).

- b) *Niveles académico y edad*: se han analizados diferentes estudios previos, donde el vigente modelo de enseñanza (MED) ha mostrado efectos beneficiosos con un impacto positivo en: (1) niñas y niños de Educación Primaria (consultar **Tabla 1**); (2) adolescentes de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria (consultar **Tabla 2**); y (3) alumnado universitario (consultar **Tabla 2**). En esta línea, otros trabajos de investigación han resaltado la relevancia de investigar el impacto de intervenciones basadas en el MED en niños/as de edades tempranas (Layne & Hastie, 2015, 2016). Del mismo modo, autores como Bessa et al. (2021) señalan en su reciente revisión sistemática crítica del MED, que hay escasos estudios de investigación en Educación Primaria, que compare específicamente intervenciones basadas en el MED con intervenciones basadas en MT-ID. En este sentido, en la vigente tesis doctoral se busca responder a las necesidades de investigar el impacto del MED en estos niveles (curso académico y edad).
- c) *Nivel organización deportiva*: en línea con algunas revisiones sistemáticas (Araújo et al., 2014; Bessa et al., 2019, 2021; Hastie et al., 2011), se expone que la disposición o distribución deportiva: (a) de forma individual; o (b) de forma grupal, es un aspecto clave en el ámbito educativo. De esta forma, los deportes de equipo (e.g., ringo polaco) adquieren más importancia en la literatura científica que los practicados de forma individual (e.g., atletismo).

Por otro lado, de forma más concreta, resultados empíricos actuales en investigación, han confirmado que intervenciones basadas en el MED, muestran un impacto positivo en variables psicosociales, tales como: (1) *procesos motivacionales* (Chu & Zhang, 2018; Cuevas et al., 2016; Gil-Arias et al., 2017); (2) *necesidades psicológicas básicas* (Cuevas et al., 2015; Knowles et al., 2018; Méndez-Giménez et

al., 2015; Perlman, 2010, 2011); (3) *cohesión, habilidad y relación social* (Kao, 2019; Pan et al., 2019; Perlman, 2010); (4) *asertividad* (García-López & Gutiérrez, 2015); (5) *inteligencia emocional rasgo y mediadores motivacionales* (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2017); (6) *disminución de conductas pasivas, de agresividad, actitudes hacia la violencia*, así como mejoras en la *responsabilidad social y relaciones de amistad* (Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016); (7) *bienestar subjetivo* (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019; Luna, Rodríguez-Donaire, et al., 2020); (8) *competencia social y ajuste psicosocial* (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2020); (9) *cooperación, competencia y relaciones sociales* (Viciano et al., 2020); (10) *amistad* (Rocamora et al., 2019); (11) *aceptación social entre iguales y autoeficacia* (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2020; Luna, Rodríguez-Donaire, et al., 2019; Pan et al., 2019); y (12) *ansiedad social* (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019).

A continuación, se reportan las siguientes tablas donde se muestran diferentes estudios previos, que evaluaron el impacto o efectos de intervenciones basadas en el MED sobre diferentes variables psicológicas en: (a) alumnado de Educación Primaria (ver **Tabla 1**); (b) alumnado adolescente y universitario (ver **Tabla 2**); y (c) revisiones sistemáticas y meta-análisis (ver **Tabla 3**).

Tabla 1. Impacto de intervenciones basadas en el modelo de Educación Deportiva en niños y niñas.

Autor / año	Participantes / Muestra	Variables	Análisis de datos / tamaño del efecto	Resultados	Origen / Revista / Indexación (JCR)
Araujo et al. (2019)	- n = 18 (8 niñas; 10 niños); - Estudiantes de 11-13 años (M = 11.8)	Índice de rendimiento de juego deportivo (impacto en género, habilidad y tiempo de habilidades físico-deportivas).	Regresión lineal; modelos lineales jerárquicos; criterio de información de Akaike (AIC); criterio de información Bayesiana (BIC); prueba de Wald; Instrumento de evaluación de rendimiento del juego (GPAI).	Efectos positivos en conducta motora y habilidades físico-deportivas.	Portugal / European Physical Education Review (EPER) /
García-López y Gutiérrez (2015)	- Muestra total (n = 154) (76 niños; 78 niñas). - Estudiantes de 11 a 12 años (n = 132)	Habilidades sociales: empatía; pasividad; asertividad; y agresividad.	Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); t de Student; ANOVA; eta-cuadrado parcial (η^2).	Mejoras significativas en asertividad.	España / Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy /
González-Villora et al. (2019)	- Alumnado de Educación Primaria (n = 112). - Estudiantes de 6-12 años (edad media: 9,35 ± 1,76).	Rendimiento físico (distancia recorrida, velocidad y número de sprints); y factores fisiológicos (e.g., frecuencia cardiaca, calorías).	Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); prueba de Kolmogorov-Smirnov; prueba k Kappa; prueba t de Student; en comparación con el grupo control activo.	Mejoras en el grupo experimental en el rendimiento físico y factores fisiológico.	España / Frontiers in Physiology /
Knowles et al. (2018)	- Muestra total (n = 6). - Alumnado de 6º de Educación Primaria (11-12 años).	Motivación [Trans-Contextual Model of Motivation]; necesidades psicológicas básicas; influencia de la Educación Deportiva y como ser físicamente activo con la elección de deportes durante el recreo escolar.	Estudio de casos (diseño cualitativo) en Educación Física y recreo escolar: Focus groups (n = 8), entrevistas individuales semiestructuradas (n = 40) y notas de campo u observaciones (n = 40) durante 10 semanas.	Los resultados revelaron que la Educación Deportiva (MED) fue eficaz para satisfacer las necesidades psicológicas básicas de los estudiantes de Educación Física y, específicamente, para promover la participación, autonomía y motivación del alumnado en el contexto deportivo y recreo escolar.	EEUU / Journal of Teaching in Physical Education /

Layne et al. (2015)	<p>- Participantes ($n = 40$) (niñas = 18; niños = 22).</p> <p>- Estudiantes de 4^o de Educación Primaria con una media de edad (M) de 9.72 años.</p>	<p>Si los niños/as de Educación Primaria son capaces de trabajar de forma independiente del profesor, así como, gestionar diferentes tareas de organización asociadas a la Educación Deportiva.</p>	<p>Análisis de varianza (ANOVA); método Holm's sequential Bonferroni; tamaños del efecto con las pruebas eta-cuadrado (η^2) y d de Cohen.</p>	<p>Resultado positivos y significativos en los niveles de ejecución de las tareas de gestión y de instrucción. Asimismo, los estudiantes fueron capaces de trabajar de forma autónoma e independiente del profesor, desarrollando eficazmente los objetivos en Educación Deportiva</p>	<p>USA / Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy /</p> <p>Q1</p>
Luna, Rodríguez-Donaire et al. (2020)	<p>- Muestra total ($n = 167$). Participantes ($n = 146$; GE: 87; GC: 59) (niñas = 79; niños = 67).</p> <p>- Estudiantes de 10-12 años ($M = 10.78$; $SD = 1.07$).</p>	<p>Bienestar subjetivo (afecto positivo y afecto negativo); ajuste psicosocial (depresión, ansiedad y estrés social).</p>	<p>Prueba de Kolmogorov-Smirnov; evidencia de fiabilidad con alfa de Cronbach (α); estadística descriptiva (M; SD); MANOVA; ANOVA; MANCOVA; ANCOVA; tamaño del efecto con el estadístico o prueba d de Cohen.</p>	<p>Mejoras significativas a favor del grupo experimental (MED) en comparación al grupo control (MT-ID) en: (a) afecto positivo; (b) afecto negativo; y (c) ansiedad. Es decir, se incrementa significativamente el afecto positivo y disminuye significativamente el afecto negativo y la ansiedad.</p>	<p>España / Sustainability/</p> <p>Q2</p>
Mesquita et al. (2012)	<p>- Muestra total ($n = 26$) (17 niñas; 9 niños).</p> <p>- Alumnado de Educación Primaria de 10 a 12 años.</p>	<p>Toma de decisiones; ejecución de habilidades; y rendimiento general del juego. Es decir, conocimientos deportivos técnico-tácticos; rendimiento y habilidades del juego deportivo.</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); prueba de Mann-Whitney; prueba de Wilcoxon; prueba de Corrección de Bonferroni.</p>	<p>Efectos positivos y ganancias en: habilidades físicas-deportivas; toma de decisiones tácticas; aprendizaje del juego deportivo en niñas y estudiantes con bajo nivel de destreza; y en aptitud física.</p>	<p>Portugal / European Physical Education Review (EPER) /</p> <p>Q2</p>
Perlam (2010)	<p>- Muestra total ($n = 1.176$) (niños: 624; niñas: 552).</p> <p>- Alumnado de Educación Primaria de 9-12 años.</p>	<p>Afecto y satisfacción de las necesidades psicológicas básicas de los estudiantes desmotivados en Educación Deportiva (disfrute, autonomía, competencia, relación, amotivación, afecto y necesidades de satisfacción).</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); evidencias de fiabilidad con Alfa de Cronbach; prueba de Levene; ANOVA; corrección de Bonferroni; tamaño del efecto con estadístico eta-cuadrado parcial (η^2).</p>	<p>Cambios significativos o ganancias en las percepciones de los estudiantes desmotivados sobre el disfrute y satisfacción de las relaciones sociales con el MED (e.g., ganancias positivas en relaciones sociales).</p>	<p>EEUU / Journal of Teaching in Physical Education /</p> <p>Q3</p>

<p>Rocamora et al. (2019)</p>	<p>- Muestra total (n = 88) con 44 niñas y 44 niños. Participantes GE (n = 47) y del GC (n = 41). Antropometría (peso, índice de Masa Corporal (IMC) y porcentaje de grasa corporal de los estudiantes); Niveles de intensidad de actividad física; rendimiento deportivo; y metas de amistad. 11.16; SD = 0.63). - Estudiantes de 10-12 años (M = 11.16; SD = 0.63).</p>	<p>- Muestra total (n = 166) (76 niños y 90 niñas). - Alumnado de 5º Educación Primaria (M = 10.9 años)</p>
<p>España / Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy / Q1</p>	<p>Los resultados mostraron que los estudiantes del grupo experimental (experimentaron el MED) tenían niveles significativamente más altos en: (a) actividad física ligera y moderada; (b) metas de acercamiento a la amistad; y (c) evitación de la amistad. Mientras que el grupo control (experimentaron el MT-ID) tenían niveles significativamente más altos en actividad física sedentaria. También se mostraron ganancias significativas en el rendimiento del juego de los estudiantes en ambos grupos, pero éstas fueron mayores con el MED.</p>	<p>Niveles de actividad física y deportiva; conocimiento y logro en "fitness"; resistencia cardiovascular aeróbica. Estadística descriptiva (M, SD); ANOVA; prueba de corrección Wilcoxon; tamaño del efecto con esta cuadrado parcial.</p>
<p>EEUU / Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport / Q2</p>	<p>Efectos positivos en actividad, conocimiento y rendimiento físico y deportivo. Los resultados indicaron un efecto de tiempo significativo para los test de "fitness" y de conocimientos físico-deportivos (instrucción, práctica libre o competición).</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M, SD); ANOVA; prueba de corrección Wilcoxon; tamaño del efecto con esta cuadrado parcial.</p>

Tabla 2. Impacto de intervenciones basadas en el modelo de Educación Deportiva en adolescentes y universitarios.

Autor / año	Muestra	Variables	Análisis de datos / tamaño del efecto	Resultados	Origen / Revista / Indexación (JCR)
Burgueño et al. (2020)	<p>- $n = 148$ (70 chicos; 78 chicas).</p> <p>- Estudiantes entre 16 y 18 años de edad ($M = 17.04$, $SD = 0.99$).</p>	<p>Deportividad u orientaciones sobre el espíritu deportivo (convenciones sociales; respeto a las reglas y árbitros; compromiso total; respeto al rival; enfoque negativo)</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); evidencias de fiabilidad con coeficiente Alfa de Cronbach; análisis multivariante de la varianza (MANOVA); Pillai's trace como una prueba estadística del análisis multivariado; tamaño del efecto con eta cuadrado parcial.</p>	<p>Mejoras significativas de la deportividad en alumnado adolescente de Educación Física, en los indicadores: nivel de respeto a las convenciones sociales, respeto a las reglas y a los árbitros, compromiso y respeto por los oponentes. No obstante, no hubo mejoras en el indicador de enfoque negativo.</p>	<p>España / International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health / Q1</p>
Cuevas et al. (2016)	<p>- Muestra total ($n = 86$; GE = 43; GC = 43) (49 chicas; 37 chicos).</p> <p>- Alumnado adolescente de ESO entre 15 y 17 años ($M = 15.65$; $SD = 0.78$).</p>	<p>Autodeterminación; motivación; necesidades psicológicas básicas; disfrute; y satisfacción con el MED. Específicamente se analizaron: regulación motivacional, motivación intrínseca, regulación identificada, regulación introducida, regulación externa, amotivación, índice de autodeterminación, competencia frustrante, autonomía frustrante, relación de frustración, satisfacción-disfrute, aburrimiento e intención en estar activo.</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); evidencias de fiabilidad con la prueba Alfa de Cronbach; análisis de varianza (ANOVA); prueba de Corrección de Bonferroni; y tamaño del efecto con la prueba eta cuadrado parcial (η^2).</p>	<p>Mejoras significativas en motivación intrínseca</p>	<p>España/ Kinesiology / Q4</p>

Farias et al. (2018)	<p>- Muestra total (n = 26) (10 chicas; 16 chicos). - Estudiantes adolescentes de ESO (M = 12.3; SD = 1.3).</p>	<p>Rendimiento físico-deportivo y participación deportiva durante diferentes intervenciones basadas en el modelo de Educación Deportiva.</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva; prueba de Shapiro-Wilks; ANOVA; tamaño del efecto con eta-cuadrado parcial (η^2).</p>	<p>Mejoras con incremento estadísticamente significativo en el rendimiento físico-deportivo de los deportes seleccionados; e incremento en la participación de los juegos deportivos.</p>	<p>Sur de Europa / Journal of Sports Science and Medicine / Q3</p>
García-López y Gutiérrez (2015)	<p>- Muestra total (n = 154) (76 niños; 78 niñas). - Adolescentes de 14 años (n = 22).</p>	<p>Habilidades sociales: Empatía; Pasividad; Asertividad; Agresividad</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); t de Student; ANOVA; eta-cuadrado parcial.</p>	<p>Mejoras significativas en</p>	<p>España/ Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy/ Q1</p>
Gil-Arías et al. (2017)	<p>- Participantes (n = 55) (chicas = 27; chicos = 28). - Estudiantes adolescentes de 15 a 16 años (M = 15,45; SD = 0,41).</p>	<p>Motivación autónoma; necesidades psicológicas básicas; distruite; e intención de ser físicamente activo.</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); prueba de Shapiro-Wilks; coeficiente alfa de Cronbach; MANOVA; MANCOVA; factor corrección Bonferroni; tamaño del efecto con estadístico eta cuadrado parcial (η^2).</p>	<p>Mejoras significativas en las variables: autonomía; competencia; y distruite. No obstante, en las variables motivación autónoma, relación e intención de ser físicamente activo no hubo mejoras. Todo ello muestra mayor motivación autónoma y, en consecuencia, una percepción de competencia en el alumno, una imagen positiva del deporte a practicar y, por tanto, mejora el distruite y la actividad física.</p>	<p>España / PLoS-One / Q1</p>
Hastie et al. (2014)	<p>- Participantes de zona rural (n = 21).</p>	<p>Clima motivacional en alumnado y profesorado (clima motivacional objetivo, clima motivacional</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); ANOVA; estadístico chi-cuadrado; Corrección de Bonferroni; tamaño del efecto con prueba d de Cohen</p>	<p>Mejoras y efectos positivos en el clima motivacional (objetivo, percibido y de dominio) de los estudiantes y</p>	<p>EEUU / European Physical Education</p>

	- Estudiantes adolescentes ($M = 15.9$ años de edad).	percibido, clima motivacional de maestría o dominio del docente).		docentes participantes en la enseñanza de deportes competitivos en Educación Física con el MED.	Review (EPER) / Q3
Kao (2019)	- Muestra total ($n = 117$). - GE = 59 (hombres: 18; mujeres: 41). GC = 58 (24 hombres y 34 mujeres). - Estudiantes universitarios GE ($M = 20,19$; $SD = 0,57$); y GC ($M = 20,53$; $SD = 1,10$).	Cohesión de equipo; interacción interpersonal; trabajo en equipo; adaptación en equipo; análisis de la talla, el peso y el índice de masa corporal. (IMC).	Estadísticas descriptivas (M ; SD); Chi-cuadrado; prueba t de Student; ANCOVA; tamaños del efecto con estadísticos d de Cohen y eta-cuadrado.	Mejoras significativas en cohesión de equipo y habilidades sociales	Taiwan / Sustainability (MDPI) / Q2
Luna et al. (2019)	- Muestra total ($n = 113$; GE = 69; GC = 44) (chicas: 49; chicos:64). - Estudiantes adolescentes de ESO de 12-15 años ($M = 13.82$, $SD = 0.79$).	Bienestar subjetivo (<i>cognitivo</i> : calidad de vida relacionada con la salud; <i>afectivo</i> : afecto positivo y afecto negativo); inteligencia emocional rasgo; y ansiedad social.	Estadística descriptiva (M ; SD); evidencias de fiabilidad: Cronbach's Alpha (α), Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE) y McDonald's omega coefficient (Ω); MANOVA; ANOVA; MANCOVA; ANCOVA; corrección Bonferroni; tamaños del efecto con eta-cuadrado parcial η^2).	Mejoras significativas en un indicador específico de bienestar subjetivo (afecto negativo) e inteligencia emocional de rasgos	España/ International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health (IJERPH) / Q1
Luna, Guerrero et al. (2020)	- Muestra total ($n = 114$). Participantes ($n = 106$; GE = 62; GC = 44) (Chicas: 55; Chicos: 51). - Alumnado adolescente de 12 a 15 años ($M = 13.41$; $SD = 0.81$).	Competencia social (<i>reevaluación cognitiva, ajuste social, conducta prosocial, autoeficacia social y ajuste normativo</i>); aceptación social entre iguales (<i>amable, acosador, cooperador, líder e índice aceptación social</i>); y diferencias significativas y efectos en los grupos, en función del género.	Estadística descriptiva (M ; SD); prueba de Kolmogorov-Smirnov; MANOVA; ANOVA; MANCOVA; ANCOVA; evidencias de fiabilidad: Alfa de Cronbach (α) y coeficiente omega de McDonald (Ω); tamaños del efecto con eta-cuadrado parcial (η^2).	Mejoras estadísticamente significativas, a favor del grupo experimental (MED) en comparación al grupo control (MT-ID): (1) en algunos indicadores de competencia social (<i>ajuste social, conducta prosocial y autoeficacia social</i>); y (2) aceptación social entre iguales (en el factor <i>cooperador</i> y en el <i>índice global de aceptación social entre iguales</i>).	España / Frontiers in Psychology / Q2

<p>Menéndez & Z-Santurio (2016)</p> <p>- Muestra total (n = 143) (GE: 78; GC: 65; Chicos: 69 y 74 chicas).</p> <p>- Adolescentes de 4º de la ESO de 14 a 17 años (M = 15.44; SD = 0.80).</p> <p>(relación).</p> <p>Actitudes hacia la violencia (violencia gratuita, violencia autoprotección y violencia general); responsabilidad (responsabilidad social y responsabilidad personal); metas de amistad (aproximación-amistad y evitación-amistad); y necesidades psicológicas básicas (competencia, autonomía y relación).</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M; SD) ANOVA (pre-test); MANCOVA (post-test); tamaños del efecto con la prueba d de Cohen.</p> <p>Mejoras significativas de las actitudes hacia la violencia, la responsabilidad social, la competencia y la relación de los participantes</p>	<p>Mejoras en autoeficacia deportiva, pasión deportiva, y rendimiento en el juego deportivo.</p>	<p>z-Santurio & Fernández-Río (2016)</p> <p>- Muestra total (n = 133) (GE = 75; 38 chicos y 37 chicas) (GC = 58; 30 chicos; 28 chicas).</p> <p>- Estudiantes adolescentes (M = 16.78; SD = 0.54).</p> <p>Variables evaluadas en las clases de Educación Física: autoeficacia deportiva; pasión deportiva; rendimiento juego; responsabilidad social; cohesión social; y rendimiento en el juego deportivo.</p>
<p>Pan et al. (2019)</p> <p>- Muestra total (n = 133) (GE = 75; 38 chicos y 37 chicas) (GC = 58; 30 chicos; 28 chicas).</p> <p>- Estudiantes adolescentes (M = 16.78; SD = 0.54).</p>	<p>Mejoras en autoeficacia deportiva, pasión deportiva, y responsabilidad y rendimiento en el juego deportivo. Del mismo modo, hubo beneficios en el aprendizaje en los dominios cognitivo, psicomotor y afectivo de los participantes de Educación Física.</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); MANCOVA; ANCOVA; tamaños del efecto con prueba eta-cuadrado (η^2).</p> <p>Mejoras significativas, a favor del grupo experimental (GE), de las diferencias significativas en resistencia cardiovascular aeróbica progresiva.</p>	<p>Wahl-Alexander & Chomentowski (2018)</p> <p>- Muestra total (n = 47). Participantes GE (n = 23; 12 hombres y 11 mujeres); y GC (n = 24; 11 hombres y 13 mujeres).</p> <p>- Estudiantes universitarios (M = 22 años en GE; M = 21.25 años en GC).</p>
<p>Taiwan / Sustainability / Q2</p> <p>Mejoras significativas de las actitudes hacia la violencia, la responsabilidad social, la competencia y la relación de los participantes</p>	<p>Estadística descriptiva (M; SD); prueba de Shapiro-Wilk test; ANOVA; M de Box; tamaño del efecto con el estadístico eta-cuadrado parcial (η^2).</p> <p>Mejoras significativas, a favor del grupo experimental (GE), de las diferencias significativas en resistencia cardiovascular aeróbica progresiva.</p>	<p>Mejoras significativas, a favor del grupo experimental (GE), de las diferencias significativas en resistencia cardiovascular aeróbica progresiva.</p>	<p>Alexander & Chomentowski (2018)</p> <p>- Muestra total (n = 47). Participantes GE (n = 23; 12 hombres y 11 mujeres); y GC (n = 24; 11 hombres y 13 mujeres).</p> <p>- Estudiantes universitarios (M = 22 años en GE; M = 21.25 años en GC).</p>

Tabla 3. Revisiones sistemáticas y Meta-análisis: impacto de intervenciones basadas en el modelo de Educación Deportiva.

Autor / año	Muestra	Variables	Selección de búsqueda	Resultados	Origen / Revista / Indexación (JCR)
Bessa et al. (2021)	<p>- Búsqueda inicial ($n = 1.722$). Artículos incluidos en la revisión sistemática crítica ($n = 28$).</p> <p>- Muestra de estudiantes de Educación Primaria, Secundaria, Bachillerato y universitarios de 6 a 22 años de edad.</p>	<p>Variables relacionadas con: (a) el desarrollo cognitivo y motor (e.g., <i>rendimiento deportivo, actividad física, habilidades tácticas-técnicas, conocimiento y competencia físico-deportivo, etc.</i>); y (b) habilidades personales, sociales y afectivas (e.g., <i>competencia social, bienestar subjetivo, ansiedad social, motivación, cohesión social, inteligencia emocional, etc.</i>) en estudiantes de Educación Física.</p>	<p>Base de datos: PubMed; Google Scholar; Web of Science; SCOPUS; Academic Search Ultimate; ERIC; Education Source; APA PsycINFO; y APA PsycARTICLES.</p>	<p>Mejoras con la aplicación del MED, en comparación con el MT-ID, en el desarrollo físico, cognitivo, social y afectivo del alumnado de Educación Física. Específicamente la revisión sistemática mostró resultados positivos en: (1) variables psicosociales y emocionales; (2) habilidades personales y socioemocionales; (3) rendimiento técnico-táctico en el juego deportivo; (4) conocimiento del contenido específico del deporte; (4) actividad física; etc.</p>	<p>Portugal y USA / Journal of Sports Science and Medicine / Q3</p>
Chu & Zhang (2018)	<p>- Búsqueda inicial ($n = 947$). Artículos incluidos en la revisión sistemática ($n = 18$).</p> <p>- Muestra total de estudiantes ($n = 2789$) (1412 niños; 1377 niñas)</p>	<p>Motivación y procesos motivacionales (Teoría de la Autodeterminación y Teoría de los Objetivos de Logro)</p>	<p>Base de datos: Academic Research Complete; ERIC; PsycINFO; SPORTDiscus; Web of Science.</p>	<p>Mejoras en aspectos motivacionales; influencia y promoción motivacional positiva</p>	<p>USA / European Physical Education Review (EPER) / Q2</p>

<p>Portugal / Movimento/</p>	<p>Mejoras en diferentes variables físicas, sociales y afectivas. De forma más específica, la presente revisión, con la implementación del MED, muestra en los participantes, mejoras en habilidades socio-emocionales. No obstante, en función del género, no se confirmaron diferencias significativas en los grupos de intervención.</p>	<p>Bases de datos: EBSCO host, ERIC, Google Scholar, SCOPUS, Medline, SPORTDiscus and Web of Science.</p>	<p>Evangelio et al. (2018) - Búsqueda inicial ($n = 6.856$). Artículos incluidos en revisión sistemática ($n = 38$). - Muestra de alumnado de Educación Primaria, Secundaria y Bachillerato de 6 a 18 años de edad. - Búsqueda inicial ($n = 49.533$). Artículos incluidos en revisión sistemática ($n = 20$). - Muestra de alumnado de Educación Primaria, Secundaria y Bachillerato de 6 a 18 años de edad en Educación Física.</p>
<p>España // European Physical Education Review (EPER) /</p>	<p>Mejoras en el desarrollo cognitivo, físico-deportivo, social y afectivo, del alumnado participante (6-18 años) en las intervenciones, basadas en el MED, implementadas en el contexto educativo.</p>	<p>Base de datos: Web of Science; Medline; SPORTDiscus (EBSCO); Scopus; ERIC (ProQuest); y Google Scholar.</p>	<p>González-Villora et al. (2018) - Búsqueda inicial ($n = 49.533$). Artículos incluidos en revisión sistemática ($n = 20$). - Muestra de alumnado de Educación Primaria, Secundaria y Bachillerato de 6 a 18 años de edad en Educación Física. - Búsqueda inicial ($n = 13.756.419$). Artículos incluidos en el Meta-análisis ($n = 14$); y en la revisión sistemática ($n = 33$). - Muestra de alumnado de Educación Primaria, Secundaria y Bachillerato de 6 a 18 años de edad en Educación Física.</p>
<p>España / Frontiers in Psychology /</p>	<p>Mejoras en motivación hacia la actividad física y compromiso con la práctica deportiva; pertenencia y responsabilidad social, autonomía y organización física y deportiva. En conclusión, se muestran programas efectivos que promuevan un estilo de vida activo y saludable en Educación Física y Deportiva.</p>	<p>Base de datos: Web of Science, SCOPUS, Medline, Google Scholar, SPORTDiscus, EBSCO-host, ERIC, PsycINFO y PubMed.</p>	<p>Sierra-Díaz et al. (2019) - Búsqueda inicial ($n = 13.756.419$). Artículos incluidos en el Meta-análisis ($n = 14$); y en la revisión sistemática ($n = 33$). - Muestra de alumnado de Educación Primaria, Secundaria y Bachillerato de 6 a 18 años de edad en Educación Física. - Búsqueda inicial ($n = 13.756.419$). Artículos incluidos en el Meta-análisis ($n = 14$); y en la revisión sistemática ($n = 33$). - Muestra de alumnado de Educación Primaria, Secundaria y Bachillerato de 6 a 18 años de edad en Educación Física.</p>

2.4. Variables dependientes objeto de estudio

Esta tesis doctoral evalúa las siguientes variables:

- **Bienestar subjetivo** [subjective well-being]: engloba dos componentes: el *cognitivo* (satisfacción con la vida) y el *afectivo* (afecto positivo y afecto negativo) (Diener, 2000; Diener et al., 1999; Diener & Biswas-Diener, 2008; Diener & Fujita, 1995). El *componente cognitivo* del bienestar subjetivo se refiere al resultado de la evaluación del procesamiento de la información que las personas hacen de sus vidas (Diener, 2000; Diener et al., 1999). Mientras que el *componente afectivo* del bienestar subjetivo implica un equilibrio individual hedonista, es decir, la frecuencia con que las personas experimentan emociones placenteras y/o no placenteras, en otras palabras, emociones de carácter positivo y/o negativo (Diener, 2000; Diener et al., 1999). En este sentido, en el presente estudio se han evaluado estos dos componentes del bienestar subjetivo.
- **Inteligencia emocional rasgo** [trait emotional intelligence]: diferentes investigaciones se han focalizado en el estudio de los efectos de variables psicológicas positivas en el desarrollo personal y social (Gable & Haidt, 2005). Estos estudios se han englobado bajo la perspectiva de la denominada Psicología Positiva (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). Una de las variables positivas que actualmente cuenta con más respaldo científico por sus estrechas relaciones con el bienestar y la salud física y mental es la inteligencia emocional (Martins et al., 2010; Sánchez-Álvarez et al., 2015; Zeidner et al., 2012). La inteligencia emocional puede definirse como el conjunto de diferencias individuales en la identificación, expresión, uso, comprensión y regulación de las propias emociones y las emociones de los demás (Brasseur et al., 2013). Probablemente, una gestión eficaz de las dimensiones que componen la inteligencia emocional promueva estados emocionales positivos y una reducción de los estados de ánimo negativos, logrando así un mayor sentido de bienestar y salud (Zeidner et al., 2012).
- **Ansiedad social** [social anxiety]: la ansiedad social puede definirse como el miedo constante de una persona a una o varias situaciones sociales o de actuación, en las que se expone a personas desconocidas o al posible

escrutinio de otras personas (Moran, 2016). La ansiedad social tiene un impacto negativo en el bienestar subjetivo de los jóvenes debido a la angustia que pueden sentir los individuos (Beidel et al., 2007) que a su vez puede afectar negativamente a la calidad de sus relaciones interpersonales (Cejudo et al., 2018; Inglés et al., 2010). Por tanto, variables como la ansiedad social inciden negativamente en el bienestar (Wersebe et al., 2018) y se relación con un mayor número de conductas de victimización en el bullying y el cyberbullying (Landoll et al., 2015).

- **Competencia social** [social competence]: Gómez-Ortiz et al. (2019) definen esta variable como la eficacia en la interacción social, que surge del uso de las habilidades socioemocionales para lograr objetivos personales a lo largo del tiempo y en diferentes situaciones. De esta manera, la competencia social engloba una serie de habilidades cognitivas, sociales y emocionales del individuo, para gestionar las relaciones interpersonales que se producen en diversos contextos, favoreciendo relaciones más saludables entre los demás (Del Prette & Del Prette, 2005). Del mismo modo, autores como Gresham (1988) divide la competencia social en los siguientes dominios: (1) conductas adaptativas (desarrollo físico y del lenguaje, competencias académicas y habilidades funcionales independientes); (2) conductas interpersonales (conductas cooperativas y de juego; habilidades de conversación y de aceptación normativa); (3) conductas autopercebidas (de sí mismo: expresar sentimientos y conductas éticas y positivas); y (4) conductas hacia la tarea (atención, resolución de tareas y trabajo individual). En este sentido, la competencia social está relacionada con el ajuste a las demandas del entorno escolar, las relaciones interpersonales, la salud emocional y la aceptación entre iguales (Losada et al., 2017).
- **Aceptación social entre iguales** [social acceptance among peers]: esta variable se refiere a la representación o reputación social de las personas, donde la personalidad constituye una valoración global de su sociabilidad (Losada et al., 2017). En este sentido, este constructo se podría definir como un conjunto de valoraciones o juicios mostrados sobre el alumnado, por sujetos sociales claves, entre los cuales se encuentran los pares o iguales (Losada et al., 2017). Estos representan un positivo entorno social de aprendizaje para las

habilidades y procesos interpersonales que son relevantes para la prevención, protección, adaptación y ajuste de los individuos a lo largo de su vida (Aron et al., 2012; García-Bacete et al., 2010). En esta línea, es importante resaltar que esta variable psicosocial se asocia significativamente con indicadores socioemocionales como la adaptación socioescolar y el bienestar (e.g., Smith & Hart, 2011) y la inteligencia emocional (e.g., Mavroveli & Sánchez-Ruiz, 2011; Petrides et al., 2006). Por otro lado, se relaciona negativamente con problemas afectivos y de conducta (e.g., Frederickson et al., 2012).

- **Ajuste psicosocial (indicadores de depresión, ansiedad y estrés social)** [psychosocial adjustment: Indicators of depression, anxiety, and social stress]: Rodríguez-Fernández et al. (2016) interpretan esta variable como una asociación de la adaptación escolar (o compromiso escolar) y el bienestar subjetivo. El constructo ajuste psicosocial hace referencia a la capacidad de las personas para adaptarse a las demandas del contexto social (Reynolds & Kamphaus, 2004). En este sentido, en los últimos años, se viene observando en los jóvenes un aumento considerable de problemas conductuales y adaptativos en el ámbito familiar y socioescolar, siendo motivo de preocupación tanto para las instituciones educativas como para la sociedad en general (Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2016). Por ello, sería clave que se promoviera un positivo ajuste psicosocial del alumnado con la finalidad de favorecer una adaptación saludable al entorno físico, psicológico, social y afectivo (Baker et al., 2003) convirtiéndose también, en un factor beneficioso para el bienestar personal y social (Bisquerra et al., 2015; Diener, 2000; Diener et al., 1999; Diener & Biswas-Diener, 2008).

En este sentido, UNESCO (2015) informa que la EFC, desarrollada con prácticas saludables y aplicadas con eficaces programas, intervenciones o experiencias físicas y deportivas mediante el juego y/o deporte contextualizado (e.g., como las desarrolladas en la vigente tesis), promueve un impacto positivo en el ajuste psicosocial del alumnado, así como, en sus dimensiones cognitivas, física, sociales y afectivas. Por tanto, promocionar en el contexto educativo hábitos o estilos de vida saludables y activos, con la implementación de intervenciones basadas en modelos pedagógico y de enseñanza eficaces, como el MED, contribuyen a desarrollar óptimos procesos de enseñanza y aprendizaje y mejoran el desarrollo personal y social en los

escolares (Bessa et al., 2019, 2021; Evangelio et al., 2018; González-Villora et al., 2018; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2015) (ver **Figura 7**).

Figura 7. Variables analizadas en estudios previos, recogidos en una reciente revisión sistemática crítica (2021), sobre el impacto y/o efectos de intervenciones basadas en el MED en comparación con intervenciones basadas en el MT-ID (Fuente: Bessa et al., 2021).

3. JUSTIFICACIÓN

*“Adonde interviene el favor y las dádivas, se allanan los riscos y se deshacen las dificultades”
(Don Quijote de la Mancha)”*

3.1. Contextos educativos activos: alfabetización física en alumnado de Educación Primaria y Educación Secundaria Obligatoria

La Organización Mundial de la Salud (OMS) recomienda la promoción en el contexto educativo de una adecuada salud física y psicosocial (WHO, 1986, 2000, 2007, 2016) que favorezca una buena calidad de vida (Buss, 2000). En este sentido, la OMS (2016) afirma que la inactividad física es un grave problema mundial, sobre todo en la infancia, donde la mayoría de las niñas y niños del mundo en edad escolar no realizan suficiente actividad física (ver **Figuras 8-9**). También es preocupante el incremento del sedentarismo en los diferentes entornos cotidianos (e.g., escolar) que hace descender el tiempo de prácticas activas saludables (Ennis, 2017). Por tanto, un objetivo primordial en el contexto educativo debería ser promocionar estilos de vida positivos y saludables (WHO, 2016). Del mismo modo, organizaciones internacionales como UNESCO (2015); Association for Physical Education (afPE) (2015); y Society of Health and Physical Educators America [SHAPE] (2017) señalan como finalidad fundamental para las escuelas, impulsar y favorecer un desarrollo integral del alumnado con conductas, experiencias y prácticas activas, participativas y motivantes, dinamizando y potenciando los aprendizajes socioemocionales (e.g., Domitrovich et al., 2017; Durlak et al., 2011) y mejorando la alfabetización física (e.g., Whitehead, 2010).

En este sentido, recientemente autores como Guthold et al. (2020) exponen un relevante estudio a nivel mundial, donde la gran mayoría de jóvenes en edad escolar no cumplen con las recomendaciones actuales para el desarrollo de estilos de vida físicamente activos y no realizan suficiente actividad física diaria, comprometiendo y poniendo en peligro su salud bio-psicosocial actual y futura (ver **Figuras 8-9**). Del mismo modo, afrontar de manera efectiva y eficiente el importante aumento de los niveles de prevalencia en actividad física insuficiente en población infantil y adolescente en edad escolar (**Figuras 8-9**), supondrá identificar, comprender e intervenir las causas y desigualdades socioeducativas que favorecen nocivos estilos de vida en el entorno educativo (Guthold et al., 2020). Por otro lado, las políticas educativas deberían promover el incremento de la actividad física y/o deportiva en todas sus formas (e.g., Educación Física y Deportiva). Además, una acción integral en la niñez y adolescencia requerirá participación y respuestas coordinadas en

Justificación

múltiples sectores y partes interesadas, incluidos, entre otros, escuelas, familias, instituciones gubernamentales y, en general, por parte de toda la comunidad o sistema educativo (Guthold et al., 2020).

Figura 8. Prevalencia (2002-2016) de actividad física insuficiente en **niños** en edad escolar (Fuente: Guthold et al., 2020).

Figura 9. Prevalencia (2001-2016) de actividad física insuficiente en **niñas** en edad escolar (Fuente: Guthold et al., 2020).

El aumento de prácticas físicas y deportivas beneficiosas entre los jóvenes menos activos, debería ser una finalidad clave de las instituciones e intervenciones comunitarias y escolares para promover el bienestar del alumnado (McMahon et al., 2017). Asimismo, una finalidad primordial de los agentes educativos debería ser promocionar hábitos de vida activos y participativos (Pate & Dowda, 2019). Por ello, desde nuestro punto de vista, se necesita impulsar urgentemente políticas educativas que promuevan intervenciones efectivas y, por ende, mejoren el desarrollo personal y social del alumnado infantil y adolescente. La inversión y el liderazgo en todos los niveles educativos para intervenir en las múltiples causas que podrían perpetuar la baja participación en la actividad física-deportiva y las diferencias en la igualdad de oportunidades, así como la participación activa de los propios estudiantes, serán vitales para fortalecer una educación de calidad y efectiva en todas las comunidades. Dichas acciones mejorarán la salud, los estilos de vida y las futuras generaciones de los estudiantes, impulsando el logro y/o éxito escolar en todas sus dimensiones (e.g., cognitivas, físicas, afectivas y sociales).

Por otro lado, el apoyo y desarrollo de marcos o enfoques teórico-prácticos como la EFC (UNESCO, 2015) y el ASE (Collaborative Academic Social Emotional Learning [CASEL], 2021) favorecerán estudiantes físicamente alfabetizados (Whitehead, 2010) (**Figura 10**). Este constructo de alfabetización física [physically literate], es la base de la EFC, y autores como Whitehead (2010) la definen como la motivación y competencia cognitiva, física y afectiva para promocionar y conservar una conducta activa durante toda la vida, permitiendo un desarrollo positivo de las aptitudes necesarias para obtener, comprender y utilizar eficazmente las decisiones para la salud. En esta línea, el alumnado físicamente alfabetizado, valorará intrínsecamente sus capacidades psicomotrices, así como su contribución al bienestar y la salud (McMahon et al., 2017). La promoción de la alfabetización física en el alumnado infantil y adolescente debe por tanto, seguir siendo un elemento fundamental de cualquier currículo educativo, específicamente en el área de Educación Física, durante las diferentes etapas académicas (UNESCO, 2015; Whitehead, 2010) (ver **Figura 10**).

¿Qué aspecto tiene una persona físicamente alfabetizada?

Las personas físicamente alfabetizadas poseen seguridad y **confianza en sí mismas**, en sintonía con sus capacidades motrices. Demuestran un **control** y una **coordinación** sólidos y pueden responder a las exigencias de un entorno cambiante. Se relacionan bien con los demás, demostrando sensibilidad en su comunicación verbal y no verbal y tendrán **relaciones** empáticas. El individuo físicamente alfabetizado disfruta descubriendo nuevas actividades y acogerá con agrado los consejos y orientaciones, confiando en el conocimiento de que experimentará algún éxito. El individuo apreciará el valor intrínseco de la educación física, así como su contribución a la **salud** y el **bienestar** y será capaz de mirar hacia adelante a lo largo de la vida con la expectativa de que la práctica de la actividad física siga formando parte de la vida.

Fuente: Whitehead (2010).

Figura 10. El constructo de Alfabetización Física [“Physically Literate”] como base de una Educación Física de Calidad (Fuente: UNESCO, 2015).

3.2. Desarrollo personal y social del alumnado en Educación Física

El papel clave que está adquiriendo la dimensión afectiva y social en el éxito escolar, así como, el desarrollo de un significativo proceso de enseñanza y aprendizaje socioemocional en las escuelas, son temas que están suscitando gran interés en la investigación empírica (Bessa et al., 2021; Biddle et al., 2000; Bisquerra et al., 2015; Domitrovich et al., 2017; Durlak et al., 2015; Evangelio et al., 2018; Franco et al., 2017; Hellison, 2011; Mestre-Navas & Guil, 2012; Payton, 2008; Taylor et al., 2017; Weissberg et al., 2015). Hayat et al. (2018) señalan que estos procesos podría convertirse en un procedimiento complejo, en el que los factores socioemocionales serían decisivos. Asimismo, se están promocionando intervenciones en el contexto educativo, donde las competencias afectivas y sociales juegan un papel relevante en los diferentes niveles o cursos académicos (Durlak et al., 2015). En este sentido, se podría afirmar que los procesos de enseñanza y aprendizaje tienen un carácter individual y social (Franco et al., 2017) donde la búsqueda de objetivos socioemocionales pueden impulsar el logro y/o éxito escolar (Cecchini Estrada et al., 2011; Domitrovich et al., 2017; Durlak et al., 2011, 2015; Elliot et al., 2006). Por tanto, para impulsar dicho éxito, no solo es necesario favorecer habilidades cognitivas, sino también promover habilidades personales y socioemocionales (Domitrovich et al.,

2017; Greenberg et al., 2003; Payton, 2008; Taylor et al., 2017). Del mismo modo, favorecer el desarrollo de habilidades socioemocionales en contextos educativos, como en Educación Física y con modelos pedagógicos eficaces (e.g., MED), hacen promueven las relaciones interpersonales entre los estudiantes y demás agentes educativos implicados (Bessa et al., 2019, 2021; Evangelio et al., 2018; Kao, 2019; Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2020; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). De esta manera, es importante impulsar en los contextos formativos, climas óptimos y motivacionales que favorezcan un ajuste psicosocial positivo y el desarrollo integral de la personalidad del alumnado (Bisquerra et al., 2015).

La Educación Física es reconocida por desempeñar un rol relevante en la adquisición de valores y competencias que contribuyan al desarrollo personal y socioemocional del alumnado (Bessa et al., 2019, 2021). En este sentido, algunos autores señalan que mediante intervenciones eficaces adecuadamente estructuradas y planificadas podrían contribuir al desarrollo personal y social del alumnado en la citada disciplina (Bessa et al., 2021; Eldar, 2008; Gil-Madrona et al., 2019; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019; Unlu et al., 2011). En esta línea, la Educación Física ofrece al estudiante una experiencia de aprendizaje significativa impulsada por el desarrollo de habilidades socioemocionales (UNESCO, 2015) y será una aliada clave en el positivo logro escolar, promoviendo ambientes o climas beneficiosos para el desarrollo de conductas prosociales (Mayfield et al., 2017), siempre y cuando se promuevan en contextos activos, participativos y motivantes (Shields et al., 2018). Sin embargo, a pesar de los vigentes beneficios expuestos, la presencia de dicha disciplina académica (EF) en el entorno educativo está disminuyendo en todas las regiones del mundo (Guthold et al., 2020; UNESCO, 2015; WHO, 2018). La OMS (WHO, 2018) ha calificado de pandemia los crecientes niveles de sedentarismo, así como el sustancial riesgo de enfermedades asociados a este nocivo estilo de vida, señalando que los recortes en la prestación de la EF sólo conseguirán incrementar este problema de forma exponencial (ver **Figura 11**).

Figura 11. Distribución en el contexto escolar español del horario lectivo en Educación Física (Fuente: WHO, 2018).

Por otro lado, UNESCO (2015, 2020) presenta una actualidad educativa en la que es clave el compromiso de los países para impulsar de forma efectiva la EFC, desarrollando políticas o pactos educativos de calidad a nivel gubernamental, con la implementación de programas significativos para los centros escolares. No obstante, algunos países están siendo más reticentes o lentos en fomentar dichas políticas que favorezcan la EFC (inclusiva y centrada en métodos constructivos con alumnado activo y participativo), así como para desarrollar acciones activas y valiosas en áreas como la EF, a través de la implementación real y la garantía de calidad educativa (ver **Figura 12**).

Figura 12. Encuesta mundial y revisión de la literatura sobre la situación de la área de Educación Física, desarrollada por la Asociación de Educación Física de los Condados del Noroeste (NWCPEA) (Fuente: UNESCO, 2015, 2020).

En conclusión, autores como Bessa et al. (2021) resaltan que, dentro del entorno escolar, la EF es analizada como un área académica importante para promover el desarrollo personal y social del alumnado infantil y adolescente, favorecedora de metodologías cooperativas y de habilidades socioemocionales positivas en los estudiantes. Asimismo, el desarrollo de actividades físicas y deportivas en EF, son beneficiosas para el alumnado desde una perspectiva integral del niño/a (Amado-Alonso et al., 2019; Bessa et al., 2019). En este sentido, existen ciertas evidencias de que la EF es una disciplina significativa para el desarrollo de formas eficaces de experiencias físico-deportivas, que mejorarán las competencias socioemocionales en el alumnado (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019, 2020; Luna, Rodríguez-Donaire, et al., 2020). Dicha asignatura fomenta un significativo entorno flexible y cooperativo que favorece interacciones intrapersonales e interpersonales entre el alumnado (Sánchez-Oliva et al., 2014). Eime et al. (2013) señalan la sinergia positiva entre la implementación de prácticas físicas y deportivas con variables intrapersonales e interpersonales, en entornos escolares. Del mismo modo, estos autores establecen que el juego deportivo de equipo y cooperativo, en contextos educativos, se asocia con una mejor salud socioemocional debido a la naturaleza social de la participación y muestran mejoras en los niveles de bienestar psicosocial en población estudiantil.

4. OBJETIVOS E HIPÓTESIS

“El científico busca lo común en lo diverso, separa lo esencial de lo superfluo: y es lo que continuamente hace Sancho Panza, que busca respuestas sensatas a los disparates de Don Quijote.”

(Jorge Wagensberg)

Tal y como expone Bisquerra (2004, p. 90) “el punto de partida de cualquier investigación es la selección de un tema, de una idea o de un área a investigar”. Este aspecto permitirá una mejor comprensión y formulación del problema a resolver. En este sentido, el tema o dominio sobre el que versa esta tesis doctoral queda formulado a continuación:

La relevancia e interés del diseño, desarrollo y evaluación de programas de intervención activos, físicos y deportivos en el contexto educativo.

En virtud de ello, basándonos en los antecedentes empíricos y conclusiones de la previa revisión de la literatura científica específica del campo objeto de estudio, se puede formular para la vigente tesis, el siguiente **problema de investigación**:

¿Qué impacto tendrá en el contexto educativo el desarrollo de programas de intervención físico-deportivos, basados en el MED, sobre el alumnado de Educación Primaria y Educación Secundaria Obligatoria, en competencias socioemocionales?

4.1. Objetivos de investigación

La presente tesis doctoral, con una finalidad fundamentalmente aplicada, tiene los siguientes objetivos generales (OG) y específicos (OE):

4.1.1. Objetivos generales (OG)

- **OG.1:** Diseñar dos programas de intervención físico-deportivo basadas en el MED, uno para alumnado de Educación Primaria (EP), y otro para alumnado de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria (ESO) en la disciplina académica de Educación Física.
- **OG.2:** Desarrollar los programas de intervención en diferentes niveles académicos y centros educativos de la Comunidad de Castilla-La Mancha (España).
- **OG.3:** Evaluar la eficacia de los programas educativos, en diversas competencias socioemocionales, tales como: bienestar subjetivo

(componente cognitivo y afectivo); inteligencia emocional rasgo; ansiedad social; competencia social; aceptación social entre iguales; y ajuste psicosocial.

4.1.2. Objetivos específicos (OE)

- **OE.1:** Garantizar la adecuación e idoneidad de los programas al contexto educativo y sociocultural, así como, a los participantes en las intervenciones físico-deportivas.
- **OE.2:** Analizar y fundamentar los programas educativos basados en el modelo de Educación Deportiva (MED), desde los marcos y enfoques teóricos de la Educación Física de Calidad (EFC) y el Aprendizaje Social y Emocional (ASE).
- **OE.3:** Asegurar experimentalmente las condiciones necesarias para: (a) fomentar la eficacia de las intervenciones; (b) sostener la funcionalidad y viabilidad de los programas en los centros escolares; y (c) dinamizar y optimizar el desarrollo de los programas físico-deportivos en el alumnado infantil y adolescente
- **OE.4:** Promocionar y facilitar, con la implementación de actividades físico-deportiva intra e interpersonales y el juego deportivo novedoso, alternativo y de equipo (e.g., Ringo polaco), la participación cooperativa e inclusiva del alumnado participante.
- **OE.5:** Garantizar en las clases de Educación Física, procesos de enseñanza y aprendizaje constructivos y eficaces, centrados en el alumnado como un sujeto activo y participativo.
- **OE.6:** Analizar las posibles diferencias estadísticamente significativas en las puntuaciones pre-test (inicio de los programas) y en las puntuaciones post-test (finalización de los programas) entre el grupo experimental (MED) y el grupo control activo (MT-ID). En otras palabras, evaluar la eficacia inmediata o a corto plazo de las variables dependientes objeto de estudio.
- **OE.7:** Examinar las posibles diferencias significativas en las puntuaciones pre-test (inicio del programa) y post-test (finalización del programa), en uno de los grupos de intervención de alumnado adolescente, teniendo en cuenta la variable moderadora de género, es decir, la eficacia inmediata

o a corto plazo de las variables competencia social y aceptación social entre iguales, en función del género.

4.2. Objetivos de los artículos publicados en la tesis doctoral

El objetivo general de evaluar, es acometido a partir de los siguientes objetivos específicos, concretamos en los tres artículos originales incluidos en la presente tesis:

- **OE.1 (manuscrito I):** Evaluar el impacto de un programa piloto de Educación Física, basado en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, sobre las variables: bienestar subjetivo, inteligencia emocional rasgo y ansiedad social, en alumnado de Educación Secundarias Obligatoria (adolescentes de 12 a 15 años) en un centro educativo de la provincia de Toledo (Castilla-La Mancha; España).
- **OE.2 (manuscrito II):** Evaluar los efectos de una intervención físico-deportiva basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, en comparación con una intervención basada en el modelo Tradicional de Instrucción Directa, en alumnado de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria (adolescentes de 12 a 15 años) sobre las variables: competencia social y aceptación social entre iguales, en un centro educativo de la provincia de Toledo (Castilla-La Mancha; España).
- **OE.3 (manuscrito III):** Evaluar en alumnado de Educación Primaria (niños y niñas de 10 a 12 años) la eficacia de un programa basado en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, en comparación con una intervención educativa basada en el modelo Tradicional de Instrucción Directa, sobre las variables: bienestar subjetivo y ajuste psicosocial, en un centro educativo de Ciudad Real (Castilla-La Mancha; España).

A continuación, en la **Tabla 4**, se describen algunos elementos relevantes (e.g., hipótesis) de los artículos incluidos en la presente tesis doctoral.

Tabla 4. Características relevantes en las publicaciones científicas de la tesis doctoral.

	Manuscrito I	Manuscrito II	Manuscrito III
Título [Título original]	Mejorando el bienestar subjetivo, la inteligencia emocional rasgo y la ansiedad social de los adolescentes mediante un programa basado en el modelo de Educación Deportiva. [Improving Adolescents' Subjective Well-Being, Trait Emotional Intelligence and Social Anxiety through a Programme Based on the Sport Education Model]	Competencia social y aceptación social entre iguales: evaluación de los efectos de una intervención educativa en adolescentes. [Social Competence and Peer Social Acceptance: Evaluating Effects of an Educational Intervention in Adolescents]	Bienestar subjetivo y ajuste psicosocial: examinando los efectos de una intervención basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva en niños y niñas. [Subjective Well-Being and Psychosocial Adjustment: Examining the Effects of an Intervention Based on the Sport Education Model on Children]
Objetivos	Evaluar el impacto de un programa piloto de Educación Física, basado en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, sobre las variables psicológicas: bienestar subjetivo, inteligencia emocional rasgo y ansiedad social, en alumnado adolescente de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria de un centro educativo de Castilla-La Mancha.	Evaluar en alumnado de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria los efectos de una intervención basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, en comparación con una intervención basada en el modelo Tradicional de Instrucción Directa, sobre las variables psicosociales: competencia social y aceptación social entre iguales, en un centro educativo de Castilla-La Mancha.	Evaluar en alumnado de Educación Primaria la eficacia de un programa basado en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, en comparación con una intervención educativa basada en el modelo Tradicional de Instrucción Directa, sobre el bienestar subjetivo y ajuste psicosocial, en un centro educativo Castilla-La Mancha.
Hipótesis	El programa (MED) mejora en los participantes del grupo experimental: (a) el bienestar subjetivo (Hipótesis 1); (b) la inteligencia emocional de rasgo (Hipótesis 2); y (c) la ansiedad social (Hipótesis 3).	La intervención (MED) mejora en los participantes del grupo experimental: (a) la competencia social (Hipótesis 1); y (b) la aceptación social entre iguales (Hipótesis 2). Por otro lado, el impacto de la intervención no muestra diferencias en función del género (Hipótesis 3).	El programa (MED) mejora en los participantes del grupo experimental: (a) el bienestar subjetivo (Hipótesis 1); y (b) el ajuste psicosocial (Hipótesis 2).
Diseño	Diseño cuasi-experimental (con medidas repetidas pretest-posttest con grupo control activo).	Diseño experimental (con medidas repetidas pretest-posttest con grupo control activo).	Diseño cuasi-experimental (con medidas repetidas pretest-posttest con grupo control activo).
Tamaño muestral	113 estudiantes adolescentes (ESO) de 12-15 años (media de edad (M) = 13.82; desviación típica (DT) = 0.79) de un centro educativo de Toledo (Castilla-La Mancha; España).	114 estudiantes adolescentes (ESO) con edades comprendidas entre 12 y 15 años (media de edad (M) = 13.41; desviación típica (DT) = 0.81) de un centro educativo de Toledo (Castilla-La Mancha; España).	167 niños y niñas, con edades comprendidas entre 10 y 12 años (media de edad (M) = 10.78; desviación típica (DT) = 1.07) de un centro educativo de Ciudad Real (Castilla-La Mancha; España).

5. RESÚMENES DE LOS MANUSCRITOS

*“Se breve en tus razonamientos, que ninguno hay gustoso si es
largo”*

(Don Quijote de la Mancha)

5.1. Resumen del Manuscrito I

Mejorando el bienestar subjetivo, la inteligencia emocional rasgo y la ansiedad social de los adolescentes mediante un programa basado en el modelo de Educación Deportiva

Este estudio tuvo como objetivo evaluar el impacto de un programa piloto de Educación Física y Deportiva en adolescentes sobre las siguientes variables psicológicas: (a) bienestar subjetivo (calidad de vida relacionada con la salud, afecto positivo y afecto negativo); (b) inteligencia emocional de rasgo; y (c) ansiedad social. El programa se basó en el modelo pedagógico de Educación Deportiva, abordándose desde los enfoques del marco de la Educación Física de Calidad y desde la perspectiva del Aprendizaje Social y Emocional. Los participantes fueron 113 estudiantes de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria (ESO) de entre 12 y 15 años, y fueron asignados a un grupo de control ($n = 44$) y a un grupo experimental ($n = 69$). Se utilizó un diseño cuasi-experimental con medidas repetidas de pre-test y post-test. Se aplicó la corrección de Bonferroni para las comparaciones múltiples. Los resultados preliminares obtenidos en esta investigación evidenciaron que el programa piloto de Educación Física y Deportiva promovió, a favor del grupo experimental, mejoras significativas en un indicador específico de la variable bienestar subjetivo y en la variable inteligencia emocional rasgo. Estos hallazgos alentadores respaldan la eficacia pedagógica del programa con respecto a su objetivo. Asimismo, los resultados también ponen de manifiesto la viabilidad y la idoneidad del programa en términos de una propuesta pedagógica innovadora.

Palabras clave: educación física; aprendizaje social y emocional; modelo de educación deportiva; bienestar subjetivo; inteligencia emocional rasgo; ansiedad social.

5.2. Resumen del Manuscrito II

Competencia social y aceptación social entre iguales: evaluación de los efectos de una intervención educativa en adolescentes

Este estudio tiene como objetivo evaluar el impacto de una intervención educativa sobre la competencia social y la aceptación social entre adolescentes. Los participantes fueron 106 adolescentes de 12 a 15 años ($M = 13.41$ años; $DT = 0.81$ años). Los participantes fueron asignados aleatoriamente al grupo de control ($n = 44$) y al grupo experimental ($n = 69$). En el grupo experimental, se aplicó una intervención basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva (MED). Mientras que en el grupo control (activo) se desarrolló una intervención basada en el modelo Tradicional de Instrucción Directa (MT-ID). Se utilizó un diseño experimental con medidas repetidas pretest y posttest. Para evaluar la competencia social se utilizó el Cuestionario multidimensional de competencia social para adolescentes (AMSC-Q). El Cuestionario Sociométrico [The Guess Who] (GW4) se usó para evaluar la aceptación social (AS) entre iguales. Los resultados preliminares mostraron con la intervención basada en el MED (grupo experimental), mejoras significativas en algunos indicadores de competencia social y aceptación social entre iguales, en comparación con los obtenidos con el MT-ID (grupo de control). Asimismo, los resultados confirman un impacto similar de la intervención en función del género, entre chicos y chicas. Estos resultados preliminares sugieren el potencial del modelo de educación Deportiva con adolescentes.

Palabras clave: educación física de calidad, modelo de educación deportiva, competencia social, aceptación social entre iguales, género, adolescentes.

5.3. Resumen del Manuscrito III

Bienestar subjetivo y ajuste psicosocial: examinando los efectos de una intervención basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva en niños

El presente estudio tiene como objetivo evaluar la eficacia de una intervención basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, en comparación con una intervención basada en el modelo tradicional de Instrucción Directa en niños y niñas. La intervención se llevó a cabo en horario escolar durante 18 sesiones de 50 minutos cada una. La muestra estuvo formada por 146 niños de 10 a 12 años ($M = 10.78$; $DT = 1.07$). Los participantes fueron asignados aleatoriamente a un grupo experimental ($n = 87$) y a un grupo control ($n = 59$). Para evaluar el componente afectivo del bienestar subjetivo se utilizó la Escala de Afecto Positivo y Negativo para niños y adolescentes (PANASN). Para evaluar el ajuste psicosocial se utilizó el Sistema de Evaluación de Conducta de niños y adolescentes (BASC). Los resultados mostraron mejoras significativas en el componente afectivo del bienestar subjetivo y una reducción de la ansiedad, a favor del grupo experimental. Nuestros resultados actuales promueven la eficacia metodológica y práctica de una intervención de Educación Deportiva.

Palabras clave: educación física; modelo de educación deportiva; niños y niñas; bienestar subjetivo; ajuste psicosocial.

6. [ABSTRACTS] DE LOS MANUSCRITOS

*“Be brief in your reasoning, for none is pleasant if it is long”
(Don Quixote of La Mancha)*

6.1. [Abstract] del Manuscrito I

Improving adolescents' subjective well-being, trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety through a programme based on the Sport Education Model

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of a physical-sport education pilot programme on adolescents' subjective well-being (health related quality of life, positive affect and negative affect), trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety. The programme was based on the pedagogical sport education model within a quality physical education framework, and approached from the perspective of social and emotional learning. Participants were 113 compulsory secondary education students aged 12-15 years that were assigned to a control group ($n = 44$) and an experimental group ($n = 69$). A quasi-experimental design with repeated pre-test and post-test measures was used. Bonferroni correction was applied for multiple comparisons. The preliminary results obtained in this investigation revealed that the physical-sport education pilot programme promoted significant improvements in a specific indicator of subjective well-being and trait emotional intelligence in the experimental group. These encouraging findings support the pedagogical efficiency of the programme with regard to the programme aim. The findings also highlight the feasibility and appropriateness of the programme in terms of an innovative teaching proposal.

Keywords: physical education; social and emotional learning; sport education model; subjective well-being; trait emotional intelligence; social anxiety.

6.2. [Abstract] del Manuscrito II

Social competence and peer social acceptance: evaluating effects of an educational intervention in adolescents

This study aims to evaluate the impact of an educational intervention on social competence and social acceptance among adolescents. The participants were 106 adolescents aged 12-15 years ($M = 13.41$ years; $SD = 0.81$ years). Participants were randomly assigned to the control group ($n = 44$) and an experimental group ($n = 69$). In the experimental group, an intervention based on the Sport Education Model (SEM) was applied. While in the control group, an intervention based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) was carried out. An experimental design with repeated pretest and posttest measurements was developed. The Adolescent Multidimensional Social Competence Questionnaire (AMSC-Q) was used to assess social competence. The Guess Who (GW4) questionnaire was used to assess social acceptance (SA) among peers. The preliminary results showed that the intervention based on the SEM (experimental group) promoted more significant improvements in some indicators of social competence and social acceptance among peers than those obtained with the TM-DI (control group). The results confirm a similar impact of the intervention between boys and girls. These preliminary results suggest the potential of the Sport Education Model with adolescents.

Keywords: quality physical education, sport education model, social competence, peer social acceptance, gender, adolescents.

6.3. [Abstract] del Manuscrito III

Subjective well-being and psychosocial adjustment: examining the effects of an intervention based on the Sport Education Model on children

The current study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of an intervention based on the Sport Education model, compared to an intervention based on the traditional model of Direct Instruction in children. The intervention was carried out during school hours for 18 sessions of 50-min each. The sample was made up of 146 children aged 10-12 years ($M = 10.78$ years; $SD = 1.07$ years). Participants were randomly assigned to the experimental group ($n = 87$) and a control group ($n = 59$). A quasi-experimental design with repeated pretest and posttest evaluations with the control group was implemented. The Positive and Negative Affect Scale for children and adolescents (PANASN) was used to assess the affective component of subjective well-being. The Child and Adolescent Behavior Assessment System (BASC) was used to assess psychosocial adjustment. The results showed significant improvements in the affective component of subjective well-being and a reduction in anxiety in favor of the experimental group. Our current results show the methodological and practical efficacy of a Sport Education intervention.

Keywords: physical education; sport education model; children; subjective well-being; psychosocial adjustment.

7. Manuscrito I. Improving adolescents' subjective well-being, trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety through a programme based on the Sport Education model

*“Cada uno es artífice de su propia ventura”
(Don Quijote de la Mancha)*

7.1. Introduction

In the education field, physical education is a subject that can contribute to improving the well-being and health of children and adolescents. The concept of quality physical education, which is understood as an interrelated system of inclusive and active teaching and learning, must be considered a key framework for integral approaches (e.g., education and health) (UNESCO, 2015). It can also be seen as a physically active teaching and learning experience that can positively impact students' psychomotor abilities, cognitive comprehension and social and affective aptitudes (afPE, 2015). Moreover, in our view, quality physical education could be grouped in the social and emotional learning category.

Quality physical education aims to achieve an integral education commitment (Le Masurier & Corbin, 2006; Penney et al., 2009) that allows students to be physically literate (Keegan et al., 2013; Whitehead, 2010). Physical literacy is the pillar of quality physical education, and can be defined as the motivation and cognitive, physical and affective competence necessary to encourage and preserve an active attitude in life, enabling a positive development of the aptitude to achieve, understand and use decisions about one's health efficiently (Whitehead, 2001). Students who are physically literate intrinsically value their own psychomotor capabilities, as well as the contribution of these abilities to well-being and health (Whitehead, 2010).

The connection between health and physical activity is widely accepted (Hallal et al., 2012; WHO, 2010). However, the effects of physical activity on health in the educational context should be deepened through experimental studies. Designing teaching and learning processes in this area will support physical, psychological, emotional and social development (National Association for Sport and Physical Education [NASPE] & American Heart Association [AHA], 2012).

The synergy between the practice of physical-sport activity together with physical and psychological health is a gradually growing interest area for education researchers (Armour et al., 2013; Bailey et al., 2009; Knowles et al., 2018; Spittle & Byrne, 2009). Moreover, different investigations in the education framework of the evolution of quality physical education have emphasised the need for methodological change (Decorby et al., 2005; Le Masurier & Corbin, 2006). Several pedagogical models share the same features (Metzler, 2017).

This study is based on quality physical education, manifested through a specific sport education model (Siedentop et al., 2020). Sport education is a pedagogical model that uses essential features of sports (seasons, competitions, membership, data register, culminating event and festivity), and aims to achieve the inclusive goal of all students living real and meaningful sport experiences in physical education. In addition, this model aspires to develop competence, enthusiasm and a physical-sport culture in students (Hastie & Wallhead, 2016).

The pedagogical potential of the sport education model, if correctly implemented (Hastie & Casey, 2014), results in benefits at a physical level (Araújo et al., 2016; Hastie, Sluder, et al., 2009; Wahl-Alexander & Chomentowski, 2018). Similarly, it has been shown to have a positive impact on psychological variables in adolescents. These positive benefits include: basic psychological needs (Méndez-Giménez, Fernández-Río, et al., 2015); improvement in competence (Cuevas et al., 2015) and the feeling of belonging to a group (Kao, 2019); decrease in attitudes towards violence and improvements in social responsibility and participants' relationships (Kao, 2019; Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016); more self-determined behaviour (Sinelnikov & Hastie, 2010); improvements in friendship and sport goals (Cuevas et al., 2015); decrease in aggressive behaviour and improvements in friendship relationships (García-López & Gutiérrez, 2015; Kao, 2019); positive changes in the perception of the social climate (Antonio Méndez-Giménez et al., 2016); improvement in social relationships (Wallhead et al., 2014); improvement in trait emotional intelligence and motivational mediators (Méndez-Giménez et al., 2017); and improvement in sport culture and enthusiasm. However, no benefits in terms of life satisfaction have been found (Puente-Maxera et al., 2018). By making use of sport, these studies provide evidence of a meaningful and positive impact on the psychological and physical development of the school-age population (Armour et al., 2013; Hastie et al., 2011).

Health is generally determined by several physical–biological, psychological and social indicators (WHO, 1948). Therefore, good health is a fundamental dimension in personal and social progress, and an important sphere in quality of life (WHO, 1986). Approached from the perspective of positive health, a state of wellness encourages individuals to reach complete social and psychological development (Fredrickson, 2009). The World Health Organization (WHO) aims to promote physical and

psychological health (WHO, 1948) that supports a good quality of life (Buss, 2000). The construct of subjective well-being is among the factors that affect health. Consequently, research on the influence of subjective well-being in different social and educational contexts has received increasing attention in recent decades (Sánchez-Álvarez et al., 2015). Subjective well-being comprises two main factors: a cognitive aspect (satisfaction with one's own life) and an affective aspect (positive and negative affect) (Diener, 2000; Diener et al., 1999). The cognitive side of well-being reflects the assessment of how individuals process information in their lives (Pavot & Diener, 2008). The affective side of well-being implies a hedonistic individual balance; that is, how often individuals experience positive and negative emotions (Diener, 2000; Diener et al., 1999).

Recent research has focused on studying the effects of positive psychological variables on personal and social development (Gable & Haidt, 2005). These studies have been categorised as positive psychology (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). Emotional intelligence is a positive variable that currently has broad support because of its close connections to subjective well-being and physical and mental health (Martins et al., 2010; Sánchez-Álvarez et al., 2015; Zeidner et al., 2012).

Variables such as social anxiety have a negative effect on subjective well-being (Wersebe et al., 2018). In this sense, social anxiety can be defined as a person's constant fear of one or more social or performance situations, in which they are exposed to unknown persons or the possible scrutiny of other people (Moran, 2016). Social anxiety has a negative impact on subjective well-being in adolescents because of the anguish individuals may feel (Beidel et al., 2007), which in turn may negatively affect the quality of their interpersonal relationships (Cejudo et al., 2018; Inglés et al., 2010). We consider that education should promote social and emotional learning, which the WHO defines as a heterogeneous set of life skills, as this is a potential factor that supports and encourages mental health (WHO, 2014). Scholars in favour of this teaching proposal argue that emotional education may also promote public health (Domitrovich et al., 2017; Kimber et al., 2008), because its ultimate goal is improvement of the general quality of health and well-being in citizens. In the school context, many researchers claim that a key purpose of education is to improve peoples' lives so that they can reach an optimal degree of personal happiness and well-being in adulthood (Ecclestone, 2012). This suggests that a healthy pedagogical and

psychological school environment may facilitate students' positive adjustment; therefore, such an environment is essential for the development of well-being in children and adolescents (Baker et al., 2003).

The theoretical and practical justification for this study was rooted in the work of various authors who developed educational interventions based on the sport education model and recommended that further research should evaluate the impact of this model on the promotion of optimal personal and social development (Araújo et al., 2014; Browne et al., 2004; Kao, 2019; Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016). In this sense, Metzler's (2017) contributions are very relevant, stating that a sports model teaching program is mainly focused on different domains (Metzler, 2017): affective, cognitive and motor. In line with this statement, our study focuses on the affective domain. We agree with several previous authors (Diener, 2000; Diener et al., 1999) that subjective well-being is a key variable that influences balanced personal and social development. In addition, the existing relationship between subjective well-being and trait emotional intelligence suggests that it is necessary to further explore this topic. Social anxiety generates inappropriate social relationships in adolescents (Beidel et al., 2007; Wersebe et al., 2018). Given the positive effects of the sport education model on social relationships (Wallhead et al., 2014), it is possible that such interventions may reduce social anxiety.

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of a pilot programme based on the sport education model on the three variables: subjective well-being, trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety. The hypotheses focused on the assumptions that the programme will result in improvements in our participants' subjective well-being (Hypothesis 1), trait emotional intelligence (Hypothesis 2) and social anxiety (Hypothesis 3).

7.2. Methods

7.2.1. Participants

This study used non-probability incidental or accessibility sampling. The sample comprised 113 students in compulsory secondary education aged 12-15 years (mean age (M) = 13.82 years; standard deviation (SD) = 0.79 years). The research was conducted in a state school with students from five class groups. The control group comprised 44 students (two class groups) and the experimental group included 69

students (three class groups). The experimental and control group assignment was based on a cluster-randomised controlled trial. The gender distribution was 64 (57%) boys and 49 (43%) girls (**Table 5**).

The main inclusion criterion was parental consent. The exclusion criteria were: (a) attending less than 80% of the sessions of the intervention programme (less than 13 sessions); (b) students with special educational needs associated with intellectual disability; and (c) students that were removed from school for disciplinary reasons.

Table 5. Sex and age of the sample.

		N	%
Sex	Male	64	57
	Female	49	43
Age	12	42	37
	13	45	40
	14	23	20
	15	3	3

7.2.2. Procedure

We requested the collaboration of the educational centre (Spain) in this study. The management board of the participating school was contacted to obtain their approval and authorisation for the study. Permission was also obtained from the families of the participating students, and from the teaching staff and school council. This study respected the relevant ethical values and guaranteed participants' confidentiality and anonymity. In addition, this study was developed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki regarding human experimentation. The study procedures were conducted in accordance with the Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha code of ethics.

This study used a quasi-experimental design with repeated pre-test and post-test measures and a control group. The study was conducted over three stages. First, before the intervention began, the assessment instruments (pre-test evaluation) were handed out for completion in the first 20 minutes of two sessions, to avoid burdening the students. Next, the programme based on the sport education model was

implemented. The programme sessions took place during the second term of the school year. Finally, the assessment instruments were completed a second time (post-test evaluation). The independent variable was the intervention programme, and the dependent variables were subjective well-being, trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety.

7.2.3. Measures

Four evaluation instruments were used to assess the variables in this study, under the psychometric parameters of reliability and validity.

The Kidscreen-10 Index (Ravens-Sieberer & European, 2006) was used to assess subjective health-related quality of life and well-being. This 10-item scale was designed for children and adolescents aged 8–18 years. Each item has five response options, ranging from ‘*Never*’ to ‘*Always*’ or ‘*Not at all*’ to ‘*Extremely*’. The 10 items cover: affective symptoms of depressed mood; cognitive symptoms of disturbed concentration; psychovegetative aspects of vitality, energy and feeling well; and psychosocial aspects correlated with mental health, such as the ability to experience fun with friends or getting along well with others at school. The adapted version of the questionnaire used in this study has adequate internal consistency reliability (*Cronbach’s alpha* = 0.82) and test-retest stability ($r = 0.73$; $ICC = 0.72$) (Aymerich et al., 2005).

The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (Watson et al., 1988) was used to assess participants’ positive and negative affect. The Spanish version of this scale for children and adolescents was validated by Sandín (2003). This scale comprises 20 items on two dimensions: positive affect and negative affect. Each subscale contains 10 items. The questionnaire is completed by participants based on the way they normally feel and behave. The scale has three response options: ‘*Never*’ = 1, ‘*Sometimes*’ = 2, and ‘*Many times*’ = 3.

We used the **Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire Adolescents Short Form** (TEIQue-ASF) (Petrides et al., 2006) (adapted into Spanish in its abridged version for teenagers by Ferrando et al., 2011) to evaluate trait emotional intelligence based on the theoretical model of Petrides & Furnham (2001). The 30 items that make up the TEIQue-ASF are scored on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = ‘*Completely disagree*’

to 7 = *‘Completely agree’*). The general emotional intelligence score of the total scale is obtained by summing the 30 items.

Finally, participants completed the **Social Anxiety Scale for Adolescents (SAS-A)** (La Greca & López, 1998). The SAS-A comprises 22 items; 18 items are self-descriptive and four are distracting elements that are not taken into account for the score. The SAS-A contains three subscales: (a) fear of negative evaluation (eight items), (b) anxiety and social avoidance before strangers or new social situations (six items) and (c) anxiety and social avoidance in social situations in general (four items). Responses are on a 5-point Likert-type scale from 1 (*‘Never’*) to 5 (*‘Always’*). In addition, a global index of social anxiety (SAS-T) is obtained by summing the scores for the items (excluding neutral items). High scores reflect high levels of social anxiety (La Greca & López, 1998). The scale was adapted to the Spanish population by Olivares et al. (2005). Only the SAS-T score was used in this study.

7.2.4. Intervention Programme

The physical-sport programme was completed following the sport education model structure (Siedentop et al., 2020): (1) *season*: lengthy didactic units; (2) *membership*: development of a team spirit and cooperation; (3) *regular competition*: showing technical–tactical abilities; (4) *data register*: giving evidence of and analysing the process that has been followed; and (5) *festivity*: a festive atmosphere. This highlighted other important education aspects such as: cooperative learning; autonomy and personal initiative; positive interdependence; and self-management of responsibility roles in conflict resolution (e.g., referee and coach). This helped to make the sport experience more real and positive, including how students transferred responsibilities by means of organisation roles (e.g., referee and scorer), team roles (e.g., coach and physical trainer) and how sport content was modified when adapted to the students (Siedentop et al., 2020).

Hastie and Casey’s guidelines were followed for the design and validation of the programme (Hastie & Casey, 2014) (p. 423): (a) thoroughly detailed curricular elements; (b) precise certification of the applied model; and (c) an in-depth explanation of the context of the programme. The intervention programme was implemented in the experimental group following sequencing of content and activities in three stages (initial, intermediate and final) over 16 sessions (**Table 6**).

Table 6. *Sequencing of stages and activity sessions in the intervention programme.*

Stage	Session	Sport Education Model
Initial (Theoretical Sessions)	1-2	Introduction and presentation of the Sport Education Model with digital and audio-visual support (ICT). Presentation and distribution of learning resources. Division and organisation of classroom groups in teams (assignment of team names with a didactic and cross curricular theme). Distribution and selection of responsibility roles.
	3	Explanation for the self-design of learning resources on digital format (ICT). Selection and assignment of anthems, badges, mascots and t-shirts representing a team.
Intermediate (Practical Sessions)	4-7	Practical implementation of the roles of each member of the teams. Learning of technical-tactical elements and abilities: kicking-off, catching, moving, throwing, defence and attack. Learning game rules.
	8-9	Warming-up, training and friendly matches. Meetings for comprehension and reflection with intervention of the responsibility roles.
	10-14	Regular stage competition (Round Robin).
Final (Practical Sessions)	15-16	Inter-class groups final competitions (final matches with class groups), final event, giving awards and diplomas.

This pilot programme was developed to reflect the teaching hours of the physical education subject, which covers 16 55-minute sessions (2-3 sessions per week for 6 weeks). The total duration was considered sufficient to analyse the possible effects of the programme on the dependent variables, as indicated by previous research (Mahedero et al., 2015).

The educational intervention applied to the experimental group consisted of a didactic unit that used an alternative sport, called ringo (Méndez Giménez, 2005; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2011). Ringo is an alternative, modified and reduced sport of divided court and net. It is played with a hoop (ringo) and a volleyball net. The objective is to score when the ringo falls on the opposite court (**Figure 13**). In this pilot programme, the application of an alternative sport that was novel and unknown to students meant that everyone started with the same theoretical and practical sports

knowledge, and there were few initial differences in their levels of technical–tactical sports skill. Alternative sports are characterised by being motivating, cooperative, socialising and adapted to participants’ characteristics. The selection and organisation of teams (five teams per classroom) was developed by drawing lots. In addition, different responsibility roles were assigned to participating students: player; referee; coach–captain; physical trainer; person responsible for statistics and reports; and member of the discipline and organisation committee. An essential rule in the development of the pilot programme was that all students would actively participate in the programme with the assignment of two roles (player role and another responsibility role). The pilot programme also used various learning and curricular resources (self-designed portfolio, worksheets and reports) that had been used by other authors (García-López & Gutiérrez, 2015).

Figure 13. *Practical session of the intervention programme.*

For the control group, a didactic unit of traditional collective sport with a conventional teaching style was developed (Delgado-Noguera, 2015). This traditional teaching model aimed to improve students’ technical motor skills only. In the teaching-learning process, the teacher assumed a managerial role and the students adopted passive individual roles limited to following the directive instructions of the teacher. This intervention consisted of 12 55-minute sessions (two sessions per week for 6

weeks). The first nine sessions aimed at learning the technical fundamentals of basketball (pot, dribbling, passing, throwing and receiving) through a task assignment teaching style (Delgado-Noguera, 2015). These traditional sports sessions were based on a 10-minute warm-up, 40-minute main session that included explanations and basketball practice and a 5-minute warm down in which stretching was performed. During these sessions, all tasks were directed by the teacher without students' participation. The last three sessions were dedicated to team competition.

Two compulsory secondary education teachers, both with advanced degrees in Sports Science participated in this research. The first teacher (with a Master's of Science in Psychology) participated in the design and implementation of the pilot programme. The second teacher developed an intervention based on the traditional model. Both teachers received a 10 hour training course on the specific theoretical and practical aspects of each teaching model. In addition, supervision and tutoring was provided by a researcher expert in the sports education model and a researcher expert in the traditional education model. This tutoring consisted of: (a) session-by-session analysis during the intervention programmes; (b) telephone conversations and emails to resolve doubts, concerns and problems; and (c) weekly visits to the teaching centre. In these visits, the experts visited the centre randomly without prior notice with the objectives of: verifying that there were no gaps between what was planned and what was implemented, and checking that the teaching models were applied with all of their characteristics.

7.2.5. Data analysis

After fulfilment of the requirements of normality and homoscedasticity was verified, we examined the distribution of the data for a univariate normality analysis. The results showed asymmetry and kurtosis values lower than 1.2. Next, we calculated the reliability coefficients (Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, average variance extracted and McDonald's omega coefficient) to obtain reliability evidence. Then, to determine the impact of the programme, descriptive analyses (mean and *SD*) and analyses of variance (ANOVA) were performed with the scores collected in the pre-test stage. Subsequently, descriptive analyses and analyses of covariance (ANCOVA) were used with post-test scores to determine the impact of the programme on each of the variables. Bonferroni correction was applied for multiple comparisons. For all

analyses, a p -value <0.05 was considered to indicate statistical significance. After application of Bonferroni correction, a p -value <0.012 was considered significant.

The effect size (η^2) of the differences was calculated using partial eta-squared (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). The effect size was analysed based on four ranges: 0-0.009, negligible; 0.010-0.089, low-effect size; 0.090-0.249, medium-effect size; and >0.250 , big-effect size (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). The data were analysed with SPSS version 24.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY).

7.3. Results

7.3.1. Reliability

In this study, we used well-established measures with appropriate psychometric properties (**Table 7**).

Table 7. Reliability evidence of the instruments used ($n = 113$).

Measures	α	CR	AVE	Ω
KIDSCREEN	0.91	0.89	0.674	0.92
PANASN-PA	0.70	0.77	0.502	0.72
PANASN-NA	0.74	0.76	0.519	0.77
TEIQue-ASF	0.71	0.70	0.503	0.79
SAS-T	0.85	0.80	0.687	0.87

Note. α = Cronbach's alpha; CR = composite reliability, AVE = average variance extracted; Ω = McDonald's omega index.

7.3.2. Effects of the Programme

The pre-test MANOVA results did not reveal statistically significant differences between the groups prior to the intervention, Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.571$, $F(5, 108) = 0.739$, $p = 0.333$, with a small effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.062$, $r = 0.11$).

The ANOVA using the pre-test scores (**Table 8**) revealed no statistically significant differences in any of the dependent variables before the programme began, except for a significantly higher score for trait emotional intelligence in the experimental group compared with the control group. The size of the effect was low for trait emotional

intelligence ($\eta^2 = 0.009$). Applying Bonferroni correction showed no significant differences in any of the variables.

Results from the pre-test–post-test MANCOVA revealed significant differences between the two conditions, Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.899$, $F(5,108) = 5.295$, $p = 0.003$, with an average effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.267$, $r = 0.32$).

Next, we performed ANCOVA for the dependent variables using the post-test scores. To assess the magnitude of these differences, the effect size for each variable was calculated by partial eta-squared (**Table 8**).

- *Effects on Subjective Well-Being*

There was no significant improvement in post-test health-related quality of life in the experimental group (**Table 8**). The experimental group did not show a significant increase in positive affect scores after testing. We confirmed a significant decrease in post-test negative affect scores in the experimental group (**Table 8**), with a medium effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.123$; partial eta-squared).

- *Effects on Trait Emotional Intelligence*

The analysis revealed significant improvements in trait emotional intelligence in the experimental group after the programme, with a medium effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.241$) (**Table 8**).

- *Effects on Social Anxiety*

There were no significant differences between the experimental and the control groups in SAS-T scores (**Table 8**).

7.4. Discussion

This study evaluated the impact of a pilot programme based on the sports education model on compulsory secondary education students' subjective well-being, trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety.

The preliminary results obtained in this study revealed significant improvement of a specific indicator of subjective well-being (NA) in the experimental group after the pilot programme. The experimental group did not show a significant improvement in health-related quality of life when compared with the control group. Our results are consistent with the findings reported in other studies (Puente-Maxera et al., 2018),

Table 8. Mean, standard deviation, analysis of variance, analysis of covariance and effect size for differences in means (partial eta-squared) as a function of the experimental and control groups at pre-test and post-test.

	PRE-TEST					POST-TEST				
	EXPERIMENTAL	CONTROL	F	p	η^2	EXPERIMENTAL	CONTROL	F	p	η^2
Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)				Mean (SD)				
KIDSCREEN										
HRQL	35.18 (5.84)	35.09 (6.01)	1.414	0.68	0.001	36.94 (6.14)	35.04 (5.99)	1.975	0.018	0.072
PANASN										
PA	21.43 (3.90)	20.02 (4.21)	3.293	0.07	0.008	21.95 (2.78)	20.33 (2.88)	5.438	0.017	0.144
NA	11.23 (3.54)	11.58 (3.58)	0.251	0.62	0.004	9.96 (2.95)	11.62 (3.86)	7.044	0.010	0.123
TEIQUE-ASF										
TEI	4.82 (0.60)	4.58 (0.64)	4.368	0.04	0.009	5.02 (0.63)	4.52 (0.53)	16.394	0.000	0.241
SAS										
SAS-T	2.61 (0.67)	2.64 (0.68)	0.040	0.84	-0.001	2.38 (0.63)	2.58 (0.62)	3.419	0.062	0.014

Note. HRQL = health-related quality of life; PA = positive affect; NA = negative affect; TEI = trait emotional intelligence; SAS-T = Total Social Anxiety Scale; SD = standard deviation.

which did not confirm significant benefits for life satisfaction among adolescents following a sport education-based experience. Our findings also indicated that the programme showed a significant decrease in negative affect, improving an indicator of the affective component of subjective well-being (e.g., a decrease in negative emotions) (Diener, 2000; Diener et al., 1999). These results partially verify Hypothesis 1, and highlight the importance of further research in this context.

This is consistent with the findings reported in other studies (Puente-Maxera et al., 2018), as previous studies established a connection between physical activity and subjective well-being (Biddle et al., 2000). These findings are also consistent with research that argues that active, inclusive and effective teaching and learning processes applied within a quality physical education framework fosters a motivating school climate in affective and psychological terms (Standage & Gillison, 2007; UNESCO, 2015). Pedagogical and methodological aspects highlighted by this intervention pilot programme (e.g., cooperative learning, a feeling of membership to a team, positive interdependence and self-management or autonomy/use of responsibility roles) could have influenced these results. Furthermore, a motivating school context, enabled by the implementation of the sport education model (Méndez-Giménez et al., 2017), may also strengthen affective bonding in adolescents (Bailey et al., 2009).

Significant improvement in trait emotional intelligence was observed in the experimental group after the programme, which confirmed Hypothesis 2. These results are also consistent with those reported by other authors (Méndez-Giménez et al., 2017). The relationship between trait emotional intelligence and subjective well-being (Sánchez-Álvarez et al., 2015; Zeidner et al., 2012), as well as that between trait emotional intelligence and physical and psychological health (Martins et al., 2010), may trigger these improvements in adolescents. This indicates that good trait emotional intelligence promotes positive emotional states and a reduction of negative moods, thereby positively impacting well-being and health (Zeidner et al., 2012).

We found no significant improvement in students' social anxiety, meaning that we could not confirm Hypothesis 3. Although this is similar to the results obtained by different authors for social relationships variables (Cuevas et al., 2015; Méndez-Giménez, Fernández-Río, et al., 2015), our results contradicted the findings of other studies (García-López & Gutiérrez, 2015; Kao, 2019; Menéndez-Santurio &

Fernández-Río, 2016; Wallhead et al., 2014). Further research on the effects of the sport education model is therefore necessary, especially given the theoretical specificity of social anxiety and its incidence in social relationships among adolescents. In addition, social anxiety can present opposing consequences. It can have positive effects on social relationships for some individuals, whereas it can have negative effects on others, characterised by anguish and social avoidance (La Greca & López, 1998).

However, in our opinion this study has been very exhaustive in the evaluation methodology of the intervention program (including the Bonferroni corrections). In this sense, we have not found any study on the effectiveness of the sport education model that uses these statistical corrections. This fact could be influencing the comparison of our results with those obtained in other similar researches on the sport education model as a teaching model.

Despite these promising results, this study had some limitations. First, the sampling procedure was chosen for reasons of convenience and not by random procedures. However, allocating students to either the experimental or control group was performed randomly based on the class group to which they belonged. Second, it would be necessary to increase the sample size to minimise potential biases in the results and increase the generalisability. Third, the instruments used were self-reported, and the results might have been influenced by bias related to social desirability in adolescents. It would be necessary to use high-performance tests or hetero-evaluation to minimise such bias. Similarly, differences in the trait emotional intelligence pre-test scores between the experimental and control groups might have had an impact on our results. Finally, it is necessary to highlight the difficulties encountered when following all of the recommendations for the implementation of the sport education model (Hastie & Casey, 2014). Similarly, it would be necessary to include session analysis procedure in order to evaluate if the main principles of the model were followed by the teachers (Práxedes et al., 2019).

Several aspects can be suggested regarding future lines of investigation, such as increasing the number of participants and diversifying their sociocultural background. It may also be worthwhile analysing the impact of the programme on other variables, such as academic performance and social and school adjustment. Similarly, to study the effects on depression with the use of biological correlates (HPA markers,

cortisol immunitarian parameters, etc.). In addition, it would be interesting to conduct a follow-up evaluation to assess the sustainability of the effects of the programme.

This study presents innovative contributions at both theoretical and practical levels. The theoretical contribution is related to fact that the lack of physical activity can have a harmful effect on individual's health and is currently an important public health concern (Haskell et al., 2009). In this respect, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (2015) emphasised the importance of fostering and promoting active behaviours (Whitehead, 2010) in all contexts, especially at schools. Consequently, it should be noted that there is a positive connection between health and physical activity: sedentarism is a major risk factor for mortality, which gives rise to concern about the prevalence of sedentarism and socio-educative patterns of inactivity, especially in school contexts. At a practical level, our findings may help teaching staff in their tasks at school, as they provide a tool that may be used in teaching practice. In addition, the findings open up interesting fields of research in terms of the application of sport education, especially in terms of its impact on psychological variables.

7.5. Conclusions

In conclusion, our findings suggest that the pilot programme stimulated some improvement in adolescents' subjective well-being and trait emotional intelligence, but did not impact social anxiety. Therefore, on the basis of quality physical education and the social and emotional learning approach, the implementation of such programmes is recommended given the possible psychological benefits for adolescents in the educational context. A commitment to sports and other physical-sport activity options within a quality physical education framework, efficiently applied by means of relevant pedagogical models (such as sport education), may play an important role in students' integral development (Eley & Kirk, 2002; Russell, 2005).

8. Manuscrito II. Social competence and peer social acceptance: evaluating effects of an educational intervention in adolescents

*“Confía en el tiempo, que suele dar dulces salidas a muchas amargas dificultades”
(Don Quijote de la Mancha)*

8.1. Introduction

Quality education requires attending to cognitive and affective-social dimensions that facilitate the physical and psychosocial development of students (UNESCO, 2015). The importance of the affective-social dimension in the success of the teaching and learning process in the educational context are issues that are arousing great interest in research (Franco et al., 2017; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2018; UNESCO, 2015). Accordingly, the teaching and learning process has an individual and social aspect (Franco et al., 2017), where the search for social objectives can boost school achievement (Cecchini Estrada et al., 2011; Elliot et al., 2006). To increase this success in the educational context, it is not only necessary to promote cognitive skills, but also to strengthen socio-emotional skills (Domitrovich et al., 2017; Greenberg et al., 2003; Payton, 2008; Taylor et al., 2017). Likewise, socio-emotional skills promote interpersonal relationships between students and other educational agents involved (Bessa et al., 2019; Garn et al., 2011; Kao, 2019). Therefore, it is relevant to promote optimal educational and motivational climates in educational contexts that favour a positive psychosocial adjustment and integral development of the student personality (Bisquerra et al., 2015).

The interest in the educational context for the social and emotional dimension, added to the promotion of satisfactory interpersonal skills (being and feeling accepted) (Zhang et al., 2014) have highlighted that social behaviour plays an essential role in the abilities of students, especially in adolescents (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017) favouring school success (Cappadocia & Weiss, 2011). It has been recognized that social competence is an inclusive, evaluative, and multidimensional construct (e.g., socio-emotional skills; emotional regulation; prosocial behaviour; ability to adapt normatively; social adjustment or perceived effectiveness in social interactions) that cannot be understood from a unilateral perspective (Dirks et al., 2007; Losada, 2018; Santos et al., 2013).

Gómez-Ortiz et al. (2019) define social competence as the effectiveness in social interaction, which arises from the use of socio-emotional skills to achieve personal goals over time and in different situations. In this way, social competence encompasses a series of cognitive, social, and emotional abilities of the individual, to manage the interpersonal relationships that occur in different contexts, favouring

healthier relationships among others (Del Prette & Del Prette, 2005). Gresham (1988) divides social competence into the following elements: (1) adaptive behaviour (physical and language development, academic competencies and independent functional skills); (2) interpersonal behaviours (cooperative and play behaviours; conversation and regulatory acceptance skills); (3) self-perceived behaviours (of oneself: expressing ethical and positive feelings and behaviours); and (4) behaviours towards homework (attention, task resolution, and individual work).

Thereby, social competence is related to the adjustment to the demands of the school environment, interpersonal relationships, emotional health and acceptance among peers (Losada et al., 2017). Also, it would be pertinent to examine and evaluate, through programs or interventions, the impact of this competence or interpersonal skills in the educational context (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017, 2019; Losada et al., 2017), especially in adolescent students, because it is a period of maturation and sensitive adaptation (typical transitions of this stage) for personal, social and emotional development (Bessa et al., 2019; Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017, 2019). Therefore, social competence plays a vital role in the educational process, since it is necessary to favour positive and quality learning (Del Prette & Del Prette, 2005; Elijah & Madeira, 2013).

A primary objective in the educational context is to promote healthy lifestyles (WHO, 2016), active and participatory (Pate & Dowda, 2019). Accordingly, physical education, within the framework of a Physical Education of quality reinforcing prosocial practices (UNESCO, 2015) is instrumentalized as an effective subject to favour an integral commitment of students (Escalié et al., 2017; Whitehead, 2010) by positively developing their cognitive, affective, physical and social spheres (Kao, 2019; Mitchell & Hutchinson, 2003; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). The Association for Physical Education (afPE) (2015) states that quality Physical Education acts as a starting point for a commitment to physical activity and sport throughout life. Thus, this subject provides students with active, cooperative and practical resources (Girard et al., 2019) that improve experiences in the school environment (Kohl & Cook, 2013; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). Similarly, it encourages students to develop personal and social skills in a real environment that in other subjects would be more complex to teach (Hellison, 2011).

Physical Education is recognized for playing a relevant role in the acquisition of values and competences that contribute to the personal and socio-emotional

development of students (Bessa et al., 2019). Thereby, some authors point out that through adequately structured and planned interventions, it could contribute to the social development of students in the subject of Physical Education (Eldar, 2008; Gil-Madrona et al., 2019; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019; Unlu et al., 2011). Physical Education offers the student a meaningful learning experience driven by the development of social skills (interpersonal interactions, tolerance, and respect) (Cronin et al., 2018; Kao, 2019); social responsibility adherence and team cohesion: group affiliation or identity, cooperative work (Brinkley et al., 2017; Cronin et al., 2018); and reinforcement of the development of social cognition (Bailey, 2006). Therefore, quality Physical Education (UNESCO, 2015) will be a crucial ally in the educational context, to promote positive environments in the development of prosocial behaviours (Mayfield et al., 2017), as long as they are promoted in active, participatory and motivating contexts (Shields et al., 2018).

Consequently, it is relevant in the educational context to configure a path of methodological renewal that evolves, as established by (UNESCO, 2015), toward a quality Physical Education for the interrelation of inclusive, active and participatory teaching and learning, over against a Physical Education, traditionally based on processes linked only to memorized methodology and mechanized and specific motor skills (e.g., technification and performance) (González-Víllora et al., 2009). Therefore, we look for methodological experiences that promote positive pedagogical practices with interventions based on teaching models (IM: *Instructional Models*) (Metzler, 2017) or based on practice (MsBP: *Models-Based Practice*) (Casey, 2014). These pedagogical models developed in a safe and contextualized way (Casey & MacPhail, 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2019) versus traditional decontextualized educational models (DI: *Direct Instruction*) (Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019) will be more motivating for students and will significantly improve the practice of physical-sports content, social and interpersonal relationships (Gil-Arias et al., 2017).

The Sport Education Model (SEM) (Bessa et al., 2019; Hastie and Wallhead, 2016; Kao, 2019; Luna et al., 2019; Siedentop et al., 2020) is among the most suitable pedagogical models (Iserbyt et al., 2016) to develop the affective-social dimension of students. This is a model (MsBP) whose purpose is that all students live authentic sports experiences (Siedentop et al., 2020). Likewise, the SEM (Siedentop, 1994) intends to develop competent, enthusiastic, and physically (Whitehead, 2010) and

sportingly literate students (Kolovelonis & Goudas, 2018). Thus, UNESCO (2015) reports that the practice of healthy and active sports activities in organized games and sports, such as those planned and developed in the SEM and instrumentalized in quality Physical Education, show a positive impact on psychosocial adjustment of students, as well as in their emotional, physical, and cognitive dimension. Therefore, it is a favourable pedagogical model for proactive social development, positive responsibility, and more equitable and inclusive learning (Farias et al., 2019).

In the same line, some systematic reviews conclude that through interventions based on the SEM, there are improvements in technical-tactical skills (physical and cognitive physical domain), social and emotional development (Evangelio et al., 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2018) and motivational aspects (Chu & Zhang, 2018). In addition, meta-analysis (e.g., Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019) confirms benefits in motivation towards physical and sports activity, belonging and social responsibility, autonomy, and organization. Recent SEM results show positive effects on motor behaviours (Araújo et al., 2019; Pereira et al., 2015; Wahl-Alexander & Chomentowski, 2018), technical-tactical skills (Farias et al., 2015) and activity, knowledge and physical performance (Ward et al., 2017). Also, improvements in trait emotional intelligence and subjective well-being (Luna et al., 2019), motivation (Cuevas et al., 2016; Gil-Arias et al., 2017), social cohesion and social skills (Kao, 2019; Pan et al., 2019), attitudes towards violence, social responsibility and friendly relations (Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016), assertiveness (García-López & Gutiérrez, 2015) and social relations (Perlman, 2010) have been found. However, regarding the statistical analysis of the data, in most of these previous studies, the change/gain score through analysis of variance (ANOVA) (that is, posttest minus pretest) was used as a criterion group comparison. In this sense, some authors such as Pérez-González & Qualter (2018) recommend the use of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) where the covariate is the baseline or pretest score, controlling for the possible effect of the pretest score on the results of the posttest. Criteria followed in the present study are in the same line as other authors (e.g., Kao, 2019; Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019; Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016; Pan et al., 2019).

On the other hand, it is necessary to point out that there are stereotyped preconceptions and sports discrimination based on gender (Leaper, 2011; Parker & Curtner-Smith, 2012). Along these lines, some previous studies on interventions based

on SEM have not shown differences in their impact, depending on gender, physical abilities (Araújo et al., 2019) and socio-emotional skills (Evangelio et al., 2018). On the contrary, other researches have shown differences in impact, depending on gender: some studies conclude that boys have greater improvements than girls in social interactions (Brock et al., 2009; Hastie, Sinelnikov, et al., 2009), while other research confirms more significant improvements in girls than in boys in technical-tactical sports knowledge (Mesquita et al., 2012).

Accordingly to all this, the purpose of the current study was to evaluate the effects of a SEM-based intervention, compared to an intervention based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI), in adolescents on the variables: (1) social competence and (2) social acceptance among peers. Regarding the hypotheses, it was proposed that said intervention (based on the SEM) would improve the participants' social competence (H1) and social acceptance among peers (H2). Finally, the impact of the intervention would not show differences, depending on gender (H3) in line with previous studies (Evangelio et al., 2018).

8.2. Materials and Methods

8.2.1. Design

A randomised experimental design was conducted with two repeated measures (pretest and posttest). The participants were randomly assigned to the experimental group (EG) and control group (CG) through a randomised controlled group trial.

8.2.2. Participants

The total sample was composed of 114 adolescents, aged between 12 and 15 years (mean age (M) = 13.41 years; standard deviation (SD) = 0.81 years). Regarding the sociodemographic distribution of the sample: (a) by gender, 52% were girls, and 48% were boys; (b) by age, 35% were 12 years old, 48% 13 years old, 15% 14 years old, and 2% 15 years old. The differences in the two conditions (experimental and control groups) were not significant by age ($\chi^2 = 1.08$, $p > 0.05$) or by gender ($\chi^2 = 1.14$, $p > 0.05$).

The criteria for inclusion ($n = 106$) in the study were: (1) regular attendance to school ($\geq 80\%$ of attendance) and (2) informed written consent from the parents (or legal guardian). The exclusion criteria ($n = 8$) were: (1) attend less than 80% of the educational intervention sessions (less than 13 sessions); (2) students with more than 30% truancy; (3) students with special educational needs; (4) students sanctioned for disciplinary reasons by the school; (5) did not obtain informed written consent from the parents (or legal guardian). The 106 participants who met the proposed criteria were randomly assigned to the EG ($n = 62$) or the CG ($n = 44$). Participant flow is displayed below (refer to **Figure 14**).

Figure 14. Participant Flow Diagram: interventions based on the Sport Education model (SEM) (EG = experimental group); Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) (CG = control group).

8.2.3. Measures

In this investigation, two measures have been used to evaluate the proposed variables.

Adolescent Multidimensional Social Competence Questionnaire (AMSC-Q).

The Adolescent Multidimensional Social Competence Questionnaire (AMSC-Q) has been used to assess social competence. The instrument was validated in Spanish for its use with Spanish adolescents (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017). The AMSC-Q contains 26 Likert-type items scored on a scale from 1 to 7 (1 = *completely false*; 7 = *completely true*). This instrument measures five factors of social competence: cognitive reappraisal, social adjustment, prosocial behaviour, perceived social efficacy, and normative adjustment. In the current study, the evidences of reliability are the following: cognitive reappraisal ($\alpha = 0.71$; $\Omega = 0.70$); social adjustment ($\alpha = 0.84$; $\Omega = 0.83$); prosocial behaviour ($\alpha = 0.76$; $\Omega = 0.72$); perceived social efficacy ($\alpha = 0.80$; $\Omega = 0.77$); and normative adjustment ($\alpha = 0.79$; $\Omega = 0.79$).

Guess Who Questionnaire (GW4). The Guess Who questionnaire (GW4) (Mavroveli et al., 2009); version adapted to Spanish by Losada et al. (2017) has been used to assess social acceptance among peers (SA). The GW4 is made up of four indicators of social behaviour or attributes based on descriptors of habitual behaviour patterns (kind; stalker; cooperator; leader). The descriptor *kind* indicates classmates who take into account the feelings of others, are friendly, and are generous with their things. The descriptor *stalker* is defined as classmates who often mess with other children, hit them, or behave unpleasantly for no reason. The descriptor *cooperator* indicates the classmates with whom they would form a group because they collaborate, participate, share, and respect others. The descriptor *leader* indicates peers who lead and encourage to keep going. Likewise, based on the results in each of the four indicators, a global score or Index of Social Acceptance (ISA) may be calculated, as a result of adding the nominations in the three prosocial domains and subsequently subtracting the score obtained in the antisocial domain. Previously, the nominations received in the four descriptors have to be transformed into percentages. In calculating the percentages for each descriptor, the account is taken of the total number of students in the class group, the total number of students responding in the class group, and the number of nominations allowed, which is unlimited, but at a minimum would be equal to one. The maximum number of nominations from one student is equal to

the total number of students minus the nominating subject (Losada et al., 2017). In the current study, the evidence of reliability for the ISA is $\alpha = 0.76$; $\Omega = 0.79$.

8.2.4. Procedure

The study design was developed in four periods. In the first period, the educational intervention was designed. Secondly, a pretest assessment (T1) was carried out in the experimental and control group, administering the assessment instruments with scheduled breaks to avoid student fatigue. The pretest evaluation was carried out as a group. The administration of the pretest evaluations was carried out by two members of the research team different from the teachers who implemented the program. In the third period, the educational intervention based on the SEM was applied in the EG, while in the CG, scheduled sessions of the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) were developed. To minimize the effect of the experimenter on the results, the participating adolescents, and the teachers who applied each of the interventions were unaware of the hypotheses and objectives of the research team (single-blind procedure). Both happened during the Physical Education class on school hours. In the last period, at the end of the intervention, the posttest assessment (T2) was carried out in both groups, following the same rest procedure as in T1. Posttest evaluations were administered by two members of the research team different from the teachers who carried out the program. The posttest evaluation was developed in groups.

8.2.5. Ethical Considerations

This study has been developed under the University of Castilla-La Mancha (UCLM) code of ethics, following international guidelines on experiments with human subjects described in the Nuremberg Code and the Declaration of Helsinki. The Management Team, the School Board, and the Teachers of the participating school authorized the investigation since it is an investigation framed within a public educational context. An informed written consent for the participating students was signed by a parent or legal guardian. Likewise, the requirements of ethical confidentiality were respected and guaranteed according to the voluntary and anonymous nature of the participants (ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association [APA], 2019; Personal Data Protection Law of the Research Ethics Committee on Human Beings, CEISH).

8.2.6. Educational Intervention

Two educational interventions were developed: in the experimental group, the intervention was based on the Sport Education model (SEM) (Siedentop et al., 2020) and in the control group, the intervention was based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) (Metzler, 2017). Both were applied simultaneously during school hours by teachers specialized in Physical Education. One of the teachers developed the SEM-based intervention in the experimental group. This teacher has 15 years of teaching experience and three years applying the SEM in Physical Education (ecological validity). A different teacher applied a Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) in the control group. This teacher has ten years of teaching experience, without previous SEM experience. They were carried out during 16 sessions of 55 minutes each, with a frequency of two sessions per week (refer to **Table 9**). A sport of split teams or net (Polskie ringo) was used for both groups of adolescents (Méndez-Giménez et al., 2011). This alternative sport, which was new for the participating students, is played in teams on a sports field divided in two by a central volleyball net. Players must throw, receive and pass a ring over the net, scoring when the ring falls on the field of the opposite team.

Characteristics of the Intervention Based on the Sport Education model (SEM).

The intervention design was developed following precisely and adequately the structure of the SEM (Siedentop et al., 2020) and the recommendations made by Hastie & Casey (2014). The educational experience was organized as follows: (1) *season*: long-term teaching unit; (2) *affiliation* and/or *team membership*: development of group identity and interpersonal cooperation; (3) performance of *rotating responsibility roles* (e.g., referee, captain, physical trainer, journalists, festival committee): individual and shared decision-making; (4) *regular competition*: practice of technical-tactical knowledge; (5) *data recording*: information gathering and analysis of the learning process; (6) *culminating and festive event*: final objectives for all students in a festive and motivating way.

The intervention was implemented for around two months, in a public educational centre, within a rural environment and with a medium socioeconomic level. Likewise, it was supervised by external researchers, consisting of: (a) personal and online

communication to solve possible issues; (b) regular visits to the school; (c) analysis and weekly verification of the research process.

The selection and training of the teams were carried out randomly (to break present groups). The educational practice was developed in different academic classes of Secondary Education (3 experimental groups with 5 teams in each) setting a total of 15 mixed teams with a random distribution of each participant following the principle of homogeneity according to gender and level of motor ability (Burgueño et al., 2017). All students of each team were always assigned two roles: one common to all (player) and another specific to each student: (1) *captain-coach* (coordinator and mediator of the team, in addition to acting as a communicative link between teachers-students and vice versa); (2) *referee* (in charge of the functions of conciliation and fair play of sports practice, in addition to being responsible for compliance with the rules of the game and formalization of the minutes and match reports); (3) *journalist* (in charge of statistics, data recording, and managing digital communication with an informative sports blog previously created); (4) *physical trainer* (direction of previous sports warm-ups and responsible for the team's sports equipment); and (5) *celebration organizing committee* (responsible for self-built materials, coordinator and manager of final festive events). This educational strategy of the rotating role aims to encourage students to develop social skills such as empathy, providing them with different tasks and insights.

In short, this is a real and educational sport experience that aims to engage students with a motivating methodology focused on cooperative teaching and learning processes between internal groups as elements such as the development of a formal competition (regular league focused on fair and social game), self-construction of their own sports materials (such as the ring for the game, medals, trophies or diplomas) (Méndez-Giménez et al., 2016) or the celebration of the final event, making the personal and social development of the adolescents more significant (Bessa et al., 2019).

Characteristics of the Intervention Based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI).

A teaching unit about Polskie ringo was designed and implemented according to a traditional methodology (Metzler, 2017; Pan et al., 2019). The methodological characteristics of Direct Instruction were: (a) teaching and learning process focused

on an outstanding position of the teachers, favouring an expository and unidirectional communication to the students; (b) transmission of educational content by teachers without student intervention (only occasionally for demonstration by modelling); (c) assignment of tasks mostly centred on decisions made by teachers, where students play a passive role, that is, a teaching style where only the teacher directs and determines the tasks, objectives, evaluation, rhythm and learning time of the planned sessions and activities; (d) development of an educational experience, by students, with sports activities characterized by technical, memorial, and repetitive motor skills individually; (e) mass education with no individualization, using sports materials provided by the school; (f) learning of decontextualized sports fundamentals and without experiencing real sports experience, that is, characterized by a first orientation of skills where students practice sports learning in isolation.

Table 9. *Sequence of sessions and activities in the educational interventions.*

SESSION	SEM (experimental group)	TM-DI (control group)
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Theoretical explanation of SEM and Polskie ringo. – Delivery of teaching material (folders; match records; reports; game rules; contingency contract, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Theoretical explanation of Polskie ringo (regulatory aspects).
2-3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Training and organization of teams (choice of thematic names, hymns/emblems, identifying colours, etc.). – Designation of rotating responsibility roles. – Self-construction of material by student art (e.g., Polskie ringo ring). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Organization of students individually or in pairs (no persistent work groups are formed). – Presentation of sports equipment provided by the school. – Technical development activities (pass, launch and reception I).
4-7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Warm-up and stretching with modified sports games, directed by the teacher and students (role of physical trainer). – Activities (by teams and using rotating roles of responsibility) aimed at learning technical and tactical skills of Polskie ringo (pass, serve, reception, throwing, displacements). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Warm-up sessions led by the teacher. – Activities to develop technical skills repetitively (pass and reception II). – Technical development activities (serve).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reflective-comprehensive meetings (positive feedback; active listening; learning-error). – Knowledge of rules through the real game (fair play = sport key element). – Pre-season or training for the championship (educational competition). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Technical development activities (throwing). – Technical development activities (displacement). – Completion with stretching exercises, led by the teacher. Also, the teacher instructs the students for the improvement of the movements developed.
8-14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Friendly team matches and educational competition (fair play) through a formal and regular league (Round Robin). – Development of responsibility roles (e.g., referee, journalist, captain...). – Use of real sports elements (minutes, interviews, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Sports warm-up. – Tactical development activities 1 vs 1. – Tactical development activities 2 vs 2. – Tactical development activities 3 vs 3. – Simultaneous Polskie ringo games. – Final stretching exercises led by the teacher.
15-16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Semi-final and final competition between classes. – Event with final festival (organized by the role of committee): delivery of trophies, diplomas and medals (self-built materials). – Summative or final evaluation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Individual theoretical assessment of Polskie ringo (regulatory aspects). – Individual practical evaluation of Polskie ringo (technical elements).

8.2.7. Statistical Analysis

Following collection, data were analysed with the SPSS software, version 24.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). First, the normality of the variables under study was calculated with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, all of them adjusting to the assumption of normality (analyses performed with a 95% confidence interval). Second, the evidence of reliability was calculated with the reliability coefficient of Cronbach's alpha (α) and the McDonald's omega coefficient (Ω). Third, to determine the effectiveness of the educational intervention, the following statistical analyses were performed: (1) multivariate analyses of variance (MANOVA) with the total pretest scores of the variables under study, to confirm possible starting (initial) differences between the

participants of the EG and CG; (2) descriptive (M = mean; SD = standard deviation) and variance (ANOVA) analyses with each of the scores obtained for the instruments used during the pretest phase; (3) in order to show significant improvements between the experimental and control group, multivariate analyses of covariance (MANCOVA) were calculated on the set of variables investigated; (4) descriptive analyses, and covariance analyses (ANCOVA) with posttest scores; (5) finally, the effect size of the differences was calculated with partial square eta (μ^2) following four statistical ranges (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007): 0-0.009, *negligible*; 0.010-0.089, *low-effect size*; 0.090-0.249, *medium-effect size*; and >0.250, *big-effect size*.

8.3. Results

The pretest MANOVA results did not reveal statistically significant differences between the groups prior to the intervention, Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.491$; $F(9,97) = 0.572$; $p = 0.273$, with a low effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.028$; $r = 0.04$).

8.3.1. Pretest Analysis

The results of ANOVA in the pretest phase (refer to **Table 10**) showed that before starting the intervention, there were no statistically significant differences in any of the study variables.

8.3.2. Posttest Analysis

The results for the pretest-posttest MANCOVA did not reveal statistically significant differences between the two conditions, Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.862$; $F(9, 97) = 1.661$; $p = 0.187$, with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.081$; $r = 0.10$).

■ *Effects on Social Competence*

After performing ANCOVA in the posttest phase (refer to **Table 10**), the results confirmed, in favour of the EG, significant improvements in: social adjustment, with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.064$); prosocial behaviour, with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.078$); perceived social efficacy, with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.072$) (refer to **Figure 15**). However, no significant differences were confirmed in the other two factors, cognitive reappraisal and normative adjustment.

■ *Effects on Social Acceptance Among Peers*

The results in the ANCOVA in the posttest phase (refer to **Table 10**) showed significant improvements in the cooperator factor with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.027$) in favour of the EG. Likewise, the results showed significant improvements in favour of the experimental group in the global index of social acceptance among peers of this variable, with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.045$) (refer to **Figure 15**). However, there were no significant differences in the other indicators: kind, stalker, and leader.

▪ *Effects on Gender*

The results of ANOVA for the pretest phase showed that before beginning the intervention, there were no statistically significant differences, depending on gender, in any of the study variables. Similarly, the results in the ANCOVA for the posttest phase did not show differential effects between boys and girls in any of the study variables.

8.4. Discussion

The current study evaluated the effects of an intervention based on the SEM, compared to an intervention based on the TM-DI, on social competence and social acceptance among adolescents. It is necessary to highlight that recent studies raise the need to continue examining the impact of SEM-based interventions in adolescents (Bessa et al., 2019; Evangelio et al., 2018; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019).

In general, the results showed statistically significant improvements, in favour of the experimental group (SEM) compared to the control group (MT-ID): (1) in some indicators of social competence; social adjustment, prosocial behaviour, and perceived social efficacy. However, no significant improvements in cognitive reappraisal and normative adjustment were confirmed; (2) improvements in social acceptance among peers; specifically, in the *cooperator* factor and in the global index of social acceptance among peers. Although no improvements were found in the factors: *kind*, *stalker*, and *leader*.

Table 10. Mean, standard deviation, analysis of variance, analysis of covariance, and effect size for differences in means (partial square eta) in the variables under study (social competence and peer social acceptance) in the experimental and control groups.

	Pretest				ANOVA			Posttest				ANCOVA		
	EG		GC		F	p	μ^2	EG		CG		F	p	μ^2
	M	SD	M	SD				M	SD	M	SD			
SC														
Cognitive reappraisal	4.68	1.35	4.71	1.40	0.453	0.915	0.002	4.72	1.40	4.68	1.42	0.454	0.243	0.010
Social adjustment	5.48	1.41	5.53	4.58	1.231	0.534	0.003	6.03	1.56	5.41	1.52	2.731	0.011	0.064
Prosocial behaviour	5.45	1.38	5.67	1.31	0.915	0.246	0.004	6.07	1.53	5.72	1.48	3.447	0.002	0.078
Perceived social efficacy	5.37	1.44	5.41	1.65	1.472	0.717	0.003	6.09	1.48	5.32	1.72	4.315	0.008	0.072
Normative adjustment	5.59	1.51	5.54	1.39	0.882	0.766	0.002	5.61	1.48	5.50	1.42	0.744	0.816	0.009
SA														
Kind	0.31	0.10	0.32	0.14	0.617	1.014	0.009	0.34	0.11	0.30	0.15	1.126	0.414	0.011
Stalker	0.27	0.18	0.25	0.20	0.074	0.879	0.007	0.25	0.13	0.26	0.19	0.933	0.736	0.001
Cooperator	0.28	0.15	0.30	0.12	1.011	0.731	0.003	0.37	0.12	0.29	0.11	2.732	0.008	0.027
Leader	0.16	0.20	0.19	0.18	0.873	0.512	0.004	0.19	0.19	0.16	0.21	0.899	0.122	0.007
Index of Social Acceptance	0.77	0.48	0.81	0.41	0.342	0.873	0.002	0.87	0.45	0.75	0.40	3.715	0.010	0.045

Note. SC: social competence; SA: peer social acceptance; μ^2 = eta square effect size; EG: experimental group ($n = 62$); CG: control group ($n = 44$); M: mean; SD: standard deviation.

Figure 15. Statistically significant effects of SEM (pretest-posttest) in experimental group and control group.

First, the results showed significant improvements in some indicators of social competence. Therefore, Hypothesis 1 is partially confirmed. Specifically, the positive impact has focused on (1) social adjustment, that is, the degree to which an adolescent engages in socially competent behaviours, whose purpose is social acceptance; (2) prosocial behaviour, defined as voluntary behaviours whose purpose is to benefit others (sharing, caring, comforting or helping); and (3) perceived social efficacy, or the subjective perception of effectiveness in social interactions. These results converge with other previous research papers that analyse the effectiveness of interventions based on the SEM in some socio-emotional variables (Bessa et al., 2019; García-López & Gutiérrez, 2015; González-Víllora et al., 2018; Kao, 2019; Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019; Antonio Méndez-Giménez et al., 2016; Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016; Pan et al., 2019; Perlman, 2010). The results of these previous investigations confirm in the variables under consideration, effect sizes between low and moderate, in line with those obtained in this study.

Secondly, the results show some significant improvements in the variable social acceptance among peers, specifically in the *cooperator* indicator and the global social acceptance score or *Index of Social Acceptance* (ISA). Hypothesis 2 is partially confirmed. These findings are in line with other research that has shown the positive impact of MbBP-SEM on the social relationship (García-López and Gutiérrez, 2015; Kao, 2019; Menéndez-Santurio and Fernández-Río, 2016). The conclusions of these previous investigations in the variables being considered point to effect sizes between low and moderate, in congruence with those obtained in the current study. As we can see, the effects obtained in social competence are higher than those obtained in social acceptance. In this sense, the nuclear aspects of the MED are probably closer to the development of helping behaviours towards others, that is, towards efficacy in social interaction (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2019) than to the social acceptance within the group.

Third, the results did not confirm differential effects between boys and girls in any of the study variables. These results are consistent with those obtained in some systematic reviews that conclude that the development of interventions based on the SEM has shown improvements in the participants in empathy, assertiveness, and fair play, regardless of gender (e.g., Evangelio et al., 2018). However, it is necessary to deepen this line of research. On the one hand, numerous studies conclude that girls have higher social skills scores than boys; while, boys have higher levels of rejection

compared to girls (Bandura et al., 2006) due to the contradictory and inconclusive results concerning the different impact of SEM-based interventions on boys and girls (Evangelio et al., 2018).

These positive results used in the social competence indicators probably favour adaptive interpersonal relationships (Eisenberg et al., 2006). In the same way, this improvement in social interaction among peers may be influenced by the intrapersonal and interpersonal emotional regulation strategies underlying the successful adaptation of adolescents to the requirements in social relationships (Mestre-Navas & Guil, 2012). Also, social acceptance is positively related to the behaviours that help to follow the rules of collective games and be actively involved in adaptive interactions with their peers (Trianes et al., 1999).

Another possible explanation of these results could be the methodology used in the intervention, based on cooperative learning and encouraging the motivation of the participants (Casey, 2014; Gil-Madrona et al., 2019; González-Víllora et al., 2018; Metzler, 2017; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019) as well as, for the improvement of assertiveness, cooperation, autonomy and positive communication among peers (García-López and Gutiérrez, 2015). Also, the intervention aims to favour team sport and increase the responsibility of each participant in achieving a common goal (Kolovelonis & Goudas, 2018; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2011; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2016). Authors such as Washington et al. (2001) consider sport as a fundamental tool for social transformation, which will allow the promotion of cooperative learning through the assignment and distribution of responsibility roles (Siedentop et al., 2020) and will foster enthusiasm and enjoyment for an educational and cooperative sports practice (Evangelio et al., 2018; Gil-Madrona et al., 2019; Iserbyt et al., 2016; Pan et al., 2019).

Likewise, it is necessary to highlight that adolescence is a crucial stage for the development of socio-emotional competencies, since adolescents experience this stage with constant and typical maturational and emotional transitions of greater social difficulty (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017, 2019). In this sense, identifying, controlling and managing socio-emotional competences contribute to optimize teaching and learning processes, strengthening social interaction among adolescents (Ang & Penney, 2013; Cañabate et al., 2018; Del Prette & Del Prette, 2005; Evangelio et al., 2018; Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017; Losada et al., 2017) and can favour an efficient evaluation of the educational practice made by the teachers (Lee et al., 2019).

8.4.1. Limitations and Future Directions

The current study had some limitations. First, it would have been necessary to carry out a follow-up evaluation of the intervention to analyse the long-term effect on the variables studied. Secondly, it would be necessary to use instruments completed by teachers or families that improve the assessment of the variables studied. Thirdly, it would be necessary to include a session analysis procedure in order to assess whether teachers followed the main principles of the model (formative evaluation) (Práxedes et al., 2019). Fourth, it is necessary to point out that the results obtained in Hypothesis 3 should be interpreted with great caution due to the sample size. However, studies that analyse this aspect should be carried out (Evangelio et al., 2018). Fifth, in terms of minimizing the effect of the experimenter, it would have been necessary for the posttest evaluation to use the balancing procedure of the members of the research team that administered the tests in each of the experimental conditions.

One of the most relevant contributions of the present study was the use of statistical analysis through ANCOVA, which evaluates the effectiveness of educational interventions as opposed to other statistical methods, such as the use of ANOVA, which evaluates changes or gains. These findings, through appropriate statistical procedures, could enrich research concerning SEM (e.g., Kao, 2019; Luna et al., 2019; Menéndez-Santurio and Fernández-Río, 2016; Pan et al., 2019).

Finally, it is necessary to highlight the difficulties in following the recommendations of the SEM in teaching sessions (Hastie & Casey, 2014; Siedentop et al., 2020). On the other hand, future lines of research could be: (1) to increase the sample and diversify the socio-cultural environment of adolescents; (2) assessment of the variables involved in the improvements obtained through these interventions, such as emotional regulation strategies (intrapersonal and interpersonal).

8.5. Conclusions

These significant results are likely due, as some research suggests, to the positive synergy among physical activity developed in positive environments (Escalié et al., 2017; Gil-Madrona et al., 2019; Mayfield et al., 2017; Shields et al., 2018) such as quality Physical Education (afPE, 2015; Shields et al., 2018; UNESCO, 2015) with affective and/or psychosocial factors (Kao, 2019; Pate & Dowda, 2019; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). Said context will facilitate in students better pedagogical strategies

(Girard et al., 2019) that make socio-emotional learning more positive (Brinkley et al., 2017; Cronin et al., 2018; Mayfield et al., 2017) and therefore, improve their educational experience (Kohl & Cook, 2013; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019).

It is relevant to note that these findings suggest that when classes are developed with a quality Physical Education (UNESCO, 2015) using effective pedagogical models such as the SEM (Franco et al., 2017), students show high levels of positive emotions and social skills favouring peer interactions, clear evidence of cooperation, and human relationships that promote prosocial coexistence (Cañabate et al., 2018).

9. Manuscrito III. Subjective well-being and psychosocial adjustment: Examining the effects of an intervention based on the Sport Education Model on children

*“Donde una puerta se cierra, otra se abre”
(Don Quijote de la Mancha)*

9.1. Introduction

Subjective well-being encompasses two dimensions (Diener, 2000) the affective dimension (positive and negative affect), and the cognitive dimension (satisfaction with life) (Diener, 2000; Diener et al., 1999). Likewise, subjective well-being (Diener et al., 1999) has been identified with positive emotions and the absence of negative emotions (Ryff & Keyes, 1995). It could be also considered as an interesting predictor of physical health, interpersonal relationships and the correct bio-psychosocial development of individuals (Diener & Biswas-Diener, 2008). Some authors argue for the need and importance of improving subjective well-being in the population (Sánchez-Álvarez et al., 2015). It is appropriate, then, that this psychological construct is becoming prominent in educational research and its influence in the social (Lyubomirsky & Lepper, 1999) and school contexts (Campbell, 1981) is relevant.

On the other hand, McMahon et al. (2017) argue that physical activity and sport practice are positively related to well-being and negatively related to psychosocial indicators such as anxiety. In this line of thought, subjective well-being, as a critical factor in the educational context, is related to variables such as psychosocial adjustment (Diener & Fujita, 1995; Huebner et al., 2000). Rodríguez-Fernández et al. (2016) interpret psychosocial adjustment as an association of school adjustment (or school commitment) and subjective well-being. The psychosocial adjustment construct refers to the ability of people to adapt to the demands of the social context (Reynolds & Kamphaus, 2004). In recent years, a considerable increase in behavioral and adaptive problems has been observed in children in the family and socio-school environment, being a cause of concern both for educational institutions and for society in general (Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2016). For this reason, it is essential to promote a positive psychosocial adjustment of the students in order to promote a healthy adaptation to the physical, psychological, social and affective environments (Baker et al., 2003), while also becoming a beneficial factor for subjective well-being (UNESCO, 2015).

A primary objective within the educational context should be to promote active and participatory lifestyle habits (Pate & Dowda, 2019). Some studies establish a positive relationship between physical-sport activity and some variables such as subjective well-being (Biddle et al., 2000) and health and psychosocial adjustment

(Biddle et al., 2000; Committee on Sports Medicine and Fitness and Committee on School Health, 2001). Therefore, increasing healthy physical and sport practices among less active youth should be a crucial objective of community and school institutions and interventions to promote well-being (McMahon et al., 2017).

Escalié et al. (2017) emphasize the importance of balanced student development. The educational system needs to foster motivating and competent environments that are significant for a positive psychosocial adjustment and, therefore, for the integral development of the student's personality (Bisquerra et al., 2015). However, internalizing and externalizing adaptive behaviors in children are increasing, and the intervention processes are not always effective (Restrepo & Rivera, 2017). In this sense, our study is in line with educational programs that promote balanced student development and aim to improve the different dimensions of children's evolutionary development: physical dimension, cognitive dimension, and affective-social dimension (Metzler, 2017). It is essential to promote motivating, participatory and active interventions (Shields et al., 2018) driven by effective pedagogical models (Iserbyt et al., 2016).

Several pedagogical models share these same characteristics (Metzler, 2017). Among the most suitable (Iserbyt et al., 2016) is the Sport Education Model (SEM) (Bessa et al., 2019; Siedentop et al., 2020) articulated as a curricular teaching model within a quality Physical Education that favors an effective motor, affective, and social commitment in students (UNESCO, 2015). The SEM is understood within a pedagogical framework based on practice, whose two main objectives are: (1) allowing students to develop authentic sport experiences, simulating the real aspects of the game, and adapting them to the educational context; (2) encouraging students to acquire competence, enthusiasm, and physical sport culture (Kolovelonis & Goudas, 2018). This is a constructivist and cooperative student-centered pedagogy (Kirk, 2013) instead of repetitive sport experiences developed in physical education based on the traditional model of Direct Instruction focused on teachers (Kirk, 2013; Metzler, 2017; Pan et al., 2019).

The SEM has attracted considerable interest in recent years from researchers and educational professionals, with different systematic reviews published (e.g., Hastie et al., 2011; Wallhead & O'sullivan, 2005). In the review by Hastie et al. (2011) improvements using the model (SEM) were confirmed in: physical fitness, knowledge,

understanding, and technical-tactical ability. In other words, improvements included effective learning of the sport game; personal and social development; positive and attractive attitudes towards Physical Education (e.g., enthusiasm and enjoyment); educational values (e.g., respect, affinity, fairness, fair play, etc.). Similarly, other more recent reviews confirm a positive impact of SEM on physical, social, and emotional development (Evangelio et al., 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2018), ethical development (Harvey et al., 2014), as well as in motivational indicators (Chu & Zhang, 2018). Furthermore, authors such as Sierra-Díaz et al. (2019), in their meta-analysis, show improvements in motivation towards physical and sport activity, belonging and social responsibility, autonomy and organization using the SEM.

A review of the scientific literature shows the scarcity of studies on educational interventions in Physical Education, based on the SEM, that evaluate the effects of the variables of the present investigation (subjective well-being and psychosocial adjustment). However, based on the scientific literature, it would be logical to think of possible positive effects of the SEM on these variables. The prior results suggest that, from an effective and efficient implementation of the model (González-Víllora et al., 2019; Hastie & Casey, 2014), they show positive effects: (a) at the physical-motor level (Araújo et al., 2019; Wahl-Alexander & Chomentowski, 2018); (b) at the affective level (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019); and (c) at the social level (Kao, 2019; Pan et al., 2019; Perlman, 2010). Likewise, the SEM has been revealed in the school context as a teaching model capable of causing positive effects on socio-personal indicators (cooperation, empathy, self-discipline) (Hastie et al., 2011) as well as on knowledge and physical (Farias et al., 2015; Ward et al., 2017) and sport performance indicators (Browne et al., 2004; Pereira et al., 2015). Likewise, various studies have shown that interventions based on the SEM show a positive impact on variables of psychosocial nature, such as motivational processes (Chu & Zhang, 2018; Cuevas et al., 2016; Gil-Arias et al., 2017); basic psychological needs (Cuevas et al., 2015; Knowles et al., 2018; Perlman, 2010); cohesion skills and social relationships (Kao, 2019; Pan et al., 2019; Perlman, 2010); trait emotional intelligence dimensions and motivational mediators (Luna et al., 2019; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2017); and a decrease in passive behaviors, aggressiveness, and violence, improving the relationship and social responsibility among the participants (Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016). However, regarding the statistical analysis of the data, in most of these previous

studies, the change/gain score through analysis of variance (ANOVA) (that is, posttest minus pretest) was used as a criterion group comparison. In this line, some authors such as Pérez-González & Qualter (2018) recommend using covariance (ANCOVA) where the covariate is the baseline or pretest score, controlling for the possible effect of the pretest score on the results of the posttest. Criteria followed in the present study are in the same line as other authors (e.g., Kao, 2019; Luna et al., 2019; Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016; Pan et al., 2019).

Taking into account the above, the objective of the current study was to evaluate the impact of a SEM-based educational intervention in children, compared to an educational intervention based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) on: (1) subjective well-being in its affective dimension; and (2) psychosocial adjustment with the indicators of depression, anxiety and social stress. The hypotheses focused on the fact that said educational intervention will improve in the participants' affective dimension of the experimental group's subjective well-being (Hypothesis 1) and psychosocial adjustment (depression, anxiety, and social stress) (Hypothesis 2).

9.2. Materials and Methods

9.2.1. Design

The study was carried out using a quasi-experimental design with repeated measurements (pretest and posttest) and a control group. Participants were randomly assigned to the experimental group (EG) and the control group (CG) through a cluster-randomized controlled trial.

9.2.2. Participants

The sample was obtained through a non-probabilistic incidental sampling method and was made up of 167 children, aged between 10 and 12 years (mean age (M) = 10.78; standard deviation (SD) = 1.07) (refer to **Table 11**).

Table 11. *Sample Description.*

		<i>n</i>	%
Age	10	79	54.11
	11	46	31.51
	12	21	14.38
Gender	Male	67	45.89
	Female	79	54.11

The inclusion criteria ($n = 146$) for the study were: (1) regular attendance at the school; (2) the written informed consent from the family (or legal guardian). The exclusion criteria ($n = 21$) were: (1) physical disability with official medical proof; (2) students with more than 30% truancy; (4) students sanctioned for disciplinary reasons by the educational center; (5) failure to obtain informed written consent from family (or legal guardian); (6) not completing the evaluation questionnaires adequately. The 146 participants who met and completed the study under research with the proposed criteria were randomly assigned to the EG through a cluster-randomized controlled trial ($n = 87$) or to the CG ($n = 59$). The differences in the two conditions (experimental group and control) were not significant by age ($\chi^2 = 1.17$; $p > 0.05$) nor by gender ($\chi^2 = 1.76$; $p > 0.05$). Participant flow is displayed below (refer to **Figure 16**).

Figure 16. Flow diagram: interventions based on the Sport Education model (SEM) (EG = experimental group) and traditional model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) (CG = control group).

9.2.3. Research Instruments

For this educational research, two measures have been used to evaluate the variables under study, with adequate psychometric parameters of reliability and validity.

Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) (Watson et al., 1988). The PANAS version validated in Spanish by Sandín (2003) for use with children and adolescents (PANASN) was used to evaluate subjective well-being in its affective dimension. It is made up of 20 items and presents a two-factor structure: positive affect (e.g., “*I am interested in people or things*”) and negative affect (e.g., “*I am afraid*”) with 10 items for each subscale. The measure consists of three response alternatives, described as «*Never*» (1), «*Sometimes*» (2), and «*Often*» (3). In the current study, the internal consistency calculated using Cronbach’s alpha was $\alpha = 0.81$ for positive affect and $\alpha = 0.78$ for negative affect.

Behavior Evaluation System for Children and Adolescents (BASC) (Reynolds & Kamphaus, 2004). The BASC-S2 questionnaire was used in its self-report version for children, made up of a total of 146 items, to evaluate the psychosocial adjustment variable. The BASC is a multidimensional instrument that measures numerous aspects of behavior and personality, including both positive (adaptive) and negative (clinical) dimensions. It consists of different adaptive subscales (which assess the positive fit) and clinical subscales (which assess mismatch), where participants rate statements that reflect their personal thoughts and feelings as true or false. In the current study, some clinical scales for evaluating negative or undesirable characteristics were used, such as: (a) depression: feelings of sadness, loneliness, and poor enjoyment of life, sometimes as a consequence of anxiety and stress processes (high scores indicate a problematic level of depression); (b) anxiety: presence of feelings of fear, obsessive thoughts, and generally irrational worries (high scores mean that the individual suffers emotionally and may experience stress reactions that make them explode due to some triviality); and (c) social stress: levels of stress (e.g., tension, anxiety, etc.) that children suffer in interpersonal relationships (high scores indicate problems related to shyness, introversion, social anxiety, and irritability). The current research used an instrument with adequate and satisfactory psychometric properties for the socio-emotional evaluation of Spanish children and

adolescents in the school and clinical context (González et al., 2004; Reynolds & Kamphaus, 2004).

9.2.4. Procedure

The study was carried out in four periods. In the first one, the educational intervention program was designed. Second, the pretest evaluation was carried out (the timing for the tests was between 50–55 min) both in the experimental and control groups, regulating students' fatigue with scheduled breaks. In the third period, the educational intervention based on the SEM was applied to the experimental group, and the intervention based on the traditional model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) to the control group. In the last period, at the end of the interventions, the posttest evaluation was performed (the time of the tests was between 50-55 min) in both groups, with scheduled breaks to avoid student fatigue.

The research was developed following the ethical code of the University of Castilla-La Mancha (Spain) following the international guidelines on experiments with human subjects described in the Nuremberg Code and the Declaration of Helsinki. As it was a study located within an educational context, it was authorized by the management team, the school council, and the participating school faculty. Also, constant telephone contact was maintained with the management team of the center for supervision and coordination of the project. As an essential requirement to participate in the research project, written informed consents were delivered to the center and requested to be signed by a parent or legal guardian. Likewise, the requirements of ethical confidentiality were respected and guaranteed by the participants' voluntary and anonymous nature (ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association [APA], 2019; Personal Data Protection Law of the Research Ethics Committee on Human Beings, CEISH).

9.2.5. Interventions

Intervention Based on the Sport Education Model (SEM)

This is the educational intervention designed and implemented in the experimental group, applying an adaptation of the intervention published by Luna et al. (2019). It was developed according to the structure and essential characteristics of the SEM (Siedentop et al., 2020): (1) season: a teaching unit of higher duration compared to the usual ones in physical education. A competitive plan is followed divided into

three phases (preseason, competition, and final); (2) affiliation: grouping into teams with cooperative and socializing work maintained throughout the season (feeling of belonging to the group); (3) formal competition: as a relevant feature for practical experience and technical-tactical knowledge of physical and sport activity; an authentic sport experience is developed where relevant and real aspects of a formal sport competition are introduced to students; (4) data recording: process of evaluation and recording of sport performance, knowledge, and behavior; (5) final event: practical demonstration of the evolution in the advances and results obtained; (6) festivity: a festive atmosphere through symbolism (songs, hymns, etc.), rituals (shaking hands, group photos, etc.) and sport celebration (awards ceremony, trophies, self-built certificates, etc.). This structure is seen in **Table 12**. In this sense, the intervention followed the recommendations proposed by Hastie & Casey (2014).

The intervention was developed with a sport education teaching unit (season) during school hours for two months (2–3 sessions per week for eight weeks) for a total of 18 sessions of 50 min of duration. The theoretical and practical sessions were applied with children for the subject of physical education, in an educational center within an urban environment and with a medium socio-cultural level. The teaching staff responsible for developing said intervention have nine years of teaching experience and four years of applying sport education. Similarly, the educational experience was controlled and examined by external researchers, in line with Sinelnikov's suggestions (2009): (1) personal and virtual contact regarding the problems that arose during the research; (2) regular inspections of the school center; (3) weekly analysis and verification of the investigation process.

The season was implemented through a divided court or net team sport, called Polskie ringo (García-López & Gutiérrez, 2016; Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019). This alternative sport was carried out with heterogeneous and permanent groups. Likewise, the game's distribution was developed in different sport spaces modified, reduced and adapted to the ages of the participating children, and divided into two equal parts by volleyball nets. It is a team game where players have to receive, grab, and throw a ring (that they have built by themselves) to the other field, and it must touch the ground to score. The use of an innovative sport, unknown to children, made it easier for all students alike to start with similar sport training and technical-tactical knowledge. Likewise, alternative and team sports such as Polskie ringo adapt effectively to the

educational environment, being collaborative, motivating, socializing and flexible with their different skills (García-López & Gutiérrez, 2016; A. Méndez-Giménez et al., 2011).

The participating students of each school year were randomly distributed in teams of five members, based on the principle of homogeneity in motor ability and gender (Burgueño et al., 2017). Throughout the season, general roles common to all participants were assigned on the one hand: (a) player role, active and participatory; and (b) referee role: responsible for the registration of time, the minutes and reports of the game, in addition to complying with the regulations governing the game (with an emphasis on a fair play). The referee role constituted a rotating team responsibility role, carried out at least once by each team during the formal competition phase. This role played was key for the students, improving their understanding of fair play and fostering their empathy with the referee team when they acted as players. On the other hand, other specific roles of responsibility within the team were also assigned to the participants: (a) captain: team captain, whose functions are coordination and mediation; (b) audiovisual reporter: official journalist of the season, responsible for all the information and the management of a didactic blog, previously created by the faculty for the sport event; (c) coach: physical trainer whose function is to design, direct and control the previous and final physical sport warm-ups in the practical sessions, in addition to being responsible for the sport equipment used; and (d) celebration committee: organization event management involving all participants (e.g., organization of the final event).

In short, the application of active and cooperative methodologies, promoting the feeling of belonging to a team, together with positive reinforcements such as the final festival, are crucial to explaining the motivation experienced by the students (Chu & Zhang, 2018). Likewise, it is essential to highlight, on the one hand, the guiding role of the teacher, and on the other hand, the active and autonomous role of the students, who act as the main protagonist of the teaching-learning process through their active participation and with the attribution of responsibility roles (Siedentop et al., 2020).

Intervention Based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI)

This is the educational intervention designed and implemented in the control group, developed using a traditional teaching-learning methodology (Metzler, 2017;

Pan et al., 2019) following a Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (Gil-Arias et al., 2017; González-Víllora et al., 2018; Kirk, 2013).

The intervention (TM-DI) was carried out through a teaching unit, following the usual curricular programming of the physical education department of the participating school. Likewise, it was applied during school hours, with a duration similar to the previous intervention (refer to **Table 12**). The theoretical and practical sessions were developed for children in the class of physical education, in the same educational center. The teachers responsible for carrying out this intervention had 12 years of teaching experience and had no previous SEM experience.

The teaching unit was also implemented with the Polskie ringo, with no working groups or permanent teams or responsibility roles being developed. In the same way, more active and total control was generated by the teachers regarding: (1) presentation, introduction and explanation of the tasks; (2) educational management; (3) methodological organization; (4) structure of activities; and (5) evaluation. Regarding the traditional model of Direct Instruction, the main characteristics were: (a) teaching-learning processes based, on the one hand, on a directive and instructive teaching function; and on the other hand, a passive function of students, determined by follow-up and search for these towards the teacher's instructions; (b) communicative processes characterized by a unidirectional and expository role of the teacher towards the students; (c) theoretical and practical sessions directed and structured solely by teachers, with rote and repetitive learning; (d) teaching style of homework assignment with the objective of learning specifically technical foundations of the sport chosen by the faculty (e.g., pass, throw, catch, etc.); (e) rhythm imposed by teachers, with an external, unidirectional, and outstanding teaching position regarding the group of students; (f) generalized teaching that did not individualize, using the sport equipment provided by the educational center (non-use of self-built materials by the students); (g) prescriptive feedback; and (h) situations of decontextualized activities and play, without experiencing authenticity, practiced individually or in pairs.

These traditional and control pedagogical approaches (TM-DI) are usually characterized by not focusing their intervention on children's autonomy and their intergroup interaction (Gil-Arias et al., 2017), reporting low levels of motivation (Pan

et al., 2019), and a decrease in satisfaction and significant learning in physical education (Metzler, 2017).

Table 12. *Sequencing of session content in the educational interventions.*

SESSION	Intervention with Sport Education model (SEM) (experimental group)	Intervention with traditional model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) (control group)
1-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of the SEM, the sport developed by teams (Polskie ringo), and the roles of responsibility, with digital and audiovisual support (ICT). • Explanation and delivery to the students of the teaching material that will be used (e.g., personalized folders with educational themes, party minutes, contingency contracts, party reports, etc.). • Organization and division of teams in a random way. The working groups were permanent with the assignment of team names following a didactic and transversal theme (e.g., characters from the Quixotic literature). • Designation and random distribution of responsibility roles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation and explanation by the teachers of the teaching unit implemented with the Polisk ringo. • General explanation of the educational intervention to students: objectives, content, and evaluation of the teaching unit. • Distribution of students individually, in pairs, and in small groups (no permanent working groups are established).
3-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theoretical explanation with a digital whiteboard (audiovisual) of how the students will carry out the self-construction of the materials applied in the intervention (e.g., Polskie ringo rings, trophies, medals, etc.). • Practical explanation from the faculty on how to make such materials (e.g., Polskie ringo rings, certificates, etc.). • Construction by the students (self-construction) of the materials in a cooperative way (permanent groups/work teams). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instructional and direct introduction and explanation by teachers of: (a) the general and specific characteristics of the operation of the game (Polskie ringo); (b) the regulations of the Polskie ringo; and (c) sport equipment used and provided by the school. • Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and rote): displacement I-II.
5-8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial warm-up and final stretching in each session (directed by the students with the coach role). These tasks should be applied through reduced and modified physical activity and sport games. • Practical team sessions to learn essential technical-tactical skills in the game of the Polskie ringo (displacement, coordination, pass, reception, serve, etc.). • Functional application of roles in the different active, participative, and cooperative tasks carried out by the teams (e.g., captain: in the game of attack and defense; referee: in the rules of the game). • Sessions ended with interactive assemblies for reflection and understanding (teacher-students) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher-directed technical warm-up and stretching. • Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and memoiristic): coordination I-II. • Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and memoiristic): pass and reception I and II. • Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and memoiristic): catch, serve, and throw. • The teachers, during the development of the practical activities, gave instructions to the

	and vice versa), to work, for example, positive feedback, active listening and error-learning.	participants on how to correct and improve motor behavior.
9-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training team sessions with friendly Polskie ringo games through educational competition (emphasis on fair play and respect for the opponent). • Responsibility role training (e.g., referee). Development of authentic sport elements (e.g., match minutes; interviews; etc.). • Formal competition: 5 vs. 5 league formats (Round Robin). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warm-ups and stretches directed by the teachers. • Tactical skill practice session 1 vs. 1. • Tactical skill practice session 2 vs. 2. • Throw and reception activities between rotating pairs. • Simultaneous Polskie ringo games by rotating pairs.
16-17	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal competition (semifinal and final): 5 vs. 5 league formats (Round Robin). • Continuous and formative evaluation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual practical evaluation (technical-tactical learning acquired).
18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Celebration of the final event (organized by the role of celebration committee). Educational prizes, trophies, certificates, and medals were presented, made by the students themselves. • Educational prizes, trophies, certificates, and medals were presented, made by the students themselves. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theoretical individual evaluation.

9.2.6. Data Analysis

First, the normality of the variables under study was calculated with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, all adjusting to the assumption of normality (analyses performed with a 95% confidence interval). Second, the reliability evidence was calculated with the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient (α). Third, to determine the impact of the pilot program, the following statistical analyses were carried out: (1) multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) with the total pretest scores of the variables under study, to confirm possible starting (initial) differences between the participants of the experimental group (EG) and control group (CG); (2) descriptive (M = mean; SD = standard deviation) and variance (ANOVA) analyses with each of the scores obtained for the instruments used during the pretest phase; (3) in order to show significant improvements between the experimental and control groups, a multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA) was calculated on the set of variables investigated; (4) descriptive analysis and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA: covarying the pretest scores) with the posttest scores; (5) finally, the effect size of the differences

was analyzed according to the criteria set forth by Cohen (1988) (*low* < 0.50; *medium* 0.50–0.79; *big* ≥ 0.80).

9.3. Results

The multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) results did not reveal statistically significant differences between the groups (EG and CG) before the intervention, Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.337$; $F_{(7,139)} = 0.419$; $p = 0.497$, with a low effect size ($d = 0.018$; $r = 0.03$).

9.3.1. Pretest Analysis

The pretest phase results (ANOVA) confirmed that before starting the educational intervention, there were no statistically significant differences in any of the variables under study (refer to **Table 13**).

9.3.2. Posttest Analysis

The multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA) results in the pretest and posttest phases did not reveal statistically significant differences between the two groups (EG and CG), Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.993$; $F_{(7,135)} = 1.528$; $p = 0.206$, with a low effect size ($d = 0.054$; $r = 0.06$).

▪ *Effects on Subjective Well-Being*

The posttest phase results (ANCOVA) (refer to **Table 13**) showed a significant increase in positive affect with a medium effect size ($d = 0.61$) and a significant decrease in negative affect with a low effect size ($d = 0.39$) in favor of the EG (refer to **Figure 17**).

▪ *Effects on Psychosocial Adjustment*

After performing ANCOVA in the posttest phase, the results confirmed a significant decrease in anxiety, in favor of the experimental group, with a low effect size ($d = 0.28$) (refer to **Figure 17**). However, no significant differences were confirmed in the other variables analyzed, depression, and social stress (refer to **Table 13**).

9.4. Discussion

In recent years, different authors (Bessa et al., 2019; Evangelio et al., 2018; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019) present the interest of research to continue examining the

Table 13. Mean, standard deviation, analysis of variance (ANOVA), analysis of covariance (ANCOVA), and effect size for the differences in the means (Cohen's d) in the variables under study (i.e., subjective well-being and psychosocial adjustment) in the experimental and control groups.

	PRETEST						POSTTEST							
	Experimental	Control	ANOVA	Experimental	Control	ANCOVA	Experimental	Control	ANOVA	Experimental	Control	ANCOVA		
	M	SD	F	M	SD	F	M	SD	F	M	SD	F		
	d		p	d		p	d		p	d		p		
Positive affect	22.26	5.00	22.71	4.15	6.811	0.146	0.10	26.48	2.93	24.61	3.23	5.088	0.018	0.61
Negative affect	18.92	3.72	18.54	3.76	0.853	0.271	0.10	16.81	3.92	18.38	4.06	1.442	0.040	0.39
PA (n = 135)														
Depression	47.57	10.41	47.40	10.51	1.045	0.445	0.02	47.02	11.57	47.46	11.35	0.573	0.258	0.04
Anxiety	40.68	10.74	40.36	10.77	0.638	0.547	0.03	38.21	10.91	41.27	10.85	1.385	0.027	0.28
Social Stress	47.75	10.75	47.83	10.59	1.127	0.489	0.01	47.10	10.46	48.36	10.57	0.982	0.875	0.12

Note. SWB = Subjective Well-Being; PA = Psychological Adjustment; M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation.

Figure 17. Significant effects of the intervention in the experimental group on the variables studied.

impact of healthy and active practices in the school context. In this sense, the present study evaluated the impact in children of an educational intervention based on the Sport Education model (SEM), compared to an educational intervention based on the traditional model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) on: (1) subjective well-being in its affective dimension; and (2) psychosocial adjustment in its clinical indicators: depression, anxiety, and social stress.

The findings of this investigation confirmed statistically significant improvements in the variables under study, in favor of the experimental group (SEM) compared to the control group (TM-DI) in: (a) positive and negative affect; and (b) anxiety. However, no significant improvements were shown in the psychosocial adjustment indicators of depression and social stress.

First, the previous results confirmed that the intervention (SEM) stimulated in the experimental group a significant increase in positive affect and a significant decrease in negative affect. Therefore, Hypothesis 1 is confirmed. These results converge with other previous studies, which analyze the efficacy of SEM-based interventions on emotional or affective variables (Bessa et al., 2019; Evangelio et al., 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2018; Luna et al., 2019; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2017). Likewise, the effect sizes, in positive affect and negative affect, are similar to those obtained in other previous investigations (e.g., Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019). A possible explanation for these results could be due to the synergy between subjective well-being with the development of physical, active, and healthy habits (Bailey, 2006; Biddle et al., 2000; Sánchez-López et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2015). Similarly, the increase in physical inactivity in the school environment (UNESCO, 2015) makes beneficial the implementation of healthy and active interventions or programs (Pate & Dowda, 2019; Shields et al., 2018) through cooperative and participatory methodologies focused on the student (active subject) (Kirk, 2013) for the well-being of the student (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019; Whitehead, 2010). Standage & Gillison (2007) establish that proactive teaching processes, applied correctly in physical education, can improve motivation and favor positive affectivity, and therefore, the quality of life in childhood. Essential elements of the SEM, such as a real and pedagogical vision of the structure and sport organization (Siedentop et al., 2020), competition, enthusiasm and physical sport culture (Hastie et al., 2011; Kolovelonis & Goudas, 2018), the positive interdependence that arises with cooperative learning (Menéndez-Santurio &

Fernández-Río, 2016), the affiliation or feeling of belonging (Browne et al., 2004), the choice and assignment of responsibility roles (Siedentop et al., 2020), and motivational indicators (Chu & Zhang, 2018; Cuevas et al., 2016; Gil-Arias et al., 2017; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019) could significantly reinforce the affective sphere in children (Sandford et al., 2008).

Second, the results showed some improvements in psychosocial adjustment, specifically a significant decrease in anxiety, although with a low effect size. In this way, Hypothesis 2 was partially confirmed, since no significant decreases in depression and social anxiety were found. Active participation in educational intervention is likely to be positively related to well-being and negatively related to anxiety. In line with the results of some authors (McMahon et al., 2017), it is concluded that participation in sport activities independently contributed to improving subjective well-being and reducing anxiety levels.

A proper analysis of psychosocial adjustment implies being able to associate this construct with other psychological variables (De la Torre-Cruz et al., 2013) such as subjective well-being (Huebner et al., 2000; Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2016), and being able to evaluate it effectively (Fernández-Berrocal et al., 2018; Reynolds & Kamphaus, 2004). The influence of psychosocial adjustment in the educational environment is relevant, particularly concerning the development of adaptive behaviors (positive adjustment) and maladjustment (mismatch) (Reynolds & Kamphaus, 2004; Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2016). A positive adjustment in the students' behavior or personality would imply an optimal school climate in its different physical, psychological, social, and affective dimensions (Baker et al., 2003; Bisquerra et al., 2015). In this sense, it would be positive to promote competent pedagogical models (Iserbyt et al., 2016) or adequate educational interventions (Shields et al., 2018), such as the SEM (González-Víllora et al., 2019; Metzler, 2017). Similarly, the positive impact of the SEM at the social (e.g., Kao, 2019; Pan et al., 2019) and emotional (e.g., Luna et al., 2019; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2017) levels, as well as its beneficial and significant effects on social relationships and against attitudes of violence and aggressiveness (Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016) could lead to reinforcement in the educational field, for the development of adaptive strategies or resources, being able to effectively face the mismatch or negative psychosocial characteristics (Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2016).

Therefore, it would be reasonable to think that essential elements of the model such as the roles of responsibilities, cooperative learning, the formal competition, and the final event, where the students were able to self-manage their learning, together with the creative, motivating, cooperative, and celebratory nature of the SEM could have influenced the participating children to improve their academic achievement in physical education. The enriching elements of the SEM included in the intervention program may also have contributed to these results, such as the self-construction of didactic materials, the interdisciplinarity of the program, and teaching with projects, since their pedagogical effectiveness has been previously verified in other studies (Knowles et al., 2018; Lleixà et al., 2016; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2016).

Despite these results, we must point out that the present research shows the following limitations: (1) the number of participants was limited and a convenience sampling was used, which may limit the generalization of the results to other populations; (2) the variables under study were evaluated with self-reports. It would be advisable to support these results with other hetero-informed instruments; (3) it would be advisable to carry out a follow-up evaluation; (4) it would be necessary to evaluate the dynamics generated in the development of the sessions (formative evaluation) (Práxedes et al., 2019); (5) difficulties in following some recommendations to start the SEM during the teaching sessions. The organization and initial grouping of the teams, follow-up of the participating students due to illness or injury, weather, facilities, equipment, and/or teacher availability are some of the aspects that could hinder the follow-up and development of the sessions (Hastie & Casey, 2014).

On the other hand, future lines of research could be directed towards: (1) expanding the sample and diversifying educational contexts, in addition to the socio-cultural environment of the participants; (2) evaluation of the effects of educational intervention on other psychological (e.g., interpersonal relationships, self-esteem, or self-concept) or clinical (e.g., cortisol) variables.

9.5. Conclusions

Sierra-Díaz et al. (2019) establish that physical education could be considered a relevant subject to promote wellness habits associated with a healthy lifestyle during sport and other types of active activities. Likewise, regarding the educational context, physical education effectively promotes the holistic development of students

(Evangelio et al., 2018) due to its active, practical, transversal, and motivating frameworks that make it unique compared to other classes.

Current educational demands emphasize the need for a methodological renewal in the evolution of traditional physical education toward a more current and motivating methodological framework driven by quality physical education (UNESCO, 2015). The current results show the benefits and efficacy in children of an intervention in physical education to improve subjective well-being, psychosocial adjustment, and school results in this subject. These findings have interesting pedagogical and empirical implications for both teachers and students. For teachers, the SEM-based intervention constitutes an effective, efficient, and motivating tool with proven positive results in physical education classes. For students, the intervention could promote well-being or quality of life, improve their socio-scholastic adaptation, and increase their autonomy, promoting positive and comprehensive development of their personalities.

In conclusion, the application of this type of intervention in the school environment is recommended for children due to the evident physical, affective, psychosocial, and academic benefits, in line with other investigations (Bessa et al., 2019; Evangelio et al., 2018). Furthermore, these conclusions offer empirical support for the pedagogical model of SEM and have interesting educational implications that promote the effectiveness of innovative and motivating teaching approaches.

10. CONCLUSIONES

*“Confía en el tiempo, que suele dar dulces salidas a muchas
amargas dificultades”
(Don Quijote de la Mancha)*

Las principales conclusiones relacionadas con los objetivos de los artículos publicados en la presente tesis doctoral se muestran a continuación (**Tabla 14**):

10.1. Conclusiones del Objetivo 1

Manuscrito 1. *Evaluar el impacto de un programa piloto de Educación Física, basado en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, sobre las variables: bienestar subjetivo, inteligencia emocional rasgo y ansiedad social, en alumnado de Educación Secundarias Obligatoria (adolescentes de 12 a 15 años) en un centro educativo de la provincia de Toledo (Castilla-La Mancha; España).*

La aplicación del programa en el centro escolar estimuló el desarrollo de las dimensiones socioemocionales del alumnado adolescente participante (grupo experimental). En este sentido, los resultados mostraron el éxito y eficacia del programa con las mejoras significativas en bienestar subjetivo y en inteligencia emocional rasgo, aunque no se pudo mostrar el impacto en la variable ansiedad social.

Por lo tanto, sobre el marco de la EFC (Le Masurier & Corbin, 2006; UNESCO, 2015) y el enfoque de ASE (CASEL, 2021; Domitrovich et al., 2017; Taylor et al., 2017), se recomienda la aplicación de este tipo de intervenciones educativas eficaces (Bessa et al., 2019, 2021; Chu & Zhang, 2018; Evangelio et al., 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2018; Hastie et al., 2011; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019), debido a los beneficios psicosociales evidenciados sobre el alumnado adolescente. Una apuesta por el deporte y otras opciones de actividad físico-deportiva, en el marco de la EFC, aplicada de forma eficiente, mediante modelos pedagógicos adecuados (e.g., MED), podría desempeñar un papel clave en el contexto educativo y en el desarrollo personal y social de los estudiantes (Eime et al., 2013; Eley & Kirk, 2002; Russell, 2005).

Este estudio presenta contribuciones novedosas a nivel teórico y práctico. A nivel teórico, la falta de actividad física puede tener un efecto perjudicial en la salud del individuo y es actualmente una relevante preocupación de salud pública (Guthold et al., 2020; Haskell et al., 2009). A este respecto, UNESCO (2015) enfatiza la importancia de fomentar y promover comportamientos activos (Whitehead, 2010) en todos los contextos, especialmente en las escuelas. En consecuencia, cabe señalar

la sinergia positiva entre salud y actividad física, donde el sedentarismo es un factor de riesgo primordial de mortalidad, lo que genera preocupación por la prevalencia del sedentarismo o patrones socioeducativos de inactividad, especialmente en contextos escolares (Guthold et al., 2020; McMahon et al., 2017; WHO, 2010). Por otro lado, a nivel práctico, los hallazgos encontrados podrían ayudar al profesorado en sus tareas docentes, dotándoles de estrategias, herramientas o recursos para utilizarlos funcionalmente en la práctica educativa habitual. Del mismo modo, los hallazgos del vigente trabajo impulsan significativos enfoques o líneas de investigación en cuanto a la aplicación en el alumnado de la Educación Deportiva, especialmente en términos del impacto sobre variables socioemocionales.

10.2. Conclusiones del Objetivo 2

Manuscrito 2. *Evaluar los efectos de una intervención físico-deportiva basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, en comparación con una intervención basada en el modelo Tradicional de Instrucción Directa, en alumnado de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria (adolescentes de 12 a 15 años) sobre las variables: competencia social y aceptación social entre iguales, en un centro educativo de la provincia de Toledo (Castilla-La Mancha; España).*

Los resultados significativos evidenciados en este artículo podrían deberse, como plantean algunas investigaciones, a la valiosa sinergia entre la actividad físico-deportiva, desarrolladas en entornos educativos positivos y motivantes (Escalié et al., 2017; Gil-Madrona et al., 2019; Mayfield et al., 2017; Shields et al., 2018; UNESCO, 2015) con los factores afectivos y/o psicosociales (Bessa et al., 2021; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). En estos eficaces contextos escolares, se favorecerá en los estudiantes mejoras en sus estrategias pedagógicas (Girard et al., 2019), haciendo más positivo el aprendizaje socioemocional (Brinkley et al., 2017; Cronin et al., 2018; Mayfield et al., 2017) y, por ende, fomentando significativas experiencias educativas en todas sus dimensiones (cognitivas, físicas, afectivas y sociales) (Bessa et al., 2021; Evangelio et al., 2018; Kohl & Cook, 2013; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019).

Es relevante señalar que estos hallazgos sugieren que los procesos de enseñanza-aprendizaje, utilizando modelos pedagógicos eficaces y activos como el MED (Siedentop et al., 2020) y desarrollados dentro de un clima de aula óptimo, como los planteados en la EFC y el ASE, promueven en el alumnado altos niveles de emociones positivas y habilidades sociales. Del mismo modo, se favorece las interacciones interpersonales, evidencias claras de cooperación y las relaciones humanas que impulsan la convivencia prosocial (Cañabate et al., 2018).

En cuanto al alumnado participante, es importante resaltar que la adolescencia es una etapa de vida crucial para el desarrollo de las competencias socioemocionales, ya que los adolescentes vivencia dicho período, con constantes y típicas transiciones madurativas y emocionales de mayor dificultad social (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017, 2019). En este sentido, identificar, controlar y gestionar las competencias socioemocionales contribuyen a optimizar los procesos de enseñanza y aprendizaje, fortaleciendo las relaciones sociales entre los adolescentes (Ang & Penney, 2013; Bessa et al., 2021; Cañabate et al., 2018; Del Prette & Del Prette, 2005; Evangelio et al., 2018; Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017; Losada et al., 2017) y pueden favorecer una evaluación eficiente de la práctica educativa, por parte del profesorado (Lee et al., 2019).

10.3. Conclusiones del Objetivo 3

Manuscrito 3. *Evaluar en alumnado de Educación Primaria (niños/as de 10 a 12 años) la eficacia de un programa basado en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, en comparación con una intervención educativa basada en el modelo Tradicional de Instrucción Directa, sobre las variables: bienestar subjetivo y ajuste psicosocial, en un centro educativo de Ciudad Real (Castilla-La Mancha; España).*

Sería razonable pensar que elementos esenciales del MED tales como la utilización de roles de responsabilidades, el aprendizaje cooperativo, la afiliación, la competición formal, el evento final, la autoconstrucción de sus recursos didácticos, donde los estudiantes pudieron autogestionar sus aprendizajes, junto a un entorno escolar creativo, motivante, cooperativo y festivo, podría haber influido para que el

alumnado participante mejorara su logro y/o éxito académico en Educación Física. A estos resultados significativos podría haber contribuido también, aspectos enriquecedores del MED incluidos en el programa de intervención, como la interdisciplinariedad del programa y la enseñanza por proyectos, ya que previamente se ha comprobado su efectividad pedagógica en estudios previos (Knowles et al., 2018; Lleixà et al., 2016; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2016).

Diferentes autores (Bessa et al., 2021; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019) señalan que la Educación Física podría considerarse como una disciplina clave para fomentar hábitos de bienestar asociados a un estilo de vida saludable durante la práctica deportiva y otros tipos de tareas activas. Asimismo, en cuanto al contexto educativo, la Educación Física impulsa de forma eficaz el desarrollo integral del alumnado (Bessa et al., 2019; Evangelio et al., 2018) debido a sus marcos activos, prácticos, transversales y motivantes que la hacen única frente a otras asignaturas (Kohl & Cook, 2013).

Las demandas educativas actuales enfatizan la necesidad de una renovación metodológica en la evolución de la tradicional Educación Física (e.g., MT-ID) hacia un marco metodológico más actual y motivador impulsado por la EFC (Decorby et al., 2005; Le Masurier & Corbin, 2006; UNESCO, 2015). Los vigentes resultados obtenidos, muestran en la niñez los beneficios, bondades y eficacia de una intervención en Educación Física para mejorar el bienestar subjetivo y el ajuste psicosocial. Estos hallazgos tienen interesantes implicaciones pedagógicas y empíricas tanto para el profesorado como para el alumnado. Para el profesorado, la intervención basada en el MED constituye una herramienta eficaz, eficiente y motivadora con efectos positivos constatados en las clases de Educación Física. Para los estudiantes, la intervención promueve el bienestar o calidad de vida, mejora su adaptación socioescolar y aumentar su autonomía, fomentando un desarrollo positivo e integral de sus personalidades.

En conclusión, se recomienda la aplicación de este tipo de intervención en el ámbito escolar en los niños y niñas por los evidentes beneficios físicos, afectivos, psicosociales y académicos, en consonancia con otras investigaciones (Bessa et al., 2019, 2021; Chu & Zhang, 2018; Evangelio et al., 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2018; Hastie et al., 2011). Del mismo modo, estas conclusiones ofrecen un soporte empírico al modelo pedagógico (MED) y tienen interesantes implicaciones educativas que promueven la eficacia de innovadores y motivantes enfoques didácticos.

Tabla 14. Relación de las conclusiones y objetivos en los artículos publicados en la tesis doctoral.

	Manuscrito I	Manuscrito II	Manuscrito III
Objetivos	<p>Evaluar el impacto de un programa piloto de Educación Física y Deportiva en adolescentes, sobre el bienestar subjetivo (calidad de vida relacionada con la salud, afecto positivo y afecto negativo), la inteligencia emocional rasgo y la ansiedad social.</p>	<p>Evaluar el impacto de una intervención educativa sobre la competencia social y la aceptación social entre iguales en alumnado adolescente (Educación Secundaria Obligatoria).</p>	<p>Evaluar la eficacia de una intervención basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva, en comparación con una intervención basada en el modelo Tradicional de Instrucción Directa en niñas y niños.</p>
Conclusiones	<p>Los resultados sugieren que el programa piloto estimuló en el alumnado adolescente, cierta mejora en el bienestar subjetivo y en inteligencia emocional rasgo, pero no tuvo impacto en la ansiedad social. Por lo tanto, sobre la base de la Educación Física de Calidad y el enfoque del Aprendizaje Social y Emocional, se recomienda la aplicación de este tipo de programas mostrados los posibles beneficios psicosociales para los adolescentes en el contexto educativo. La apuesta por el deporte y otras opciones de actividad físico-deportiva en el marco de la EFC, aplicadas eficazmente mediante modelos pedagógicos pertinentes (como la Educación Deportiva), puede desempeñar un papel clave en el desarrollo integral de los estudiantes.</p>	<p>Los hallazgos significativos probablemente se deban a la sinergia positiva entre la actividad física desarrollada en entornos positivos (EFC) con los factores afectivos y/o psicosociales. Dicho contexto facilitará en el alumnado mejores estrategias pedagógicas que hacen más positivo el aprendizaje socioemocional y, por tanto, mejoran su experiencia educativa. Es relevante señalar que cuando las clases de EF se desarrollan utilizando efectivos modelos pedagógicos, como el MED, los escolares muestran: (a) altos niveles de emociones positivas; (b) beneficiosas habilidades sociales, que favorecen las interacciones entre iguales; (c) significativas evidencias de cooperación; y (d) efectivas relaciones humanas que promueven la convivencia prosocial.</p>	<p>Las demandas educativas actuales enfatizan la necesidad de una renovación metodológica en la evolución de la Educación Física tradicional hacia un marco metodológico más actual y motivador impulsado por la Educación Física de Calidad (EFC). Los presentes resultados muestran, en alumnado de Educación Primaria, los beneficios y la eficacia de una intervención basada en el MED en Educación Física, para mejorar el bienestar subjetivo y el ajuste psicosocial. En este sentido, se recomienda la aplicación de este tipo de intervenciones en el ámbito escolar para los niños y niñas, debido a los evidentes beneficios físicos, afectivos y psicosociales. Del mismo modo, estas conclusiones ofrecen un apoyo y soporte empírico al modelo pedagógico del MED, teniendo interesantes implicaciones pedagógicas que promueven la eficacia de enfoques metodológicos educativos innovadores y motivantes.</p>

10.4. Limitaciones y líneas futuras

En la **Tabla 15**, se recogen las principales limitaciones y líneas futuras de los artículos científicos incluidos en la presente tesis doctoral.

Tabla 15. Principales limitaciones y líneas futuras de los artículos científicos publicados en la tesis doctoral.

	Manuscrito I	Manuscrito II	Manuscrito III
Limitaciones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - El procedimiento de muestreo fue por conveniencia y no por procedimientos aleatorios. - Aumentar la muestra para minimizar los sesgos en los resultados y favorecer los procesos de generalización a otros contextos socioculturales. - Los instrumentos utilizados eran auto-informes, por lo que los resultados podrían estar influidos por el sesgo de deseabilidad social. Se sugiere utilizar pruebas de alto rendimiento o hetero-informes para minimizar dicho sesgo. - Diferencias en las puntuaciones en la fase pretest en inteligencia emocional rasgo, entre los grupos experimental y control. - Dificultades para seguir todas las recomendaciones en la implementación del MED. - Incluir un procedimiento de análisis de las sesiones para evaluar si los docentes siguieron los principios fundamentales del MED. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluación de seguimiento de la intervención para analizar el efecto a largo plazo. - Utilizar instrumentos o medidas de evaluación cumplimentadas por el profesorado o las familias. - Incluir un procedimiento de análisis de las sesiones con el fin de evaluar si los profesores siguieron los principios esenciales del MED (evaluación formativa). - Los resultados obtenidos en la Hipótesis 3 deben ser interpretados con cautela debido al tamaño muestral. - Para minimizar los efectos del experimentador, sería necesario en la fase posttest usar un procedimiento de balanceo en cada una de las condiciones experimentales. - Dificultades para seguir las recomendaciones del MED. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Número de participantes limitado y el muestreo es por conveniencia, lo que pudo limitar la generalización de los resultados a otras poblaciones. - Las variables objeto de estudio son evaluadas con autoinformes, sería recomendable apoyar estos resultados con otras medidas heteroinformadas. - No se realizó una evaluación de seguimiento. - Evaluar las dinámicas generadas en el desarrollo de las sesiones. - Dificultades en seguir algunas recomendaciones del MED (e.g., organización y agrupación inicial de los equipos, seguimiento del alumnado por enfermedad o lesión, la climatología, las instalaciones, etc.).

Líneas futuras

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Ampliar el número de participantes, así como, diversificar su origen sociocultural.- Analizar el impacto del programa con otras variables dependientes: (a) rendimiento escolar y (b) la adaptación socioescolar.- Examinar los efectos sobre variables clínicas como la depresión, utilizando medidas como el uso de correlatos biológicos (marcadores hipotalámico-pituitario-adrenal (HPA), parámetros de cortisol, etc.).- Realizar una evaluación de seguimiento para valorar la sostenibilidad de los efectos del programa educativo. | <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Incrementar el tamaño muestral.- Diversificar el contexto sociocultural de los participantes.- Evaluar otras variables involucradas en las mejoras obtenidas mediante estas intervenciones, tales como, estrategias de regulación o gestión emocional (e.g., intrapersonales e interpersonales). | <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Ampliar la muestra y diversificar los contextos educativos, además del ambiente sociocultural de los participantes.- Evaluar los efectos de la intervención educativa sobre otras variables psicológicas (e.g., relaciones interpersonales, autoestima o autoconcepto) y/o clínicas (e.g. cortisol). |
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Por otro lado, es relevante resaltar en relación a los análisis estadísticos desarrollados en las publicaciones de esta tesis doctoral, que algunos autores como Pérez-González & Qualter, (2018), recomiendan que para evaluar la eficacia de intervenciones o programas educativos es clave el uso de análisis de covarianza (ANCOVA), donde la covariable es la puntuación pretest o inicial, controlando el posible efecto de las puntuaciones pretest sobre los resultados de las puntuaciones posttest o finales. Los criterios estadísticos seguidos en todos los estudios presentados, convergen con otros estudios previos (e.g., Kao, 2019; Menéndez-Santurio & Fernández-Río, 2016; Pan et al., 2019). Además, también es importante apuntar que en una reciente revisión sistemática publicada por Bessa et al. (2021) consideraron los manuscritos I (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2019) y III (Luna, Rodríguez-Donaire, et al., 2020) con una significativa calidad metodológica (moderada), así como el manuscrito II (Luna, Guerrero, et al., 2020) como el artículo mejor valorado de todos los evaluados y analizados en dicha revisión crítica sobre el impacto del MED.

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(Montalbán)

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12. CONTRIBUCIONES CIENTÍFICAS DE LA TESIS

*“Dad crédito a las obras y no a las palabras”
(Don Quijote de la Mancha)*

12.1. Improving adolescents' subjective well-being, trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety through a programme based on the Sport Education model

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Article

Improving Adolescents' Subjective Well-Being, Trait Emotional Intelligence and Social Anxiety through a Programme Based on the Sport Education Model

Pablo Luna , Jerónimo Guerrero and Javier Cejudo *

Department of Psychology, Faculty of Education of Ciudad Real, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Ronda de Calatrava 3, 13071 Ciudad Real, Spain; pablo.luna@uclm.es (P.L.); jeronimo.guerrero@alu.uclm.es (J.G.)

* Correspondence: manueljaviercejudo@uclm.es; Tel.: +34-926295300 (ext. 3215)

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Abstract: This study aimed to evaluate the impact of a physical-sport education pilot programme on adolescents' subjective well-being (health-related quality of life, positive affect and negative affect), trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety. The programme was based on the pedagogical sport education model within a quality physical education framework, and approached from the perspective of social and emotional learning. Participants were 113 compulsory secondary education students aged 12–15 years that were assigned to a control group ($n = 44$) and an experimental group ($n = 69$). A quasi-experimental design with repeated pre-test and post-test measures was used. Bonferroni correction was applied for multiple comparisons. The preliminary results obtained in this investigation revealed that the physical-sport education pilot programme promoted significant improvements in a specific indicator of subjective well-being and trait emotional intelligence in the experimental group. These encouraging findings support the pedagogical efficiency of the programme with regard to the programme aim. The findings also highlight the feasibility and appropriateness of the programme in terms of an innovative teaching proposal.

Keywords: physical education; social and emotional learning; sport education model; subjective well-being; trait emotional intelligence; social anxiety

1. Introduction

In the education field, physical education is a subject that can contribute to improving the well-being and health of children and adolescents. The concept of quality physical education, which is understood as an interrelated system of inclusive and active teaching and learning, must be considered a key framework for integral approaches (i.e., education and health) [1]. It can also be seen as a physically active teaching and learning experience that can positively impact students' psychomotor abilities, cognitive comprehension and social and affective aptitudes [2]. Moreover, in our view, quality physical education could be grouped in the social and emotional learning category.

Quality physical education aims to achieve an integral education commitment [3,4] that allows students to be physically literate [5,6]. Physical literacy is the pillar of quality physical education, and can be defined as the motivation and cognitive, physical and affective competence necessary to encourage and preserve an active attitude in life, enabling a positive development of the aptitude to achieve, understand and use decisions about one's health efficiently [7]. Students who are physically literate intrinsically value their own psychomotor capabilities, as well as the contribution of these abilities to well-being and health [6].

The connection between health and physical activity is widely accepted [8,9]. However, the effects of physical activity on health in the educational context should be deepened through experimental

studies. Designing teaching and learning processes in this area will support physical, psychological, emotional and social development [10].

The synergy between the practice of physical-sport activity together with physical and psychological health is a gradually growing interest area for education researchers [11–14]. Moreover, different investigations in the education framework of the evolution of quality physical education have emphasised the need for methodological change [4,15]. Several pedagogical models share the same features [16].

This study is based on quality physical education, manifested through a specific sport education model [17]. Sport education is a pedagogical model that uses essential features of sports (seasons, competitions, membership, data register, culminating event and festivity), and aims to achieve the inclusive goal of all students living real and meaningful sport experiences in physical education. In addition, this model aspires to develop competence, enthusiasm and a physical-sport culture in students [18].

The pedagogical potential of the sport education model, if correctly implemented [19], results in benefits at a physical level [20–22]. Similarly, it has been shown to have a positive impact on psychological variables in adolescents. These positive benefits include: basic psychological needs [23]; improvement in competence [24] and the feeling of belonging to a group [25]; decrease in attitudes towards violence and improvements in social responsibility and participants' relationships [25,26]; more self-determined behaviour [27]; improvements in friendship and sport goals [24]; decrease in aggressive behaviour and improvements in friendship relationships [25,28]; positive changes in the perception of the social climate [29]; improvement in social relationships [30]; improvement in trait emotional intelligence and motivational mediators [31]; and improvement in sport culture and enthusiasm. However, no benefits in terms of life satisfaction have been found [32]. By making use of sport, these studies provide evidence of a meaningful and positive impact on the psychological and physical development of the school-age population [11,33].

Health is generally determined by several physical–biological, psychological and social indicators [34]. Therefore, good health is a fundamental dimension in personal and social progress, and an important sphere in quality of life [35]. Approached from the perspective of positive health, a state of wellness encourages individuals to reach complete social and psychological development [36].

The World Health Organization (WHO) aims to promote physical and psychological health [34] that supports a good quality of life [37]. The construct of subjective well-being is among the factors that affect health. Consequently, research on the influence of subjective well-being in different social and educational contexts has received increasing attention in recent decades [38]. Subjective well-being comprises two main factors: a cognitive aspect (satisfaction with one's own life) and an affective aspect (positive and negative affect) [39,40]. The cognitive side of well-being reflects the assessment of how individuals process information in their lives [41]. The affective side of well-being implies a hedonistic individual balance; that is, how often individuals experience positive and negative emotions [39,40].

Recent research has focused on studying the effects of positive psychological variables on personal and social development [42]. These studies have been categorised as positive psychology [43]. Emotional intelligence is a positive variable that currently has broad support because of its close connections to subjective well-being and physical and mental health [38,44,45].

Variables such as social anxiety have a negative effect on subjective well-being [46]. In this sense, social anxiety can be defined as a person's constant fear of one or more social or performance situations, in which they are exposed to unknown persons or the possible scrutiny of other people [47]. Social anxiety has a negative impact on subjective well-being in adolescents because of the anguish individuals may feel [48], which in turn may negatively affect the quality of their interpersonal relationships [49,50].

We consider that education should promote social and emotional learning, which the WHO defines as a heterogeneous set of life skills, as this is a potential factor that supports and encourages mental health [51]. Scholars in favour of this teaching proposal argue that emotional education may also promote public health [52,53], because its ultimate goal is improvement of the general quality of

health and well-being in citizens. In the school context, many researchers claim that a key purpose of education is to improve peoples' lives so that they can reach an optimal degree of personal happiness and well-being in adulthood [54]. This suggests that a healthy pedagogical and psychological school environment may facilitate students' positive adjustment; therefore, such an environment is essential for the development of well-being in children and adolescents [55].

The theoretical and practical justification for this study was rooted in the work of various authors who developed educational interventions based on the sport education model and recommended that further research should evaluate the impact of this model on the promotion of optimal personal and social development [25,26,56,57]. In this sense, Metzler's [16] contributions are very relevant, stating that a sports model teaching program is mainly focused on different domains [16]: affective, cognitive and motor. In line with this statement, our study focuses on the affective domain. We agree with several previous authors [39,40] that subjective well-being is a key variable that influences balanced personal and social development. In addition, the existing relationship between subjective well-being and trait emotional intelligence suggests that it is necessary to further explore this topic. Social anxiety generates inappropriate social relationships in adolescents [46,48]. Given the positive effects of the sport education model on social relationships [30], it is possible that such interventions may reduce social anxiety.

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of a pilot programme based on the sport education model on the three variables: subjective well-being, trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety. The hypotheses focused on the assumptions that the programme will result in improvements in our participants' subjective well-being (Hypothesis 1), trait emotional intelligence (Hypothesis 2) and social anxiety (Hypothesis 3).

2. Methods

2.1. Participants

This study used non-probability incidental or accessibility sampling. The sample comprised 113 students in compulsory secondary education aged 12–15 years (mean age (M) = 13.82 years, standard deviation (SD) = 0.79 years). The research was conducted in a state school with students from five class groups. The control group comprised 44 students (two class groups) and the experimental group included 69 students (three class groups). The experimental and control group assignment was based on a cluster-randomised controlled trial. The gender distribution was 64 (57%) boys and 49 (43%) girls (Table 1).

The main inclusion criterion was parental consent. The exclusion criteria were: (a) attending less than 80% of the sessions of the intervention programme (less than 13 sessions); (b) students with special educational needs associated with intellectual disability; and (c) students that were removed from school for disciplinary reasons.

Table 1. Sex and age of the sample.

		<i>n</i>	%
Sex	Male	64	57
	Female	49	43
Age	12	42	37
	13	45	40
	14	23	20
	15	3	3

2.2. Procedure

We requested the collaboration of the educational centre (Spain) in this study. The management board of the participating school was contacted to obtain their approval and authorisation for the study. Permission was also obtained from the families of the participating students, and from the teaching staff and school council. This study respected the relevant ethical values and guaranteed participants' confidentiality and anonymity. In addition, this study was developed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki regarding human experimentation. The study procedures were conducted in accordance with the Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha code of ethics.

This study used a quasi-experimental design with repeated pre-test and post-test measures and a control group. The study was conducted over three stages. First, before the intervention began, the assessment instruments (pre-test evaluation) were handed out for completion in the first 20 minutes of two sessions, to avoid burdening the students. Next, the programme based on the sport education model was implemented. The programme sessions took place during the second term of the school year. Finally, the assessment instruments were completed a second time (post-test evaluation). The independent variable was the intervention programme, and the dependent variables were subjective well-being, trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety.

2.3. Measures

Four evaluation instruments were used to assess the variables in this study, under the psychometric parameters of reliability and validity.

The Kidscreen-10 Index [58] was used to assess subjective health-related quality of life and well-being. This 10-item scale was designed for children and adolescents aged 8–18 years. Each item has five response options, ranging from 'Never' to 'Always' or 'Not at all' to 'Extremely'. The 10 items cover: affective symptoms of depressed mood; cognitive symptoms of disturbed concentration; psychovegetative aspects of vitality, energy and feeling well; and psychosocial aspects correlated with mental health, such as the ability to experience fun with friends or getting along well with others at school. The adapted version of the questionnaire used in this study has adequate internal consistency reliability (*Cronbach's alpha* = 0.82) and test-retest stability ($r = 0.73$; $ICC = 0.72$) [59].

The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule [60] was used to assess participants' positive and negative affect. The Spanish version of this scale for children and adolescents was validated by Sandín [61]. This scale comprises 20 items on two dimensions: positive affect and negative affect. Each subscale contains 10 items. The questionnaire is completed by participants based on the way they normally feel and behave. The scale has three response options: 'Never' = 1, 'Sometimes' = 2, and 'Many times' = 3.

We used the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire Adolescents Short Form (TEIQue-ASF) [62] (adapted into Spanish in its abridged version for teenagers by Ferrando and Serra [63]) to evaluate trait emotional intelligence based on the theoretical model of Petrides and Furnham [64]. The 30 items that make up the TEIQue-ASF are scored on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = 'Completely disagree' to 7 = 'Completely agree'). The general emotional intelligence score of the total scale is obtained by summing the 30 items.

Finally, participants completed the Social Anxiety Scale for Adolescents (SAS-A) [65]. The SAS-A comprises 22 items; 18 items are self-descriptive and four are distracting elements that are not taken into account for the score. The SAS-A contains three subscales: (a) fear of negative evaluation (eight items), (b) anxiety and social avoidance before strangers or new social situations (six items) and (c) anxiety and social avoidance in social situations in general (four items). Responses are on a 5-point Likert-type scale from 1 ('Never') to 5 ('Always'). In addition, a global index of social anxiety (SAS-T) is obtained by summing the scores for the items (excluding neutral items). High scores reflect high levels of social anxiety [65]. The scale was adapted to the Spanish population by Olivares, Ruiz, Hidalgo, García-López, Rosa and Piqueras [66]. Only the SAS-T score was used in this study.

2.4. Intervention Programme

The physical-sport programme was completed following the sport education model structure [17]: (1) *season*: lengthy didactic units; (2) *membership*: development of a team spirit and cooperation; (3) *regular competition*: showing technical–tactical abilities; (4) *data register*: giving evidence of and analysing the process that has been followed; and (5) *festivity*: a festive atmosphere. This highlighted other important education aspects such as: cooperative learning; autonomy and personal initiative; positive interdependence; and self-management of responsibility roles in conflict resolution (i.e., referee and coach). This helped to make the sport experience more real and positive, including how students transferred responsibilities by means of organisation roles (i.e., referee and scorer), team roles (i.e., coach and physical trainer) and how sport content was modified when adapted to the students [17].

Hastie and Casey’s guidelines were followed for the design and validation of the programme [19] (p. 423): (a) thoroughly detailed curricular elements; (b) precise certification of the applied model; and (c) an in-depth explanation of the context of the programme. The intervention programme was implemented in the experimental group following sequencing of content and activities in three stages (initial, intermediate and final) over 16 sessions (Table 2).

Table 2. Sequencing of stages and activity sessions in the intervention programme.

Stage	Session	Sport Education Model
Initial (Theoretical Sessions)	1–2	Introduction and presentation of the Sport Education Model with digital and audio-visual support (ICT). Presentation and distribution of learning resources. Division and organisation of classroom groups in teams (assignment of team names with a didactic and cross curricular theme). Distribution and selection of responsibility roles.
	3	Explanation for the self-design of learning resources on digital format (ICT). Selection and assignment of anthems, badges, mascots and t-shirts representing a team.
Intermediate (Practical Sessions)	4–7	Practical implementation of the roles of each member of the teams. Learning of technical-tactical elements and abilities: kicking-off, catching, moving, throwing, defence and attack. Learning game rules.
	8–9	Warming-up, training and friendly matches. Meetings for comprehension and reflection with intervention of the responsibility roles.
	10–14	Regular stage competition (Round Robin).
Final (Practical Sessions)	15–16	Inter-class groups final competitions (final matches with class groups), final event, giving awards and diplomas.

This pilot programme was developed to reflect the teaching hours of the physical education subject, which covers 16 55 minute sessions (2–3 sessions per week for 6 weeks). The total duration was considered sufficient to analyse the possible effects of the programme on the dependent variables, as indicated by previous research [67].

The educational intervention applied to the experimental group consisted of a didactic unit that used an alternative sport, called ringo [68,69]. Ringo is an alternative, modified and reduced sport of divided court and net. It is played with a hoop (ringo) and a volleyball net. The objective is to score when the ringo falls on the opposite court (Figure 1). In this pilot programme, the application of an alternative sport that was novel and unknown to students meant that everyone started with the same theoretical and practical sports knowledge, and there were few initial differences in their levels of technical–tactical sports skill. Alternative sports are characterised by being motivating, cooperative, socialising and adapted to participants’ characteristics. The selection and organisation of teams (five teams per classroom) was developed by drawing lots. In addition, different responsibility roles were assigned to participating students: player; referee; coach–captain; physical trainer; person responsible

for statistics and reports; and member of the discipline and organisation committee. An essential rule in the development of the pilot programme was that all students would actively participate in the programme with the assignment of two roles (player role and another responsibility role). The pilot programme also used various learning and curricular resources (self-designed portfolio, worksheets and reports) that had been used by other authors [70].

Figure 1. Practical session of the intervention programme.

For the control group, a didactic unit of traditional collective sport with a conventional teaching style was developed [71]. This traditional teaching model aimed to improve students' technical motor skills only. In the teaching–learning process, the teacher assumed a managerial role and the students adopted passive individual roles limited to following the directive instructions of the teacher. This intervention consisted of 12 55 minute sessions (two sessions per week for 6 weeks). The first nine sessions were aimed at learning the technical fundamentals of basketball (pot, dribbling, passing, throwing and receiving) through a task assignment teaching style [71]. These traditional sports sessions were based on a 10 minute warm-up, 40 minute main session that included explanations and basketball practice and a 5-minute warm down in which stretching was performed. During these sessions, all tasks were directed by the teacher without students' participation. The last three sessions were dedicated to team competition.

Two compulsory secondary education teachers, both with advanced degrees in Sports Science participated in this research. The first teacher (with a Master's of Science in Psychology) participated in the design and implementation of the pilot programme. The second teacher developed an intervention based on the traditional model. Both teachers received a 10 hour training course on the specific theoretical and practical aspects of each teaching model. In addition, supervision and tutoring was provided by a researcher expert in the sports education model and a researcher expert in the traditional education model. This tutoring consisted of: (a) session-by-session analysis during the intervention programmes; (b) telephone conversations and emails to resolve doubts, concerns and problems; and (c) weekly visits to the teaching centre. In these visits, the experts visited the centre randomly, without prior notice, with the objectives of: verifying that there were no gaps between what was planned and what was implemented, and checking that the teaching models were applied with all of their characteristics.

2.5. Data Analysis

After fulfilment of the requirements of normality and homoscedasticity was verified, we examined the distribution of the data for a univariate normality analysis. The results showed asymmetry and kurtosis values lower than 1.2. Next, we calculated the reliability coefficients (Cronbach's alpha,

composite reliability, average variance extracted and McDonald's omega coefficient) to obtain reliability evidence. Then, to determine the impact of the programme, descriptive analyses (mean and SD) and analyses of variance (ANOVA) were performed with the scores collected in the pre-test stage. Subsequently, descriptive analyses and analyses of covariance (ANCOVA) were used with post-test scores to determine the impact of the programme on each of the variables. Bonferroni correction was applied for multiple comparisons. For all analyses, a p -value <0.05 was considered to indicate statistical significance. After application of Bonferroni correction, a p -value <0.012 was considered significant.

The effect size (μ^2) of the differences was calculated using partial eta-squared [72]. The effect size was analysed based on four ranges: 0–0.009, negligible; 0.010–0.089, low-effect size; 0.090–0.249, medium-effect size; and >0.250 , big-effect size [72]. The data were analysed with SPSS version 24.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Reliability

In this study, we used well-established measures with appropriate psychometric properties (Table 3).

Table 3. Reliability evidence of the instruments used ($n = 113$).

Measures	α	CR	AVE	Ω
KIDSCREEN	0.91	0.89	0.674	0.92
PANASN-PA	0.70	0.77	0.502	0.72
PANASN-NA	0.74	0.76	0.519	0.77
TEIQue-ASF	0.71	0.70	0.503	0.79
SAS-T	0.85	0.80	0.687	0.87

Notes: α = Cronbach's alpha; CR = composite reliability, AVE = average variance extracted; Ω = McDonald's omega index.

3.2. Effects of the Programme

The pre-test MANOVA results did not reveal statistically significant differences between the groups prior to the intervention, Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.571$, $F(5, 108) = 0.739$, $p = 0.333$, with a small effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.062$, $r = 0.11$).

The ANOVA using the pre-test scores (Table 4) revealed no statistically significant differences in any of the dependent variables before the programme began, except for a significantly higher score for trait emotional intelligence in the experimental group compared with the control group. The size of the effect was low for trait emotional intelligence ($\mu^2 = 0.009$). Applying Bonferroni correction showed no significant differences in any of the variables.

Results from the pre-test–post-test MANCOVA revealed significant differences between the two conditions, Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.899$, $F(5, 108) = 5.295$, $p = 0.003$, with an average effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.267$, $r = 0.32$).

Next, we performed ANCOVA for the dependent variables using the post-test scores. To assess the magnitude of these differences, the effect size for each variable was calculated by partial eta-squared (Table 4).

3.2.1. Effects on Subjective Well-Being

There was no significant improvement in post-test health-related quality of life in the experimental group (Table 4). The experimental group did not show a significant increase in positive affect scores after testing. We confirmed a significant decrease in post-test negative affect scores in the experimental group (Table 4), with a medium effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.123$; partial eta-squared).

3.2.2. Effects on Trait Emotional Intelligence

The analysis revealed significant improvements in trait emotional intelligence in the experimental group after the programme, with a medium effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.241$) (Table 4).

3.2.3. Effects on Social Anxiety

There were no significant differences between the experimental and the control groups in SAS-T scores (Table 4).

Table 4. Mean, standard deviation, analysis of variance, analysis of covariance and effect size for differences in means (partial eta-squared) as a function of the experimental and control groups at pre-test and post-test.

Measures	PRE-TEST					POST-TEST					
	EXPERIMENTAL		CONTROL		<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	μ^2	EXPERIMENTAL		CONTROL	
	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>				<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	μ^2	
KIDSCREEN											
HRQL	35.18 (5.84)	35.09 (6.01)	1.414	0.697	0.001	36.94 (6.14)	35.04 (5.99)	1.975	0.018	0.072	
PANASN											
PA	21.43 (3.90)	20.02 (4.21)	3.293	0.07	0.008	21.95 (2.78)	20.33 (2.88)	5.438	0.017	0.144	
NA	11.23 (3.54)	11.58 (3.58)	0.251	0.62	0.004	9.96 (2.95)	11.62 (3.86)	7.044	0.010	0.123	
TEIQUE-ASF											
TEI	4.82 (0.60)	4.58 (0.64)	4.368	0.04	0.009	5.02 (0.63)	4.52 (0.53)	16.394	0.000	0.241	
SAS											
SAS-T	2.61 (0.67)	2.64 (0.68)	0.040	0.84	−0.001	2.38 (0.63)	2.58 (0.62)	3.419	0.062	0.014	

Note: HRQL = health-related quality of life; PA = positive affect; NA = negative affect; TEI = trait emotional intelligence; SAS-T = Total Social Anxiety Scale; SD = standard deviation.

4. Discussion

This study evaluated the impact of a pilot programme based on the sports education model on compulsory secondary education students' subjective well-being, trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety.

The preliminary results obtained in this study revealed significant improvement of a specific indicator of subjective well-being (NA) in the experimental group after the pilot programme. The experimental group did not show a significant improvement in health-related quality of life when compared with the control group. Our results are consistent with the findings reported in other studies [32], which did not confirm significant benefits for life satisfaction among adolescents following a sport education-based experience. Our findings also indicated that the programme showed a significant decrease in negative affect, improving an indicator of the affective component of subjective well-being (i.e., a decrease in negative emotions) [39,40]. These results partially verify Hypothesis 1, and highlight the importance of further research in this context.

This is consistent with the findings reported in other studies [32], as previous studies established a connection between physical activity and subjective well-being [73]. These findings are also consistent with research that argues that active, inclusive and effective teaching and learning processes applied within a quality physical education framework fosters a motivating school climate in affective and psychological terms [1,74]. Pedagogical and methodological aspects highlighted by this intervention pilot programme (e.g., cooperative learning, a feeling of membership to a team, positive interdependence and self-management or autonomy/use of responsibility roles) could have influenced these results. Furthermore, a motivating school context, enabled by the implementation of the sport education model [31], may also strengthen affective bonding in adolescents [12].

Significant improvement in trait emotional intelligence was observed in the experimental group after the programme, which confirmed Hypothesis 2. These results are also consistent with those reported by other authors [31]. The relationship between trait emotional intelligence and subjective well-being [38,45], as well as that between trait emotional intelligence and physical and psychological

health [44], may trigger these improvements in adolescents. This indicates that good trait emotional intelligence promotes positive emotional states and a reduction of negative moods, thereby positively impacting well-being and health [45].

We found no significant improvement in students' social anxiety, meaning that we could not confirm Hypothesis 3. Although this is similar to the results obtained by different authors for social relationships variables [23,24], our results contradicted the findings of other studies [25,26,28,30]. Further research on the effects of the sport education model is therefore necessary, especially given the theoretical specificity of social anxiety and its incidence in social relationships among adolescents. In addition, social anxiety can present opposing consequences. It can have positive effects on social relationships for some individuals, whereas it can have negative effects on others, characterised by anguish and social avoidance [65].

However, in our opinion this study has been very exhaustive in the evaluation methodology of the intervention program (including the Bonferroni corrections). In this sense, we have not found any study on the effectiveness of the sport education model that uses these statistical corrections. This fact could be influencing the comparison of our results with those obtained in other similar researches on the sport education model as a teaching model.

Despite these promising results, this study had some limitations. First, the sampling procedure was chosen for reasons of convenience and not by random procedures. However, allocating students to either the experimental or control group was performed randomly based on the class group to which they belonged. Second, it would be necessary to increase the sample size to minimise potential biases in the results and increase the generalisability. Third, the instruments used were self-reported, and the results might have been influenced by bias related to social desirability in adolescents. It would be necessary to use high-performance tests or hetero-evaluation to minimise such bias. Similarly, differences in the trait emotional intelligence pre-test scores between the experimental and control groups might have had an impact on our results. Finally, it is necessary to highlight the difficulties encountered when following all of the recommendations for the implementation of the sport education model [19]. Similarly, it would be necessary to include session analysis procedure in order to evaluate if the main principles of the model were followed by the teachers [75].

Several aspects can be suggested regarding future lines of investigation, such as increasing the number of participants and diversifying their sociocultural background. It may also be worthwhile analysing the impact of the programme on other variables, such as academic performance and social and school adjustment. Similarly, to study the effects on depression with the use of biological correlates (HPA markers, cortisol immunitarian parameters, etc.). In addition, it would be interesting to conduct a follow-up evaluation to assess the sustainability of the effects of the programme.

This study presents innovative contributions at both theoretical and practical levels. The theoretical contribution is related to fact that the lack of physical activity can have a harmful effect on individual's health and is currently an important public health concern [76]. In this respect, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) [1] emphasised the importance of fostering and promoting active behaviours [6] in all contexts, especially at schools. Consequently, it should be noted that there is a positive connection between health and physical activity: sedentarism is a major risk factor for mortality, which gives rise to concern about the prevalence of sedentarism and socio-educative patterns of inactivity, especially in school contexts. At a practical level, our findings may help teaching staff in their tasks at school, as they provide a tool that may be used in teaching practice. In addition, the findings open up interesting fields of research in terms of the application of sport education, especially in terms of its impact on psychological variables.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, our findings suggest that the pilot programme stimulated some improvement in adolescents' subjective well-being and trait emotional intelligence, but did not impact social anxiety. Therefore, on the basis of quality physical education and the social and emotional learning approach,

the implementation of such programmes is recommended given the possible psychological benefits for adolescents in the educational context. A commitment to sports and other physical-sport activity options within a quality physical education framework, efficiently applied by means of relevant pedagogical models (such as sport education), may play an important role in students' integral development [77,78].

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Social Competence and Peer Social Acceptance: Evaluating Effects of an Educational Intervention in Adolescents

Pablo Luna¹, Jerónimo Guerrero², Débora Rodrigo-Ruiz³, Lidía Losada⁴ and Javier Cejudo^{1*}

¹ Department of Psychology, Faculty of Education, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Ciudad Real, Spain, ² Department of Physical Education, Instituto de Enseñanza Secundaria (IES) Lazarillo de Tormes, Toledo, Spain, ³ Department of Research and Diagnostic Methods in Education II, Faculty of Education, International University of La Rioja (UNIR), Logroño, Spain, ⁴ Faculty of Education, National University of Distance Education (UNED), Madrid, Spain

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*Correspondence:

Javier Cejudo
manueljavier.cejudo@uclm.es

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This study aims to evaluate the impact of an educational intervention on social competence and social acceptance among adolescents. The participants were 106 adolescents aged 12–15 years ($M = 13.41$ years; $SD = 0.81$ years). Participants were randomly assigned to the control group ($n = 44$) and an experimental group ($n = 69$). In the experimental group, an intervention based on the Sport Education Model (SEM) was applied. While in the control group, an intervention based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) was carried out. An experimental design with repeated pretest and posttest measurements was developed. The Adolescent Multidimensional Social Competence Questionnaire (AMSC-Q) was used to assess social competence. The Guess Who (GW4) questionnaire was used to assess social acceptance (SA) among peers. The preliminary results showed that the intervention based on the SEM (experimental group) promoted more significant improvements in some indicators of social competence and social acceptance among peers than those obtained with the TM-DI (control group). The results confirm a similar impact of the intervention between boys and girls. These preliminary results suggest the potential of the Sport Education Model with adolescents.

Keywords: quality physical education, sport education model, social competence, peer social acceptance, gender, adolescents

INTRODUCTION

Quality education requires attending to cognitive and affective-social dimensions that facilitate the physical and psychosocial development of students (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2015). The importance of the affective-social dimension in the success of the teaching and learning process in the educational context are issues that are arousing great interest in research (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2015; Franco et al., 2017; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2018). Accordingly, the teaching and learning process has an individual and social aspect (Franco et al., 2017), where the search for social objectives can boost school achievement (Elliot et al., 2006; Cecchini-Estrada et al., 2011).

To increase this success in the educational context, it is not only necessary to promote cognitive skills, but also to strengthen socio-emotional skills (Greenberg et al., 2003; Payton et al., 2008; Domitrovich et al., 2017; Taylor et al., 2017). Likewise, socio-emotional skills promote interpersonal relationships between students and other educational agents involved (Garn et al., 2011; Bessa et al., 2019; Kao, 2019). Therefore, it is relevant to promote optimal educational and motivational climates in educational contexts that favor a positive psychosocial adjustment and integral development of the student personality (Bisquerra et al., 2015).

The interest in the educational context for the social and emotional dimension, added to the promotion of satisfactory interpersonal skills (being and feeling accepted) (Zhang et al., 2014) have highlighted that social behavior plays an essential role in the abilities of students, especially in adolescents (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017) favoring school success (Cappadocia and Weiss, 2011). It has been recognized that social competence is an inclusive, evaluative, and multidimensional construct (e.g., socio-emotional skills; emotional regulation; prosocial behavior; ability to adapt normatively; social adjustment or perceived effectiveness in social interactions) that cannot be understood from a unilateral perspective (Dirks et al., 2007; Santos et al., 2013; Losada, 2018).

Gómez-Ortiz et al. (2019) define social competence as the effectiveness in social interaction, which arises from the use of socio-emotional skills to achieve personal goals over time and in different situations. In this way, social competence encompasses a series of cognitive, social, and emotional abilities of the individual, to manage the interpersonal relationships that occur in different contexts, favoring healthier relationships among others (Del Prette and Del Prette, 2005). Gresham (1988) divides social competence into the following elements: (1) adaptive behavior (physical and language development, academic competencies and independent functional skills); (2) interpersonal behaviors (cooperative and play behaviors; conversation and regulatory acceptance skills); (3) self-perceived behaviors (of oneself: expressing ethical and positive feelings and behaviors); and (4) behaviors toward homework (attention, task resolution, and individual work).

Thereby, social competence is related to the adjustment to the demands of the school environment, interpersonal relationships, emotional health and acceptance among peers (Losada et al., 2017). Also, it would be pertinent to examine and evaluate, through programs or interventions, the impact of this competence or interpersonal skills in the educational context (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017, 2019; Losada et al., 2017), especially in adolescent students, because it is a period of maturation and sensitive adaptation (typical transitions of this stage) for personal, social and emotional development (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017, 2019; Bessa et al., 2019). Therefore, social competence plays a vital role in the educational process, since it is necessary to favor positive and quality learning (Del Prette and Del Prette, 2005; Elijah and Madeira, 2013).

A primary objective in the educational context is to promote healthy lifestyles (World Health Organization [WHO], 2016), active and participatory (Pate and Dowda, 2019). Accordingly, physical education, within the framework of a Physical Education

of quality reinforcing prosocial practices (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2015) is instrumentalized as an effective subject to favor an integral commitment of students (Whitehead, 2010; Escalié et al., 2019) by positively developing their cognitive, affective, physical and social spheres (Mitchell and Hutchinson, 2003; Kao, 2019; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). The Association for Physical Education [afPE] (2015) states that quality Physical Education acts as a starting point for a commitment to physical activity and sport throughout life. Thus, this subject provides students with active, cooperative and practical resources (Girard et al., 2019) that improve experiences in the school environment (Kohl and Cook, 2013; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). Similarly, it encourages students to develop personal and social skills in a real environment that in other subjects would be more complex to teach (Hellison, 2011).

Physical Education is recognized for playing a relevant role in the acquisition of values and competences that contribute to the personal and socio-emotional development of students (Bessa et al., 2019). Thereby, some authors point out that through adequately structured and planned interventions, it could contribute to the social development of students in the subject of Physical Education (Eldar, 2008; Unlu et al., 2011; Gil-Madrona et al., 2019; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). Physical Education offers the student a meaningful learning experience driven by the development of social skills (interpersonal interactions, tolerance, and respect) (Cronin et al., 2018; Kao, 2019); social responsibility adherence and team cohesion: group affiliation or identity, cooperative work (Brinkley et al., 2017; Cronin et al., 2018); and reinforcement of the development of social cognition (Bailey, 2006). Therefore, quality Physical Education (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2015) will be a crucial ally in the educational context, to promote positive environments in the development of prosocial behaviors (Mayfield et al., 2017), as long as they are promoted in active, participatory and motivating contexts (Shields et al., 2018).

Consequently, it is relevant in the educational context to configure a path of methodological renewal that evolves, as established by United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO] (2015), toward a quality Physical Education for the interrelation of inclusive, active and participatory teaching and learning, over against a Physical Education, traditionally based on processes linked only to memorized methodology and mechanized and specific motor skills (e.g., technification and performance) (González-Víllora et al., 2009). Therefore, we look for methodological experiences that promote positive pedagogical practices with interventions based on teaching models (IM: *Instructional Models*) (Metzler, 2017) or based on practice (MsBP: *Models-Based Practice*) (Casey, 2014). These pedagogical models developed in a safe and contextualized way (Casey and MacPhail, 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2019) versus traditional decontextualized educational models (DI: *Direct Instruction*) (Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019) will be more motivating for students and will significantly improve the practice of physical-sports content, social and interpersonal relationships (Gil-Arias et al., 2017).

The Sport Education Model (SEM) (Hastie and Wallhead, 2016; Bessa et al., 2019; Kao, 2019; Luna et al., 2019;

Siedentop et al., 2019) is among the most suitable pedagogical models (Iserbyt et al., 2016) to develop the affective-social dimension of students. This is a model (MsBP) whose purpose is that all students live authentic sports experiences (Siedentop et al., 2019). Likewise, the SEM (Siedentop, 1994) intends to develop competent, enthusiastic, and physically (Whitehead, 2010) and sportingly literate students (Kolovelonis and Goudas, 2018). Thus, United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO] (2015) reports that the practice of healthy and active sports activities in organized games and sports, such as those planned and developed in the SEM and instrumentalized in quality Physical Education, show a positive impact on psychosocial adjustment of students, as well as in their emotional, physical, and cognitive dimension. Therefore, it is a favorable pedagogical model for proactive social development, positive responsibility, and more equitable and inclusive learning (Farias et al., 2019).

In the same line, some systematic reviews conclude that through interventions based on the SEM, there are improvements in technical-tactical skills (physical and cognitive physical domain), social and emotional development (Evangelio et al., 2018; González-Víllora et al., 2018) and motivational aspects (Chu and Zhang, 2018). In addition, meta-analysis (e.g., Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019) confirms benefits in motivation toward physical and sports activity, belonging and social responsibility, autonomy, and organization. Recent SEM results show positive effects on motor behaviors (Pereira et al., 2015; Wahl-Alexander and Chomentowski, 2018; Araújo et al., 2019), technical-tactical skills (Farias et al., 2015) and activity, knowledge, and physical performance (Ward et al., 2017). Also, improvements in trait emotional intelligence and subjective well-being (Luna et al., 2019), motivation (Cuevas et al., 2016; Gil-Arias et al., 2017), social cohesion and social skills (Kao, 2019; Pan et al., 2019), attitudes toward violence, social responsibility, and friendly relations (Menéndez-Santurio and Fernández-Río, 2016), assertiveness (García-López and Gutiérrez, 2015), and social relations (Perlman, 2010) have been found. However, regarding the statistical analysis of the data, in most of these previous studies, the change/gain score through analysis of variance (ANOVA) (that is, posttest minus pretest) was used as a criterion group comparison. In this sense, some authors such as Pérez-González and Qualter (2018) recommend the use of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) where the covariate is the baseline or pretest score, controlling for the possible effect of the pretest score on the results of the posttest. Criteria followed in the present study are in the same line as other authors (e.g., Menéndez-Santurio and Fernández-Río, 2016; Kao, 2019; Luna et al., 2019; Pan et al., 2019).

On the other hand, it is necessary to point out that there are stereotyped preconceptions and sports discrimination based on gender (Leaper, 2011; Parker and Curtner-Smith, 2012). Along these lines, some previous studies on interventions based on SEM have not shown differences in their impact, depending on gender, physical abilities (Araújo et al., 2019) and socio-emotional skills (Evangelio et al., 2018). On the contrary, other researches have shown differences in impact, depending on gender: some studies conclude that boys have greater improvements than girls in

social interactions (Brock et al., 2009; Hastie et al., 2009), while other research confirms more significant improvements in girls than in boys in technical-tactical sports knowledge (Mesquita et al., 2012).

Accordingly to all this, the purpose of the current study was to evaluate the effects of a SEM-based intervention, compared to an intervention based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI), in adolescents on the variables: (1) social competence and (2) social acceptance among peers. Regarding the hypotheses, it was proposed that said intervention (based on the SEM) would improve the participants' social competence (H1) and social acceptance among peers (H2). Finally, the impact of the intervention would not show differences, depending on gender (H3) in line with previous studies (Evangelio et al., 2018).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design

A randomized experimental design was conducted with two repeated measures (pretest and posttest). The participants were randomly assigned to the experimental group (EG) and control group (CG) through a randomized controlled group trial.

Participants

The total sample was composed of 114 adolescents, aged between 12 and 15 years (mean age (M) = 13.41 years; standard deviation (SD) = 0.81 years). Regarding the sociodemographic distribution of the sample: (a) by gender, 52% were girls, and 48% were boys; (b) by age, 35% were 12 years old, 48% 13 years old, 15% 14 years old, and 2% 15 years old. The differences in the two conditions (experimental and control groups) were not significant by age ($\chi^2 = 1.08, p > 0.05$) or by gender ($\chi^2 = 1.14, p > 0.05$).

The criteria for inclusion ($n = 106$) in the study were: (1) regular attendance to school ($\geq 80\%$ of attendance) and (2) informed written consent from the parents (or legal guardian). The exclusion criteria ($n = 8$) were: (1) attend less than 80% of the educational intervention sessions (less than 13 sessions); (2) students with more than 30% truancy; (3) students with special educational needs; (4) students sanctioned for disciplinary reasons by the school; (5) did not obtain informed written consent from the parents (or legal guardian). The 106 participants who met the proposed criteria were randomly assigned to the EG ($n = 62$) or the CG ($n = 44$). Participant flow is displayed below (refer to **Figure 1**).

Measures

In this investigation, two measures have been used to evaluate the proposed variables.

Adolescent Multidimensional Social Competence Questionnaire (AMSC-Q)

The Adolescent Multidimensional Social Competence Questionnaire (AMSC-Q) has been used to assess social competence. The instrument was validated in Spanish for its use with Spanish adolescents (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017). The AMSC-Q contains 26 Likert-type items scored on a scale from 1

to 7 (1 = *completely false*; 7 = *completely true*). This instrument measures five factors of social competence: cognitive reappraisal, social adjustment, prosocial behavior, perceived social efficacy, and normative adjustment. In the current study, the evidences of reliability are the following: cognitive reappraisal ($\alpha = 0.71$; $\Omega = 0.70$); social adjustment ($\alpha = 0.84$; $\Omega = 0.83$); prosocial behavior ($\alpha = 0.76$; $\Omega = 0.72$); perceived social efficacy ($\alpha = 0.80$; $\Omega = 0.77$); and normative adjustment ($\alpha = 0.79$; $\Omega = 0.79$).

Guess Who Questionnaire (GW4)

The Guess Who questionnaire (GW4) (Mavroveli et al., 2009); version adapted to Spanish by Losada et al. (2017) has been used to assess social acceptance among peers (SA). The GW4 is made up of four indicators of social behavior or attributes based on descriptors of habitual behavior patterns (kind; stalker; cooperator; leader). The descriptor *kind* indicates classmates who take into account the feelings of others, are friendly, and are generous with their things. The descriptor *stalker* is defined as classmates who often mess with other children, hit them, or

behave unpleasantly for no reason. The descriptor *cooperator* indicates the classmates with whom they would form a group because they collaborate, participate, share, and respect others. The descriptor *leader* indicates peers who lead and encourage to keep going. Likewise, based on the results in each of the four indicators, a global score or Index of Social Acceptance (ISA) may be calculated, as a result of adding the nominations in the three prosocial domains and subsequently subtracting the score obtained in the antisocial domain. Previously, the nominations received in the four descriptors have to be transformed into percentages. In calculating the percentages for each descriptor, the account is taken of the total number of students in the class group, the total number of students responding in the class group, and the number of nominations allowed, which is unlimited, but at a minimum would be equal to one. The maximum number of nominations from one student is equal to the total number of students minus the nominating subject (Losada et al., 2017). In the current study, the evidence of reliability for the ISA is $\alpha = 0.76$; $\Omega = 0.79$.

Procedure

The study design was developed in four periods. In the first period, the educational intervention was designed. Secondly, a pretest assessment (T1) was carried out in the experimental and control group, administering the assessment instruments with scheduled breaks to avoid student fatigue. The pretest evaluation was carried out as a group. The administration of the pretest evaluations was carried out by two members of the research team different from the teachers who implemented the program. In the third period, the educational intervention based on the SEM was applied in the EG, while in the CG, scheduled sessions of the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) were developed. To minimize the effect of the experimenter on the results, the participating adolescents, and the teachers who applied each of the interventions were unaware of the hypotheses and objectives of the research team (single-blind procedure). Both happened during the Physical Education class on school hours. In the last period, at the end of the intervention, the posttest assessment (T2) was carried out in both groups, following the same rest procedure as in T1. Posttest evaluations were administered by two members of the research team different from the teachers who carried out the program. The posttest evaluation was developed in groups.

Ethical Considerations

This study has been developed under the University of Castilla-La Mancha (UCLM) code of ethics, following international guidelines on experiments with human subjects described in the Nuremberg Code and the Declaration of Helsinki. The Management Team, the School Board, and the Teachers of the participating school authorized the investigation since it is an investigation framed within a public educational context. An informed written consent for the participating students was signed by a parent or legal guardian. Likewise, the requirements of ethical confidentiality were respected and guaranteed according to the voluntary and anonymous nature of the participants (ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association [APA], 2019; Personal Data Protection Law of the Research Ethics Committee on Human Beings, CEISH).

Educational Intervention

Two educational interventions were developed: in the experimental group, the intervention was based on the Sport Education model (SEM) (Siedentop et al., 2019) and in the control group, the intervention was based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) (Metzler, 2017). Both were applied simultaneously during school hours by teachers specialized in Physical Education. One of the teachers developed the SEM-based intervention in the experimental group. This teacher has 15 years of teaching experience and 3 years applying the SEM in Physical Education (ecological validity). A different teacher applied a Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) in the control group. This teacher has 10 years of teaching experience, without previous SEM experience. They were carried

out during 16 sessions of 55 min each, with a frequency of two sessions per week (refer to **Table 1**). A sport of split teams or net (Polskie ringo) was used for both groups of adolescents (Méndez-Giménez et al., 2011). This alternative sport, which was new for the participating students, is played in teams on a sports field divided in two by a central volleyball net. Players must throw, receive and pass a ring over the net, scoring when the ring falls on the field of the opposite team.

Characteristics of the Intervention Based on the Sport Education Model (SEM)

The intervention design was developed following precisely and adequately the structure of the SEM (Siedentop et al., 2019) and the recommendations made by Hastie and Casey (2014). The educational experience was organized as follows: (1) *season*: long-term teaching unit; (2) *affiliation* and/or *team membership*: development of group identity and interpersonal cooperation; (3) performance of *rotating responsibility roles* (e.g., referee, captain, physical trainer, journalists, festival committee): individual and shared decision-making; (4) *regular competition*: practice of technical-tactical knowledge; (5) *data recording*: information gathering and analysis of the learning process; (6) *culminating and festive event*: final objectives for all students in a festive and motivating way.

The intervention was implemented for around 2 months, in a public educational center, within a rural environment and with a medium socioeconomic level. Likewise, it was supervised by external researchers, consisting of: (a) personal and online communication to solve possible issues; (b) regular visits to the school; (c) analysis and weekly verification of the research process.

The selection and training of the teams were carried out randomly (to break present groups). The educational practice was developed in different academic classes of Secondary Education (3 experimental groups with 5 teams in each) setting a total of 15 mixed teams with a random distribution of each participant following the principle of homogeneity according to gender and level of motor ability (Burgueño et al., 2017). All students of each team were always assigned two roles: one common to all (player) and another specific to each student: (1) *captain-coach* (coordinator and mediator of the team, in addition to acting as a communicative link between teachers-students and vice versa); (2) *referee* (in charge of the functions of conciliation and fair play of sports practice, in addition to being responsible for compliance with the rules of the game and formalization of the minutes and match reports); (3) *journalist* (in charge of statistics, data recording, and managing digital communication with an informative sports blog previously created); (4) *physical trainer* (direction of previous sports warm-ups and responsible for the team's sports equipment); and (5) *celebration organizing committee* (responsible for self-built materials, coordinator, and manager of final festive events). This educational strategy of the rotating role aims to encourage students to develop social skills such as empathy, providing them with different tasks and insights.

In short, this is a real and educational sport experience that aims to engage students with a motivating methodology

TABLE 1 | Sequence of sessions and activities in the educational interventions.

Session	SEM (experimental group)	TM-DI (control group)
1	Theoretical explanation of SEM and Polskie ringo. Delivery of teaching material (folders; match records; reports; game rules; contingency contract, etc.).	Theoretical explanation of Polskie ringo (regulatory aspects).
2–3	Training and organization of teams (choice of thematic names, hymns/emblems, identifying colors, etc.). Designation of rotating responsibility roles. Self-construction of material by student art (e.g., Polskie ringo ring).	Organization of students individually or in pairs (no persistent work groups are formed). Presentation of sports equipment provided by the school. Technical development activities (pass, launch and reception I).
4–7	Warm-up and stretching with modified sports games, directed by the teacher and students (role of physical trainer). Activities (by teams and using rotating roles of responsibility) aimed at learning technical and tactical skills of Polskie ringo (pass, serve, reception, throwing, displacements). Reflective-comprehensive meetings (positive feedback; active listening; learning-error). Knowledge of rules through the real game (fair play = sport key element). Pre-season or training for the championship (educational competition).	Warm-up sessions led by the teacher. Activities to develop technical skills repetitively (pass and reception II). Technical development activities (serve). Technical development activities (throwing). Technical development activities (displacement). Completion with stretching exercises, led by the teacher. Also, the teacher instructs the students for the improvement of the movements developed.
8–14	Friendly team matches and educational competition (fair play) through a formal and regular league (Round Robin). Development of responsibility roles (e.g., referee, journalist, captain. . .). Use of real sports elements (minutes, interviews, etc.).	Sports warm-up. Tactical development activities 1 vs. 1. Tactical development activities 2 vs. 2. Tactical development activities 3 vs. 3. Simultaneous Polskie ringo games. Final stretching exercises led by the teacher.
15–16	Semi-final and final competition between classes. Event with final festival (organized by the role of committee): delivery of trophies, diplomas and medals (self-built materials). Summative or final evaluation.	Individual theoretical assessment of Polskie ringo (regulatory aspects). Individual practical evaluation of Polskie ringo (technical elements).

focused on cooperative teaching and learning processes between internal groups as elements such as the development of a formal competition (regular league focused on fair and social game), self-construction of their own sports materials (such as the ring for the game, medals, trophies, or diplomas) (Méndez-Giménez et al., 2016) or the celebration of the final event, making the personal and social development of the adolescents more significant (Bessa et al., 2019).

Characteristics of the Intervention Based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI)

A teaching unit about Polskie ringo was designed and implemented according to a traditional methodology (Metzler, 2017; Pan et al., 2019). The methodological characteristics of Direct Instruction were: (a) teaching and learning process focused on an outstanding position of the teachers, favoring an expository and unidirectional communication to the students; (b) transmission of educational content by teachers without student intervention (only occasionally for demonstration by modeling); (c) assignment of tasks mostly centered on decisions made by teachers, where students play a passive role, that is, a teaching style where only the teacher directs and determines the tasks, objectives, evaluation, rhythm and learning time of the planned sessions and activities; (d) development of an educational experience, by students, with sports activities characterized by technical, memorial, and repetitive motor skills individually; (e) mass education with no individualization, using sports materials provided by the school; (f) learning of decontextualized sports fundamentals and

without experiencing real sports experience, that is, characterized by a first orientation of skills where students practice sports learning in isolation.

Statistical Analysis

Following collection, data were analyzed with the SPSS software, version 24.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, United States). First, the normality of the variables under study was calculated with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, all of them adjusting to the assumption of normality (analyses performed with a 95% confidence interval). Second, the evidence of reliability was calculated with the reliability coefficient of Cronbach's alpha (α) and the McDonald's omega coefficient (Ω). Third, to determine the effectiveness of the educational intervention, the following statistical analyses were performed: (1) multivariate analyses of variance (MANOVA) with the total pretest scores of the variables under study, to confirm possible starting (initial) differences between the participants of the EG and CG; (2) descriptive (M = mean; SD = standard deviation) and variance (ANOVA) analyses with each of the scores obtained for the instruments used during the pretest phase; (3) in order to show significant improvements between the experimental and control group, multivariate analyses of covariance (MANCOVA) were calculated on the set of variables investigated; (4) descriptive analyses, and covariance analyses (ANCOVA) with posttest scores; (5) finally, the effect size of the differences was calculated with partial square eta (η^2) following four statistical ranges (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007): 0–0.009, *negligible*; 0.010–0.089, *low-effect size*; 0.090–0.249, *medium-effect size*; and > 0.250, *big-effect size*.

RESULTS

The pretest MANOVA results did not reveal statistically significant differences between the groups prior to the intervention, Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.491$; $F(9, 97) = 0.572$; $p = 0.273$, with a low effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.028$; $r = 0.04$).

Pretest Analysis

The results of ANOVA in the pretest phase (refer to Table 2) showed that before starting the intervention, there were no statistically significant differences in any of the study variables.

Posttest Analysis

The results for the pretest-posttest MANCOVA did not reveal statistically significant differences between the two conditions, Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.862$; $F(9, 97) = 1.661$; $p = 0.187$, with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.081$; $r = 0.10$).

Effects on Social Competence

After performing ANCOVA in the posttest phase (refer to Table 2), the results confirmed, in favor of the EG, significant improvements in: social adjustment, with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.064$); prosocial behavior, with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.078$); perceived social efficacy, with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.072$) (refer to Figure 2). However, no significant differences were confirmed in the other two factors, cognitive reappraisal and normative adjustment.

Effects on Social Acceptance Among Peers

The results in the ANCOVA in the posttest phase (refer to Table 2) showed significant improvements in the cooperator factor with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.027$) in favor of the EG. Likewise, the results showed significant improvements in favor of the experimental group in the global index of social acceptance among peers of this variable, with a low-effect size ($\mu^2 = 0.045$) (refer to Figure 2). However, there were no significant differences in the other indicators: kind, stalker, and leader.

Effects on Gender

The results of ANOVA for the pretest phase showed that before beginning the intervention, there were no statistically significant differences, depending on gender, in any of the study variables. Similarly, the results in the ANCOVA for the posttest phase did not show differential effects between boys and girls in any of the study variables.

DISCUSSION

The current study evaluated the effects of an intervention based on the SEM, compared to an intervention based on the TM-DI, on social competence and social acceptance among adolescents. It is necessary to highlight that recent studies raise the need to continue examining the impact of SEM-based interventions in adolescents (Evangelió et al., 2018; Bessa et al., 2019; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019).

In general, the results showed statistically significant improvements, in favor of the experimental group (SEM)

TABLE 2 | Mean, standard deviation, analysis of variance, analysis of covariance, and effect size for differences in means (partial square eta) in the variables under study (social competence and peer social acceptance) in the experimental and control groups.

	Pretest						ANOVA						Posttest						ANOVA						
	EG			GC			EG			GC			EG			GC			EG			GC			
	M	SD	μ^2	M	SD	μ^2	F	p	μ^2	M	SD	μ^2	F	p	μ^2	M	SD	μ^2	F	p	μ^2	M	SD	μ^2	
SC																									
Cognitive reappraisal	4.68	1.35	0.002	4.71	1.40	0.002	0.453	0.915	0.002	4.72	1.40	0.002	0.454	0.243	0.010	4.68	1.42	0.002	0.454	0.243	0.010	4.68	1.42	0.002	
Social adjustment	5.48	1.41	0.003	5.53	4.58	0.003	1.231	0.534	0.003	6.03	1.56	0.003	2.731	0.011	0.064	5.41	1.52	0.003	2.731	0.011	0.064	5.41	1.52	0.003	
Prosocial behavior/or	5.45	1.38	0.004	5.67	1.31	0.004	0.915	0.246	0.004	6.07	1.53	0.004	3.447	0.002	0.078	5.72	1.48	0.004	3.447	0.002	0.078	5.72	1.48	0.004	
Perceived social efficacy	5.37	1.44	0.003	5.41	1.65	0.003	1.472	0.717	0.003	6.09	1.48	0.003	4.315	0.008	0.072	5.32	1.72	0.003	4.315	0.008	0.072	5.32	1.72	0.003	
Normative adjustment	5.59	1.51	0.002	5.54	1.39	0.002	0.882	0.766	0.002	5.61	1.48	0.002	0.744	0.816	0.009	5.50	1.42	0.002	0.744	0.816	0.009	5.50	1.42	0.002	
SA																									
Kind	0.31	0.10	0.009	0.32	0.14	0.009	0.617	1.014	0.009	0.34	0.11	0.009	1.126	0.414	0.011	0.30	0.15	0.009	1.126	0.414	0.011	0.30	0.15	0.009	
Stalker	0.27	0.18	0.007	0.25	0.20	0.007	0.074	0.879	0.007	0.25	0.13	0.007	0.933	0.736	0.001	0.26	0.19	0.007	0.933	0.736	0.001	0.26	0.19	0.007	
Cooperator	0.28	0.15	0.003	0.30	0.12	0.003	1.011	0.731	0.003	0.37	0.12	0.003	2.732	0.008	0.027	0.29	0.11	0.003	2.732	0.008	0.027	0.29	0.11	0.003	
Leader	0.16	0.20	0.004	0.19	0.18	0.004	0.873	0.512	0.004	0.19	0.19	0.004	0.899	0.122	0.007	0.16	0.21	0.004	0.899	0.122	0.007	0.16	0.21	0.004	
Index of social acceptance	0.77	0.48	0.002	0.81	0.41	0.002	0.342	0.873	0.002	0.87	0.45	0.002	3.715	0.010	0.045	0.75	0.40	0.002	3.715	0.010	0.045	0.75	0.40	0.002	

SC, social competence; SA, peer social acceptance; $\mu^2 = \eta^2$ = eta square effect size; EG, experimental group ($n = 62$); GC, control group ($n = 44$); M, mean; SD, standard deviation.

compared to the control group (MT-ID): (1) in some indicators of social competence; social adjustment, prosocial behavior, and perceived social efficacy. However, no significant improvements in cognitive reappraisal and normative adjustment were confirmed; (2) improvements in social acceptance among peers; specifically, in the *cooperator* factor and in the global index of social acceptance among peers. Although no improvements were found in the factors: *kind*, *stalker*, and *leader*.

First, the results showed significant improvements in some indicators of social competence. Therefore, Hypothesis 1 is partially confirmed. Specifically, the positive impact has focused on (1) social adjustment, that is, the degree to which an adolescent engages in socially competent behaviors, whose purpose is social acceptance; (2) prosocial behavior, defined as voluntary behaviors whose purpose is to benefit others (sharing, caring, comforting or helping); and (3) perceived social efficacy, or the subjective perception of effectiveness in social interactions. These results converge with other previous research papers that analyze the effectiveness of interventions based on the SEM in some socio-emotional variables (Perlman, 2010; García-López and Gutiérrez, 2015; Menéndez-Santurio and Fernández-Río, 2016; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2016; González-Villora et al., 2018; Bessa et al., 2019; Kao, 2019; Luna et al., 2019; Pan et al., 2019). The results of these previous investigations confirm in the variables under consideration, effect sizes between low and moderate, in line with those obtained in this study.

Secondly, the results show some significant improvements in the variable social acceptance among peers, specifically in the *cooperator* indicator and the global social acceptance score or *Index of Social Acceptance* (ISA). Hypothesis 2 is partially confirmed. These findings are in line with other research that has shown the positive impact of MbBP-SEM on the social

relationship (García-López and Gutiérrez, 2015; Menéndez-Santurio and Fernández-Río, 2016; Kao, 2019). The conclusions of these previous investigations in the variables being considered point to effect sizes between low and moderate, in congruence with those obtained in the current study. As we can see, the effects obtained in social competence are higher than those obtained in social acceptance. In this sense, the nuclear aspects of the MED are probably closer to the development of helping behaviors toward others, that is, toward efficacy in social interaction (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2019) than to the social acceptance within the group.

Third, the results did not confirm differential effects between boys and girls in any of the study variables. These results are consistent with those obtained in some systematic reviews that conclude that the development of interventions based on the SEM has shown improvements in the participants in empathy, assertiveness, and fair play, regardless of gender (e.g., Evangelio et al., 2018). However, it is necessary to deepen this line of research. On the one hand, numerous studies conclude that girls have higher social skills scores than boys; while, boys have higher levels of rejection compared to girls (Bandura et al., 2006) due to the contradictory and inconclusive results concerning the different impact of SEM-based interventions on boys and girls (Evangelio et al., 2018).

These positive results used in the social competence indicators probably favor adaptive interpersonal relationships (Eisenberg et al., 2006). In the same way, this improvement in social interaction among peers may be influenced by the intrapersonal and interpersonal emotional regulation strategies underlying the successful adaptation of adolescents to the requirements in social relationships (Mestre-Navas and Guil, 2012). Also, social acceptance is positively related to the behaviors that help to follow

the rules of collective games and be actively involved in adaptive interactions with their peers (Trianes et al., 1999).

Another possible explanation of these results could be the methodology used in the intervention, based on cooperative learning and encouraging the motivation of the participants (Casey, 2014; Metzler, 2017; González-Víllora et al., 2018; Gil-Madrona et al., 2019; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019) as well as, for the improvement of assertiveness, cooperation, autonomy and positive communication among peers (García-López and Gutiérrez, 2015). Also, the intervention aims to favor team sport and increase the responsibility of each participant in achieving a common goal (Méndez-Giménez et al., 2011, 2016; Kolovelonis and Goudas, 2018). Authors such as Washington et al. (2001) consider sport as a fundamental tool for social transformation, which will allow the promotion of cooperative learning through the assignment and distribution of responsibility roles (Siedentop et al., 2019) and will foster enthusiasm and enjoyment for an educational and cooperative sports practice (Iserbyt et al., 2016; Evangelio et al., 2018; Gil-Madrona et al., 2019; Pan et al., 2019).

Likewise, it is necessary to highlight that adolescence is a crucial stage for the development of socio-emotional competencies, since adolescents experience this stage with constant and typical maturational and emotional transitions of greater social difficulty (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017, 2019). In this sense, identifying, controlling and managing socio-emotional competences contribute to optimize teaching and learning processes, strengthening social interaction among adolescents (Del Prette and Del Prette, 2005; Ang and Penney, 2013; Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2017; Losada et al., 2017; Cañabate et al., 2018; Evangelio et al., 2018) and can favor an efficient evaluation of the educational practice made by the teachers (Lee et al., 2019).

Limitations and Future Directions

The current study had some limitations. First, it would have been necessary to carry out a follow-up evaluation of the intervention to analyze the long-term effect on the variables studied. Secondly, it would be necessary to use instruments completed by teachers or families that improve the assessment of the variables studied. Thirdly, it would be necessary to include a session analysis procedure in order to assess whether teachers followed the main principles of the model (formative evaluation) (Práxedes et al., 2019). Fourth, it is necessary to point out that the results obtained in Hypothesis 3 should be interpreted with great caution due to the sample size. However, studies that analyze this aspect should be carried out (Evangelio et al., 2018). Fifth, in terms of minimizing the effect of the experimenter, it would have been necessary for the posttest evaluation to use the balancing procedure of the members of the research team that administered the tests in each of the experimental conditions.

One of the most relevant contributions of the present study was the use of statistical analysis through ANCOVA, which evaluates the effectiveness of educational interventions as opposed to other statistical methods, such as the use of ANOVA, which evaluates changes or gains. These findings, through appropriate statistical procedures, could enrich research concerning SEM (e.g., Menéndez-Santurio and Fernández-Río, 2016; Kao, 2019; Luna et al., 2019; Pan et al., 2019).

Finally, it is necessary to highlight the difficulties in following the recommendations of the SEM in teaching sessions (Hastie and Casey, 2014; Siedentop et al., 2019). On the other hand, future lines of research could be: (1) to increase the sample and diversify the socio-cultural environment of adolescents; (2) assessment of the variables involved in the improvements obtained through these interventions, such as emotional regulation strategies (intrapersonal and interpersonal).

CONCLUSION

These significant results are likely due, as some research suggests, to the positive synergy among physical activity developed in positive environments (Mayfield et al., 2017; Shields et al., 2018; Escalié et al., 2019; Gil-Madrona et al., 2019) such as quality Physical Education (Association for Physical Education [afPE], 2015; United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2015; Shields et al., 2018) with affective and/or psychosocial factors (Kao, 2019; Pate and Dowda, 2019; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019). Said context will facilitate in students better pedagogical strategies (Girard et al., 2019) that make socio-emotional learning more positive (Brinkley et al., 2017; Mayfield et al., 2017; Cronin et al., 2018) and therefore, improve their educational experience (Kohl and Cook, 2013; Sierra-Díaz et al., 2019).

It is relevant to note that these findings suggest that when classes are developed with a quality Physical Education (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2015) using effective pedagogical models such as the SEM (Franco et al., 2017), students show high levels of positive emotions and social skills favoring peer interactions, clear evidence of cooperation, and human relationships that promote prosocial coexistence (Cañabate et al., 2018).

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All datasets generated for this study are included in the article/supplementary material.

ETHICS STATEMENT

Ethical review and approval was not required for the study on human participants in accordance with the local legislation and institutional requirements. Written informed consent to participate in this study was provided by the participants' legal guardian/next of kin.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

PL and JC conceived and designed the work. PL and JC were responsible for the design of the educational intervention, implemented by JG. PL, DR-R, LL, and JC collected the data

and drafted the manuscript. PL, JG, LL, and JC were responsible for the data analysis and interpretation. PL, JG, DR-R, and JC were responsible for critical revision of the manuscript. PL, JG, DR-R, LL, and JC approved the final version of the manuscript to be published. All authors made substantial contributions to the work.

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Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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12.3. Subjective well-being and psychosocial adjustment: examining the effects of an intervention based on the Sport Education Model on children

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Article

Subjective Well-Being and Psychosocial Adjustment: Examining the Effects of an Intervention Based on the Sport Education Model on Children

Pablo Luna ¹

¹ Department of Psychology, Faculty of Education, University of Castilla-La Mancha, 13071 Ciudad Real, Spain; pablo.luna@uclm.es (P.L.); Alba.Rodriguez11@alu.uclm.es (A.R.-D.)

² Department of Research and Diagnostic Methods in Education, Faculty of Education, International University of La Rioja (UNIR), 26006 Logroño, Spain; debora.rodrigo.ruiz@unir.net

* Correspondence: manueljavier.cejudo@uclm.es; Tel.: +34-926295300 (ext. 3215)

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Abstract: The current study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of an intervention based on the Sport Education model, compared to an intervention based on the traditional model of Direct Instruction in children. The intervention was carried out during school hours for 18 sessions of 50-min each. The sample was made up of 146 children aged 10–12 years ($M = 10.78$ years; $SD = 1.07$ years). Participants were randomly assigned to the experimental group ($n = 87$) and a control group ($n = 59$). A quasi-experimental design with repeated pretest and posttest evaluations with the control group was implemented. The Positive and Negative Affect Scale for children and adolescents (PANASN) was used to assess the affective component of subjective well-being. The Child and Adolescent Behavior Assessment System (BASC) was used to assess psychosocial adjustment. The results showed significant improvements in the affective component of subjective well-being and a reduction in anxiety in favor of the experimental group. Our current results show the methodological and practical efficacy of a Sport Education intervention.

Keywords: physical education; sport education model; children; subjective well-being; psychosocial adjustment

1. Introduction

Subjective well-being encompasses two dimensions [1], the affective dimension (positive and negative affect), and the cognitive dimension (satisfaction with life) [1,2]. Likewise, subjective well-being [2] has been identified with positive emotions and the absence of negative emotions [3]. It could also be considered as an interesting predictor of physical health, interpersonal relationships, and the correct bio-psychosocial development of individuals [4]. Some authors argue for the need and importance of improving subjective well-being in the population [5]. It is then appropriate that this psychological construct is becoming prominent in educational research, and its influence in social [6] and school contexts [7] is relevant.

On the other hand, McMahan et al. [8] argue that physical activity and sport practice are positively related to well-being and negatively related to psychosocial indicators such as anxiety. In this line of thought, subjective well-being, as a critical factor in the educational context, is related to variables such as psychosocial adjustment [9,10]. Rodríguez-Fernández et al. [11] interpret psychosocial adjustment as an association of school adjustment (or school commitment) and subjective well-being. The psychosocial adjustment construct refers to people's ability to adapt to the demands of the social context [12]. In recent years, a considerable increase in behavioral and adaptive problems has

been observed in children in the family and socio-school environment, being a cause of concern for educational institutions and society in general [11]. For this reason, it is essential to promote a positive psychosocial adjustment of the students in order to promote a healthy adaptation to the physical, psychological, social, and affective environments [13], while also becoming a beneficial factor for subjective well-being [14].

A primary objective within the educational context should be to promote active and participatory lifestyle habits [15]. Some studies establish a positive relationship between physical sport activity and some variables such as subjective well-being [16] and health and psychosocial adjustment [16,17]. Therefore, increasing healthy physical and sport practices among less active youth should be a crucial objective of community and school institutions and interventions to promote well-being [8].

Escalié et al. [18] emphasize the importance of balanced student development. The educational system needs to foster motivating and competent environments that are significant for a positive psychosocial adjustment and, therefore, for the integral development of the student's personality [19]. However, internalizing and externalizing adaptive behaviors in children are increasing, and the intervention processes are not always effective [20]. In this sense, our study is in line with educational programs that promote balanced student development and aim to improve the different dimensions of children's evolutionary development: the physical dimension, cognitive dimension, and affective-social dimension [21]. It is essential to promote motivating, participatory, and active interventions [22] driven by effective pedagogical models [23].

Several pedagogical models share these same characteristics [21]. Among the most suitable [23] is the Sport Education model (SEM) [24,25] articulated as a curricular teaching model within a quality physical education that favors an effective motor, affective, and social commitment in students [14]. The SEM is understood within a pedagogical framework based on practice, whose two main objectives are: (1) allowing students to develop authentic sport experiences, simulating the real aspects of the game, and adapting them to the educational context; (2) encouraging students to acquire competence, enthusiasm, and physical sport culture [26]. This is a constructivist and cooperative student-centered pedagogy [27] instead of repetitive sport experiences developed in physical education based on the traditional model of Direct Instruction focused on teachers [21,27,28].

The SEM has attracted considerable interest in recent years from researchers and educational professionals, with different systematic reviews published (e.g., [29,30]). In the review by Hastie et al. [29], improvements using the model (SEM) were confirmed in: physical fitness, knowledge, understanding, and technical-tactical ability. In other words, improvements included effective learning of the sport game; personal and social development; positive and attractive attitudes towards physical education (e.g., enthusiasm and enjoyment); and educational values (e.g., respect, affinity, fairness, fair play, etc.). Similarly, other more recent reviews confirm a positive impact of SEM on physical, social, and emotional development [31,32], ethical development [33], as well as in motivational indicators [34]. Furthermore, authors such as Sierra-Díaz et al. [35], in their meta-analysis, show improvements in motivation towards physical and sport activity, belonging and social responsibility, autonomy, and organization using the SEM.

A review of the scientific literature shows the scarcity of studies on educational interventions in physical education, based on the SEM, that evaluate the effects of the variables of the present investigation (subjective well-being and psychosocial adjustment). However, based on the scientific literature, it would be logical to think of possible positive effects of the SEM on these variables. The prior results suggest that, from an effective and efficient implementation of the model [36,37], they show positive effects: (a) at the physical-motor level [38,39]; (b) at the affective level [40]; and (c) at the social level [28,41,42]. Likewise, the SEM has been revealed in the school context as a teaching model capable of causing positive effects on socio-personal indicators (cooperation, empathy, self-discipline) [29] as well as on knowledge and physical [43,44] and sport performance indicators [45,46]. Likewise, various studies have shown that interventions based on the SEM show a positive impact on variables of psychosocial nature, such as motivational processes [34,47,48]; basic psychological needs [42,49,50];

cohesion skills and social relationships [28,41,42]; trait emotional intelligence dimensions and motivational mediators [40,51]; and a decrease in passive behaviors, aggressiveness, and violence, improving the relationship and social responsibility among the participants [52]. However, regarding the statistical analysis of the data, in most of these previous studies, the change/gain score through analysis of variance (ANOVA) (that is, posttest minus pretest) was used as a criterion group comparison. In this line, some authors such as Pérez-González et al. [53] recommend using covariance (ANCOVA) where the covariate is the baseline or pretest score, controlling for the possible effect of the pretest score on the results of the posttest. Criteria followed in the present study are in the same line as other authors (e.g., [28,40,41,52]).

Taking into account the above, the objective of the current study was to evaluate the impact of a SEM-based educational intervention in children, compared to an educational intervention based on the traditional model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) on: (1) subjective well-being in its affective dimension; and (2) psychosocial adjustment with the indicators of depression, anxiety, and social stress. The hypotheses focused on the fact that said educational intervention will improve the participants' affective dimension of the experimental group's subjective well-being (Hypothesis 1) and psychosocial adjustment (depression, anxiety, and social stress) (Hypothesis 2).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design

The study was carried out using a quasi-experimental design with repeated measurements (pretest and posttest) and a control group. Participants were randomly assigned to the experimental group (EG) and the control group (CG) through a cluster-randomized controlled trial.

2.2. Participants

The sample was obtained through a non-probabilistic incidental sampling method and was made up of 167 children, aged between 10 and 12 years (mean age (M) = 10.78; standard deviation (SD) = 1.07) (refer to Table 1).

Table 1. Sample Description.

		<i>n</i>	%
Age	10	79	54.11
	11	46	31.51
	12	21	14.38
Gender	Male	67	45.89
	Female	79	54.11

The inclusion criteria ($n = 146$) for the study were: (1) regular attendance at the school; (2) the written informed consent from the family (or legal guardian). The exclusion criteria ($n = 21$) were: (1) physical disability with official medical proof; (2) students with more than 30% truancy; (4) students sanctioned for disciplinary reasons by the educational center; (5) failure to obtain informed written consent from family (or legal guardian); (6) not completing the evaluation questionnaires adequately. The 146 participants who met and completed the study under research with the proposed criteria were randomly assigned to the EG through a cluster-randomized controlled trial ($n = 87$) or to the CG ($n = 59$). The differences in the two conditions (experimental group and control) were not significant by age ($\chi^2 = 1.17$; $p > 0.05$) nor by gender ($\chi^2 = 1.76$; $p > 0.05$). Participant flow is displayed below (refer to Figure 1).

Figure 1. Flow diagram: interventions based on the Sport Education model (SEM) (EG = experimental group) and traditional model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) (CG = control group).

2.3. Research Instruments

For this educational research, two measures have been used to evaluate the variables under study, with adequate psychometric parameters of reliability and validity.

Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) [54]. The PANAS version validated in Spanish by Sandín [55] for use with children and adolescents (PANASN) was used to evaluate subjective well-being in its affective dimension. It is made up of 20 items and presents a two-factor structure: positive affect (e.g., “I am interested in people or things”) and negative affect (e.g., “I am afraid”) with 10 items for each subscale. The measure consists of three response alternatives, described as «Never» (1), «Sometimes» (2), and «Often» (3). In the current study, the internal consistency calculated using Cronbach’s alpha was $\alpha = 0.81$ for positive affect and $\alpha = 0.78$ for negative affect.

Behavior Evaluation System for Children and Adolescents (BASC) [12]. The BASC-S2 questionnaire was used in its self-report version for children, made up of a total of 146 items, to evaluate the psychosocial adjustment variable. The BASC is a multidimensional instrument that measures numerous aspects of behavior and personality, including both positive (adaptive) and negative (clinical) dimensions. It consists of different adaptive subscales (which assess the positive fit) and clinical subscales (which assess mismatch), where participants rate statements that reflect their personal thoughts and feelings as true or false. In the current study, some clinical scales for evaluating negative or undesirable characteristics were used, such as: (a) depression: feelings of sadness, loneliness, and poor enjoyment of life, sometimes as a consequence of anxiety and stress processes (high scores indicate a problematic level of depression); (b) anxiety: presence of feelings of fear, obsessive thoughts,

and generally irrational worries (high scores mean that the individual suffers emotionally and may experience stress reactions that make them explode due to some triviality); and (c) social stress: levels of stress (e.g., tension, anxiety, etc.) that children suffer in interpersonal relationships (high scores indicate problems related to shyness, introversion, social anxiety, and irritability). The current research used an instrument with adequate and satisfactory psychometric properties for the socio-emotional evaluation of Spanish children and adolescents in the school and clinical context [12,56].

2.4. Procedure

The study was carried out in four periods. In the first one, the educational intervention program was designed. Second, the pretest evaluation was carried out (the timing for the tests was between 50–55 min) both in the experimental and control groups, regulating students' fatigue with scheduled breaks. In the third period, the educational intervention based on the SEM was applied to the experimental group, and the intervention based on the traditional model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) to the control group. In the last period, at the end of the interventions, the posttest evaluation was performed (the time of the tests was between 50–55 min) in both groups, with scheduled breaks to avoid student fatigue.

The research was developed following the ethical code of the University of Castilla-La Mancha (Spain) following the international guidelines on experiments with human subjects described in the Nuremberg Code and the Declaration of Helsinki. As it was a study located within an educational context, it was authorized by the management team, the school council, and the participating school faculty. Also, constant telephone contact was maintained with the management team of the center for supervision and coordination of the project. As an essential requirement to participate in the research project, written informed consents were delivered to the center and requested to be signed by a parent or legal guardian. Likewise, the requirements of ethical confidentiality were respected and guaranteed by the participants' voluntary and anonymous nature (ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association [APA], 2019; Personal Data Protection Law of the Research Ethics Committee on Human Beings, CEISH).

2.5. Interventions

2.5.1. Intervention Based on the Sport Education Model (SEM)

This is the educational intervention designed and implemented in the experimental group, applying an adaptation of the intervention published by Luna et al. [40]. It was developed according to the structure and essential characteristics of the SEM [25]: (1) season: a teaching unit of higher duration compared to the usual ones in physical education. A competitive plan is followed divided into three phases (preseason, competition, and final); (2) affiliation: grouping into teams with cooperative and socializing work maintained throughout the season (feeling of belonging to the group); (3) formal competition: as a relevant feature for practical experience and technical-tactical knowledge of physical and sport activity; an authentic sport experience is developed where relevant and real aspects of a formal sport competition are introduced to students; (4) data recording: process of evaluation and recording of sport performance, knowledge, and behavior; (5) final event: practical demonstration of the evolution in the advances and results obtained; (6) festivity: a festive atmosphere through symbolism (songs, hymns, etc.), rituals (shaking hands, group photos, etc.) and sport celebration (awards ceremony, trophies, self-built certificates, etc.). This structure is seen in Table 2. In this sense, the intervention followed the recommendations proposed by Hastie and Casey [37].

The intervention was developed with a sport education teaching unit (season) during school hours for two months (2–3 sessions per week for eight weeks) for a total of 18 sessions of 50 min of duration. The theoretical and practical sessions were applied with children for the subject of physical education, in an educational center within an urban environment and with a medium socio-cultural level. The teaching staff responsible for developing said intervention have nine years of teaching

experience and four years of applying sport education. Similarly, the educational experience was controlled and examined by external researchers, in line with Sinelnikov's suggestions [57]: (1) personal and virtual contact regarding the problems that arose during the research; (2) regular inspections of the school center; (3) weekly analysis and verification of the investigation process.

The season was implemented through a divided court or net team sport, called *Polskie ringo* [40,58]. This alternative sport was carried out with heterogeneous and permanent groups. Likewise, the game's distribution was developed in different sport spaces modified, reduced and adapted to the ages of the participating children, and divided into two equal parts by volleyball nets. It is a team game where players have to receive, grab, and throw a ring (that they have built by themselves) to the other field, and it must touch the ground to score. The use of an innovative sport, unknown to children, made it easier for all students alike to start with similar sport training and technical-tactical knowledge. Likewise, alternative and team sports such as *Polskie ringo* adapt effectively to the educational environment, being collaborative, motivating, socializing, and flexible with their different skills [58,59].

The participating students of each school year were randomly distributed in teams of five members, based on the principle of homogeneity in motor ability and gender [60]. Throughout the season, general roles common to all participants were assigned on the one hand: (a) player role, active and participatory; and (b) referee role: responsible for the registration of time, the minutes and reports of the game, in addition to complying with the regulations governing the game (with an emphasis on a fair play). The referee role constituted a rotating team responsibility role, carried out at least once by each team during the formal competition phase. This role played was key for the students, improving their understanding of fair play and fostering their empathy with the referee team when they acted as players. On the other hand, other specific roles of responsibility within the team were also assigned to the participants: (a) captain: team captain, whose functions are coordination and mediation; (b) audiovisual reporter: official journalist of the season, responsible for all the information and the management of a didactic blog, previously created by the faculty for the sport event; (c) coach: physical trainer whose function is to design, direct and control the previous and final physical sport warm-ups in the practical sessions, in addition to being responsible for the sport equipment used; and (d) celebration committee: organization event management involving all participants (e.g., organization of the final event).

In short, the application of active and cooperative methodologies, promoting the feeling of belonging to a team, together with positive reinforcements such as the final festival are crucial to explaining the motivation experienced by the students [34]. Likewise, it is essential to highlight, on the one hand, the guiding role of the teacher, and on the other hand, the active and autonomous role of the students, who act as the main protagonist of the teaching-learning process through their active participation and with the attribution of responsibility roles [25].

2.5.2. Intervention Based on the Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI)

This is the educational intervention designed and implemented in the control group, developed using a traditional teaching-learning methodology [21,28] following a traditional model of Direct Instruction [27,32,48].

The intervention (TM-DI) was carried out through a teaching unit, following the usual curricular programming of the physical education department of the participating school. Likewise, it was applied during school hours, with a duration similar to the previous intervention (refer to Table 2). The theoretical and practical sessions were developed for children in the class of physical education, in the same educational center. The teachers responsible for carrying out this intervention had 12 years of teaching experience and had no previous SEM experience.

The teaching unit was also implemented with the *Polskie ringo*, with no working groups or permanent teams or responsibility roles being developed. In the same way, more active and total control was generated by the teachers regarding: (1) presentation, introduction and explanation of

the tasks; (2) educational management; (3) methodological organization; (4) structure of activities; and (5) evaluation. Regarding the traditional model of Direct Instruction, the main characteristics were: (a) teaching-learning processes based, on the one hand, on a directive and instructive teaching function; and on the other hand, a passive function of students, determined by follow-up and search for these towards the teacher's instructions; (b) communicative processes characterized by a unidirectional and expository role of the teacher towards the students; (c) theoretical and practical sessions directed and structured solely by teachers, with rote and repetitive learning; (d) teaching style of homework assignment with the objective of learning specifically technical foundations of the sport chosen by the faculty (e.g., pass, throw, catch, etc.); (e) rhythm imposed by teachers, with an external, unidirectional, and outstanding teaching position regarding the group of students; (f) generalized teaching that did not individualize, using the sport equipment provided by the educational center (non-use of self-built materials by the students); (g) prescriptive feedback; and (h) situations of decontextualized activities and play, without experiencing authenticity, practiced individually or in pairs.

These traditional and control pedagogical approaches (TM-DI) are usually characterized by not focusing their intervention on children's autonomy and their intergroup interaction [48], reporting low levels of motivation [28], and a decrease in satisfaction and significant learning in physical education [21].

Table 2. Sequencing of session content in the educational interventions.

SESSION	Intervention with Sport Education Model (SEM) (Experimental Group)	Intervention with Traditional Model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) (Control Group)
1–2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of the SEM, the sport developed by teams (Polskie ringo), and the roles of responsibility, with digital and audiovisual support (ICT). • Explanation and delivery to the students of the teaching material that will be used (e.g., personalized folders with educational themes, party minutes, contingency contracts, party reports, etc.). • Organization and division of teams in a random way. The working groups were permanent with the assignment of team names following a didactic and transversal theme (e.g., characters from the Quixotic literature). • Designation and random distribution of responsibility roles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation and explanation by the teachers of the teaching unit implemented with the Polskie ringo. • General explanation of the educational intervention to students: objectives, content, and evaluation of the teaching unit. • Distribution of students individually, in pairs, and in small groups (no permanent working groups are established).
3–4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theoretical explanation with a digital whiteboard (audiovisual) of how the students will carry out the self-construction of the materials applied in the intervention (e.g., Polskie ringo rings, trophies, medals, etc.). • Practical explanation from the faculty on how to make such materials (e.g., Polskie ringo rings, certificates, etc.). • Construction by the students (self-construction) of the materials in a cooperative way (permanent groups/work teams). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instructional and direct introduction and explanation by teachers of: (a) the general and specific characteristics of the operation of the game (Polskie ringo); (b) the regulations of the Polskie ringo; and (c) sport equipment used and provided by the school. • Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and rote): displacement I-II.

Table 2. Cont.

5–8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial warm-up and final stretching in each session (directed by the students with the coach role). These tasks should be applied through reduced and modified physical activity and sport games. Practical team sessions to learn essential technical-tactical skills in the game of the Polskie ringo (displacement, coordination, pass, reception, serve, etc.). Functional application of roles in the different active, participative, and cooperative tasks carried out by the teams (e.g., captain: in the game of attack and defense; referee: in the rules of the game). Sessions ended with interactive assemblies for reflection and understanding (teacher-students and vice versa), to work, for example, positive feedback, active listening and error-learning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher-directed technical warm-up and stretching. Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and memoiristic): coordination I-II. Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and memoiristic): pass and reception I and II. Practical activities for developing individual and pair technical skills (repetitive and memoiristic): catch, serve, and throw. The teachers, during the development of the practical activities, gave instructions to the participants on how to correct and improve motor behavior.
9–15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training team sessions with friendly Polskie ringo games through educational competition (emphasis on fair play and respect for the opponent). Responsibility role training (e.g., referee). Development of authentic sport elements (e.g., match minutes; interviews; etc.). Formal competition: 5 vs. 5 league format (Round Robin). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Warm-ups and stretches directed by the teachers. Tactical skill practice session 1 vs. 1 Tactical skill practice session 2 vs. 2. Throw and reception activities between rotating pairs. Simultaneous Polskie ringo games by rotating pairs.
16–17	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formal competition (semifinal and final): 5 vs. 5 league format (Round Robin). Continuous and formative evaluation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual practical evaluation (technical-tactical learning acquired).
18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Celebration of the final event (organized by the role of celebration committee). Educational prizes, trophies, certificates, and medals were presented, made by the students themselves. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theoretical individual evaluation.

2.6. Data Analysis

First, the normality of the variables under study was calculated with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, all adjusting to the assumption of normality (analyses performed with a 95% confidence interval). Second, the reliability evidence was calculated with the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient (α). Third, to determine the impact of the pilot program, the following statistical analyses were carried out: (1) multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) with the total pretest scores of the variables under study, to confirm possible starting (initial) differences between the participants of the experimental group (EG) and control group (CG); (2) descriptive (M = mean; SD = standard deviation) and variance (ANOVA) analyses with each of the scores obtained for the instruments used during the pretest phase; (3) in order to show significant improvements between the experimental and control groups, a multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA) was calculated on the set of variables investigated; (4) descriptive analysis and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA: covariating the pretest scores) with the posttest scores; (5) finally, the effect size of the differences was analyzed according to the criteria set forth by Cohen [61] (low < 0.50 ; medium 0.50 – 0.79 ; big ≥ 0.80).

3. Results

The multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) results did not reveal statistically significant differences between the groups (EG and CG) before the intervention, Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.337$; $F_{(7,139)} = 0.419$; $p = 0.497$, with a low effect size ($d = 0.018$; $r = 0.03$).

3.1. Pretest Analysis

The pretest phase results (ANOVA) confirmed that before starting the educational intervention, there were no statistically significant differences in any of the variables under study (refer to Table 3).

Table 3. Mean, standard deviation, analysis of variance (ANOVA), analysis of covariance (ANCOVA), and effect size for the differences in the means (Cohen's d) in the variables under study (subjective well-being and psychosocial adjustment) in the experimental and control groups.

	PRETEST								POSTTEST						
	Experimental		Control		ANOVA			Experimental		Control		ANCOVA			
	M	SD	M	SD	F	p	d	M	SD	M	SD	F	p	d	
SWB ($n = 143$)															
Positive affect	22.26	5.00	22.71	4.15	6.811	0.146	0.10	26.48	2.93	24.61	3.23	5.088	0.018	0.61	
Negative affect	18.92	3.72	18.54	3.76	0.853	0.271	0.10	16.81	3.92	18.38	4.06	1.442	0.040	0.39	
PA ($n = 135$)															
Depression	47.57	10.41	47.40	10.51	1.045	0.445	0.02	47.02	11.57	47.46	11.35	0.573	0.258	0.04	
Anxiety	40.68	10.74	40.36	10.77	0.638	0.547	0.03	38.21	10.91	41.27	10.85	1.385	0.027	0.28	
Social Stress	47.75	10.75	47.83	10.59	1.127	0.489	0.01	47.10	10.46	48.36	10.57	0.982	0.875	0.12	

SWB = Subjective Well-Being; PA = Psychological Adjustment; M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation.

3.2. Posttest Analysis

The multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA) results in the pretest and posttest phases did not reveal statistically significant differences between the two groups (EG and CG), Wilks' Lambda, $\Lambda = 0.993$; $F_{(7,135)} = 1.528$; $p = 0.206$, with a low effect size ($d = 0.054$; $r = 0.06$).

3.2.1. Effects on Subjective Well-Being

The posttest phase results (ANCOVA) (refer to Table 3) showed a significant increase in positive affect with a medium effect size ($d = 0.61$) and a significant decrease in negative affect with a low effect size ($d = 0.39$) in favor of the EG (refer to Figure 2).

Figure 2. Significant effects of the intervention in the experimental group on the variables studied.

3.2.2. Effects on Psychosocial Adjustment

After performing ANCOVA in the posttest phase, the results confirmed a significant decrease in anxiety, in favor of the experimental group, with a low effect size ($d = 0.28$) (refer to Figure 2). However, no significant differences were confirmed in the other variables analyzed, depression, and social stress (refer to Table 3).

4. Discussion

In recent years, different authors [24,31,35] present the interest of research to continue examining the impact of healthy and active practices in the school context. In this sense, the present study evaluated the impact in children of an educational intervention based on the Sport Education model (SEM), compared to an educational intervention based on the traditional model of Direct Instruction (TM-DI) on: (1) subjective well-being in its affective dimension; and (2) psychosocial adjustment in its clinical indicators: depression, anxiety, and social stress.

The findings of this investigation confirmed statistically significant improvements in the variables under study, in favor of the experimental group (SEM) compared to the control group (TM-DI) in: (a) positive and negative affect; and (b) anxiety. However, no significant improvements were shown in the psychosocial adjustment indicators of depression and social stress.

First, the previous results confirmed that the intervention (SEM) stimulated in the experimental group a significant increase in positive affect and a significant decrease in negative affect. Therefore, Hypothesis 1 is confirmed. These results converge with other previous studies, which analyze the efficacy of SEM-based interventions on emotional or affective variables [24,31,32,40,51]. Likewise, the effect sizes, in positive affect and negative affect, are similar to those obtained in other previous investigations (e.g., [40]). A possible explanation for these results could be due to the synergy between subjective well-being with the development of physical, active, and healthy habits [14,16,62,63]. Similarly, the increase in physical inactivity in the school environment [14] makes beneficial the implementation of healthy and active interventions or programs [15,22] through cooperative and participatory methodologies focused on the student (active subject) [27] for the well-being of the student [40,64]. Standage and Gillison [65] establish that proactive teaching processes, applied correctly in physical education, can improve motivation and favor positive affectivity, and therefore, the quality of life in childhood. Essential elements of the SEM, such as a real and pedagogical vision of the structure and sport organization [25], competition, enthusiasm, and physical sport culture [26,29], the positive interdependence that arises with cooperative learning [52], the affiliation or feeling of belonging [46], the choice and assignment of responsibility roles [25], and motivational indicators [34,35,47,48] could significantly reinforce the affective sphere in children [66].

Second, the results showed some improvements in psychosocial adjustment, specifically a significant decrease in anxiety, although with a low effect size. In this way, Hypothesis 2 was partially confirmed, since no significant decreases in depression and social anxiety were found. Active participation in educational intervention is likely to be positively related to well-being and negatively related to anxiety. In line with the results of some authors [8], it is concluded that participation in sport activities independently contributed to improving subjective well-being and reducing anxiety levels.

A proper analysis of psychosocial adjustment implies being able to associate this construct with other psychological variables [67] such as subjective well-being [10,11], and being able to evaluate it effectively [12,68]. The influence of psychosocial adjustment in the educational environment is relevant, particularly concerning the development of adaptive behaviors (positive adjustment) and maladjustment (mismatch) [11,12]. A positive adjustment in the students' behavior or personality would imply an optimal school climate in its different physical, psychological, social, and affective dimensions [13,19]. In this sense, it would be positive to promote competent pedagogical models [23] or adequate educational interventions [22], such as the SEM [21,36]. Similarly, the positive impact of the SEM at the social (e.g., [28,41]) and emotional (e.g., [40,51]) levels, as well as its beneficial and

significant effects on social relationships and against attitudes of violence and aggressiveness [52] could lead to reinforcement in the educational field, for the development of adaptive strategies or resources, being able to effectively face the mismatch or negative psychosocial characteristics [11].

Therefore, it would be reasonable to think that essential elements of the model such as the roles of responsibilities, cooperative learning, the formal competition, and the final event, where the students were able to self-manage their learning, together with the creative, motivating, cooperative, and celebratory nature of the SEM could have influenced the participating children to improve their academic achievement in physical education. The enriching elements of the SEM included in the intervention program may also have contributed to these results, such as the self-construction of didactic materials, the interdisciplinarity of the program, and teaching with projects, since their pedagogical effectiveness has been previously verified in other studies [50,69,70].

Despite these results, we must point out that the present research shows the following limitations: (1) the number of participants was limited and a convenience sampling was used, which may limit the generalization of the results to other populations; (2) the variables under study were evaluated with self-reports. It would be advisable to support these results with other hetero-informed instruments; (3) it would be advisable to carry out a follow-up evaluation; (4) it would be necessary to evaluate the dynamics generated in the development of the sessions (formative evaluation) [71]; (5) difficulties in following some recommendations to start the SEM during the teaching sessions. The organization and initial grouping of the teams, follow-up of the participating students due to illness or injury, weather, facilities, equipment, and/or teacher availability are some of the aspects that could hinder the follow-up and development of the sessions [37].

On the other hand, future lines of research could be directed towards: (1) expanding the sample and diversifying educational contexts, in addition to the socio-cultural environment of the participants; (2) evaluation of the effects of educational intervention on other psychological (e.g., interpersonal relationships, self-esteem, or self-concept) or clinical (e.g., cortisol) variables.

5. Conclusions

Sierra-Díaz et al. [35] establish that physical education could be considered a relevant subject to promote wellness habits associated with a healthy lifestyle during sport and other types of active activities. Likewise, regarding the educational context, physical education effectively promotes the holistic development of students [31] due to its active, practical, transversal, and motivating frameworks that make it unique compared to other classes.

Current educational demands emphasize the need for a methodological renewal in the evolution of traditional physical education toward a more current and motivating methodological framework driven by quality physical education [14]. The current results show the benefits and efficacy in children of an intervention in physical education to improve subjective well-being, psychosocial adjustment, and school results in this subject. These findings have interesting pedagogical and empirical implications for both teachers and students. For teachers, the SEM-based intervention constitutes an effective, efficient, and motivating tool with proven positive results in physical education classes. For students, the intervention could promote well-being or quality of life, improve their socio-scholastic adaptation, and increase their autonomy, promoting positive and comprehensive development of their personalities.

In conclusion, the application of this type of intervention in the school environment is recommended for children due to the evident physical, affective, psychosocial, and academic benefits, in line with other investigations [24,31]. Furthermore, these conclusions offer empirical support for the pedagogical model of SEM and have interesting educational implications that promote the effectiveness of innovative and motivating teaching approaches.

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13. OTRAS CONTRIBUCIONES CIENTÍFICAS

“La libertad es uno de los más preciosos dones que a los hombres dieron los cielos; con ella no pueden igualarse los tesoros que encierran la tierra y el mar: por la libertad, así como por la honra, se puede y debe aventurar la vida”

(Don Quijote de la Mancha)

13.1. Capítulos de libro

- **Referencia:** Luna, P., Rodríguez-Donaire, A., & Cejudo, J. (2019). Recreos activos, convivencia escolar y juegos participativos: impacto de una intervención basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva sobre bienestar subjetivo, agresividad y habilidades sociales en Educación Primaria. En J. A. Marín, G. Gómez, M. Ramos, & M. N. Campos (Eds.), *Inclusión, Tecnología y Sociedad: Investigación e innovación en educación* (pp. 2071-2084). Dykinson. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=7415154>

Factor de calidad Scholarly Publishers Indicators (SPI) e Índice de Calidad de Editoriales según los Expertos (ICEE):

- *Psicología*: 0.190; posición 15/77 (**Q1**).
 - *Educación*: 0.954; posición 16/94 (**Q1**).
- **Referencia:** Luna, P., Rodríguez-Donaire, A., & Cejudo, J. (2021). ¿Es posible mejorar la autoeficacia cinestésica y el rendimiento académico mediante una intervención basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva? En I. Aznar, J. A. López, M. P. Cáceres, C. De Barros, & F. J. Hinojo (Eds.), *Desempeño docente y formación en competencia digital en la era SARS COV 2* (pp. 654-667). Dykinson. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/libro?codigo=793078>

Factor de calidad Scholarly Publishers Indicators (SPI) e Índice de Calidad de Editoriales según los Expertos (ICEE):

- *Psicología*: 0.190; posición 15/77 (**Q1**).
- *Educación*: 0.954; posición 16/94 (**Q1**).

13.2. Ponencias y/o comunicaciones científicas en congresos internacionales

- Título: *Psychological well-being and academic performance: effects in primary education of a program based on the Sport Education model* (comunicación oral).

- Lugar: Setúbal (Portugal).
 - Fecha: 2018.
 - Entidad organizadora: 6th International Congress of Educational Sciences and Development; Universidade do Minho.
 - Carácter del congreso: Internacional.
-
- Título: *Psychosocial adjustment and psychological well-being: effects of an educational program based on the Sport Education model in a school for at-risk students* (comunicación oral).
 - Lugar: Setúbal (Portugal).
 - Fecha: 2018.
 - Entidad organizadora: 6th International Congress of Educational Sciences and Development; Universidade do Minho.
 - Carácter del congreso: Internacional.
-
- Título: Improving subjective well-being and trait emotional intelligence in the educational context by applying a didactic intervention based on the Sport Education model (comunicación oral).
 - Lugar: Oporto (Portugal).
 - Fecha: 2019.
 - Entidad organizadora: 8th International Congress on Education and Learning.
 - Carácter del congreso: Internacional.
-
- Título: *“¿Es posible mejorar la autoeficacia cinestésica y el rendimiento académico mediante una intervención basada en el modelo de Educación Deportiva?”* (comunicación oral).
 - Lugar: Coimbra (Portugal).
 - Fecha: 2020.
 - Entidad organizadora: XIV International Conference on Education and Innovation.
 - Carácter del congreso: Internacional.

13.3. Ponencias y/o comunicaciones científicas en congresos nacionales

- Título: *An innovative proposal from the model of Sports Education in primary education* (comunicación oral).
 - Lugar: Sevilla (España).
 - Fecha: 2017.
 - Entidad organizadora: ISSP 14th World Congress Sevilla.
 - Carácter del congreso: Nacional.
- Título: *Resultados preliminares del impacto de un programa basado en el modelo de Educación Deportiva sobre el bienestar psicológico en el alumnado de Educación Primaria* (comunicación oral).
 - Lugar: Santander (España).
 - Fecha: 2017.
 - Entidad organizadora: 5th International Congress of Educational Sciences and Development.
 - Carácter del congreso: Nacional.
- Título: *Sport Education model impact on psychological well-being in elementary education students* (póster).
 - Lugar: Ciudad Real (España).
 - Fecha: 2019.
 - Entidad organizadora: IV Jornadas de divulgación de TFG de Excelencia; Facultad de Educación de Ciudad Real; Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha (UCLM).
 - Carácter del congreso: Nacional.
- Título: *Impacto del modelo de Educación Deportiva sobre inteligencia emocional rasgo y bienestar subjetivo en el contexto educativo* (premio extraordinario al mejor póster de investigación en el Programa de Doctorado de Educación).
 - Lugar: Ciudad Real (España).
 - Fecha: 2019.

- Entidad organizadora: IX Jornadas Doctorales de la Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha (UCLM).
 - Carácter del congreso: Nacional.

- Título: *Mejora de la adaptación socio-escolar mediante un programa educativo basado en Educación Deportiva: “programa Deporte Cervantino”* (comunicación oral).
 - Lugar: Oviedo (España).
 - Fecha: 2019.
 - Entidad organizadora: 5th International Congress of Clinical and Health Psychology on Children and Adolescents.
 - Carácter del congreso: Nacional.

- Título: *Impacto de un programa basado en el modelo de Educación Deportiva sobre el bienestar subjetivo en niños/as* (simposio).
 - Lugar: Oviedo (España).
 - Fecha: 2019.
 - Entidad organizadora: 5th International Congress of Clinical and Health Psychology on Children and Adolescents.
 - Carácter del congreso: Nacional.

- Título: *Impacto en adolescentes del modelo de Educación Deportiva sobre inteligencia emocional rasgo* (póster).
 - Lugar: Oviedo (España).
 - Fecha: 2019.
 - Entidad organizadora: 5th International Congress of Clinical and Health Psychology on Children and Adolescents.
 - Carácter del congreso: Nacional.

- Título: *Recreos activos, convivencia escolar y juegos participativos: impacto de una intervención basada en el modelo de educación deportiva sobre bienestar subjetivo, agresividad y habilidades sociales en educación primaria* (comunicación oral).
 - Lugar: Granada (España).

- Fecha: 2019.
- Entidad organizadora: XIII Congreso Internacional de Educación e Innovación; Universidad de Granada.
- Carácter del congreso: Nacional.

13.4. Formación y/o contribuciones en cursos especializados

- Título: *Programas basados en el modelo de Educación deportiva: técnicas de resolución de conflictos y de modificación de conductas para la mejora de la convivencia escolar* (Seminario formativo).
 - Ponente/formador: Pablo Luna Nogales y Javier Cejudo Prado.
 - Lugar: Castilla-La Mancha (España).
 - Fecha: 2020.
 - Entidad organizadora: Fundación CEPAIM (UCLM).
- Título: *Modelo de Educación Deportiva en Educación Secundaria Obligatoria: desarrollo de competencias socioemocionales en Educación Secundaria* (Curso formativo).
 - Ponente/formador: Pablo Luna Nogales y Javier Cejudo Prado.
 - Lugar: Castilla-La Mancha (España).
 - Fecha: 2021.
 - Entidad organizadora: Servicio Planificación Ciudad Real; Delegación Provincial de la Consejería de Educación, Cultura y Deporte (unidad de formación e innovación).
- Título: *Modelo de Educación Deportiva en Educación Primaria: educando la inteligencia emocional desde el currículum* (Curso formativo).
 - Ponente/formador: Pablo Luna Nogales y Javier Cejudo Prado.
 - Lugar: Castilla-La Mancha (España).
 - Fecha: 2021.
 - Entidad organizadora: Servicio Planificación Ciudad Real; Delegación Provincial de la Consejería de Educación, Cultura y Deporte (unidad de formación e innovación).

ANEXOS

*“El que lee mucho y anda mucho, ve mucho y sabe mucho”
(Don Quijote de la Mancha)*

Anexo 1. KIDSCREEN-10. Cuestionario de calidad de vida para la población infantil y adolescente (Aymerich et al., 2005).

KIDSCREEN-10

Cuando pienses en tu respuesta, por favor intenta **recordar la última semana, es decir, los últimos siete días.**

1. ¿Te has sentido bien y en forma?	Nada	Un poco	Moderadamente	Mucho	Muchísimo
2. ¿Te has sentido lleno/a de energía?	Nunca	Casi nunca	Algunas veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
3. ¿Te has sentido triste?	Nunca	Casi nunca	Algunas veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
4. ¿Te has sentido solo/a?	Nunca	Casi nunca	Algunas veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
5. ¿Has tenido suficiente tiempo para ti?	Nunca	Casi nunca	Algunas veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
6. ¿Has podido hacer las cosas que querías en tu tiempo libre?	Nunca	Casi nunca	Algunas veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
7. ¿Tus padres te han tratado de forma justa?	Nunca	Casi nunca	Algunas veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
8. ¿Te has divertido con tus amigos/as?	Nunca	Casi nunca	Algunas veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
9. ¿Te ha ido bien en la escuela?	Nada	Un poco	Moderadamente	Mucho	Muchísimo
10. ¿Has podido poner atención?	Nunca	Casi nunca	Algunas veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
En general, ¿cómo dirías que es tu salud?	Excelente	Muy buena	Buena	Regular	Mala

Anexo 2. Escalas PANAS de afecto positivo y negativo para niños y adolescentes (PANASN) (Sandín, 2003).

ANEXO I. CUESTIONARIO PANASN

Cuestionario PANAS para niños y adolescentes (PANASN)

B. Sandín

NOMBRE EDAD SEXO: Chico Chica

Instrucciones: A continuación se indican algunas frases que los chicos y chicas utilizan para describirse a sí mismos. Lee detenidamente cada frase y marca cada una de ellas con una «X» en el espacio correspondiente a una de las tres alternativas (**Nunca**, **A veces** o **Muchas veces**). No existen contestaciones buenas ni malas. Recuerda que tienes que señalar la alternativa que mejor se ajuste a tu forma de ser.

NUNCA: si nunca o casi nunca sientes o te comportas de la manera que dice la frase

A VECES: si en algunas ocasiones sientes o te comportas como indica la frase

MUCHAS VECES: si la mayor parte del tiempo sientes o te comportas como dice la frase

- | | | | |
|---|--------------------------------|----------------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| 1. Me intereso por la gente o las cosas | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 2. Me siento tenso/a, agobiado/a, con sensación de estrés | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 3. Soy una persona animada, suelo emocionarme | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 4. Me siento disgustado/a o molesto/a | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 5. Siento que tengo vitalidad o energía | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 6. Me siento culpable | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 7. Soy un/a chico/a asustadizo/a | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 8. Estoy enfadado/a o furioso/a | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 9. Me entusiasmo (por cosas, personas, etc.) | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 10. Me siento orgulloso/a (de algo), satisfecho/a | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 11. Tengo mal humor (me altero o irrito) | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 12. Soy un/a chico/a despierto/a, «despabilado/a» | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 13. Soy vergonzoso/a | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 14. Me siento inspirado/a | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 15. Me siento nervioso/a | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 16. Soy un/a chico/a decidido/a | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 17. Soy una persona atenta, esmerada | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 18. Siento sensaciones corporales de estar intranquilo/a o preocupado/a | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 19. Soy un/a chico/a activo/a | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |
| 20. Siento miedo | <input type="checkbox"/> NUNCA | <input type="checkbox"/> A VECES | <input type="checkbox"/> MUCHAS VECES |

Subescalas: Afecto positivo (AP, items 1, 3, 5, 9, 10, 12, 14, 16, 17, 19); Afecto negativo (AN, items 2, 4, 6, 7, 8, 11, 13, 15, 18, 20). Tomado de Sandín (1997, p. 19) (reproducido con permiso).

Anexo 3. Cuestionario de inteligencia emocional rasgo para adolescentes (TEIQue-ASF) (Ferrando et al., 2011).

TEIQue-ASF

Translation by
 Mercedes Ferrando (Research Fellow, Murcia University) mferran@um.es
 Blanca Sema (PhD Student, Murcia University) bsg@alu.um.es

Nombre y Apellidos _____ Hombre Mujer

Fecha de Nacimiento: ___/___/___ Edad: _____ Fecha de hoy: ___/___/___

Centro Educativo: _____ Curso: _____

Instrucciones:

- Por favor, responde rodeando con un círculo el número que mejor se ajuste a tu grado de acuerdo o desacuerdo con cada una de las frases siguientes.
- Si estás muy en desacuerdo con la frase, rodea el número más cercano al 1.
- Si estás muy de acuerdo con la frase, rodea el número cercano al 7.
- Si dudas de si estás de acuerdo o en desacuerdo, rodea el número cercano a 4.
- Trabaja rápido, pero cuidadosamente. No hay respuestas correctas ni incorrectas.

		TOTALMENTE DESACUERDO			TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO			
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1.	Me resulta fácil hablar de mis sentimientos con otras personas	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2.	A menudo, me resulta difícil ver las cosas desde el punto de vista del otro	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3.	Soy una persona con alta motivación	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4.	Me cuesta controlar mis sentimientos	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
5.	Mi vida no es agradable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6.	Me llevo bien con mis compañeros de clase	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7.	A menudo, cambio de opinión	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8.	Me resulta difícil saber con exactitud qué emoción estoy sintiendo	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9.	Me gusta mi apariencia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
10.	Me resulta difícil defender mis derechos	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
11.	Cuando quiero, puedo hacer que los otros se sientan bien	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
12.	A veces, pienso que toda mi vida va a ser un "desastre"	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
13.	A veces, los otros se quejan de que los trato mal	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
14.	Es difícil para mí, afrontar los cambios en mi vida	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
15.	Soy capaz de controlar el stress (la ansiedad, el nerviosismo, etc.)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
16.	Me cuesta mostrar a las personas cercanas que me preocupo por ellas	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
17.	Soy capaz de "ponerme en el lugar del otro" y sentir sus emociones	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
18.	Me cuesta mantenerme motivado	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
19.	Cuando quiero, puedo controlar mi enfado	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
20.	Soy feliz con mi vida	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
21.	Me veo como un buen negociador	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
22.	Algunas veces, me implico en cosas de las que más tarde me arrepiento	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
23.	Presto mucha atención a mis sentimientos	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
24.	Me siento bien conmigo mismo	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
25.	Tiendo a rectificar, incluso sabiendo que tengo razón	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
26.	Soy incapaz de cambiar los sentimientos de los demás	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
27.	Pienso que la cosas me irán bien en la vida	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
28.	Algunas veces, me hubiera gustado tener una mejor relación con mis padres	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
29.	Soy capaz de adaptarme bien a ambientes nuevos	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
30.	Trato de controlar mis pensamientos y no preocuparme demasiado sobre las cosas	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Claves de puntuación:

Invertir la puntuación de los siguientes ítems, y entonces sumar las puntuaciones en cada ítem para obtener el total.

- Ítem 2 “A menudo, me resulta difícil ver las cosas desde el punto de vista del otro”
- Ítem 4 “Me cuesta controlar mis sentimientos”
- Ítem 5 “Mi vida no es agradable”
- Ítem 7 “A menudo, cambio de opinión”
- Ítem 8 “Me resulta difícil saber con exactitud qué emoción estoy sintiendo”
- Ítem 10 “Me resulta difícil defender mis derechos”
- Ítem 12 “A veces, pienso que toda mi vida va a ser un “desastre””
- Ítem 13 “A veces, los otros se quejan de que los trato mal”
- Ítem 14 “Es difícil para mí, afrontar los cambios en mi vida”
- Ítem 16 “Me cuesta mostrar a las personas cercanas que me preocupo por ellas”
- Ítem 18 “Me cuesta mantenerme motivado”
- Ítem 22 “Algunas veces, me implico en cosas de las que más tarde me arrepiento”
- Ítem 25 “Tiendo a rectificar, incluso sabiendo que tengo razón”
- Ítem 26 “Soy incapaz de cambiar los sentimientos de los demás”
- Ítem 28” Algunas veces, me hubiera gustado tener una mejor relación con mis padres”

El *Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire-Adolescent Short Form* (TEIQue-ASF) es una versión simplificada en términos de sintaxis y formulación de la forma abreviada para adultos del TEIQue. La versión ASF está diseñada para medir el rasgo *global* de inteligencia emocional y comprende 30 afirmaciones cortas, dos por cada una de las 15 facetas del rasgo de inteligencia emocional. La fiabilidad de consistencia interna de la escala usualmente está por encima de .80 y nunca ha sido inferior a .70 en ningún estudio. La forma ha sido usada con éxito con niños de 11 años.

Referencia del TEIQue-ASF: Petrides, K. V., Sangareau, Y., Furnham, A., & Frederickson, N. (2007). Trait emotional intelligence and children's peer relations at school. *Social Development, 15*, 537-547

Por favor, nótese que cualquier uso comercial de este producto esta estrictamente prohibido.

Para más información acerca del programa de investigación sobre la inteligencia emocional como rasgo visite la página: <http://www.psychometriclab.com/>

M(SD)=149.00(20.60)

[Adaptación española: Ferrando et al., 2011, *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment*; N=290, age=12 years)

M(SD)=4.62(.63) ; <4.13 dangerous

[Mikolajczak, Petrides et al., 2009, *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*; N=490, age=17 years)

Anexo 4. Escala de ansiedad social para adolescentes (SAS-A) (La Greca & López, 1998; Olivares et al., 2005).

El cuestionario tiene 22 preguntas. Por favor, contéstelas todas indicando en que medida la afirmación "es cierta" para usted, siendo las respuestas extremas "nunca es cierta" y "siempre es cierta".

		Nunca		Siempre		
◀ ▲ ▼ ▶						
1	Me preocupa hacer algo que nunca he hecho delante de los demás.	<input type="radio"/>				
2	Me gusta practicar deportes.	<input type="radio"/>				
3	Me preocupa que me tomen el pelo.	<input type="radio"/>				
4	Me da vergüenza estar rodeado de personas que no conozco.	<input type="radio"/>				
5	Sólo hablo con personas que conozco bien.	<input type="radio"/>				
6	Creo que mis compañeros hablan de mí a mis espaldas.	<input type="radio"/>				
7	Me gusta pasear por el campo.	<input type="radio"/>				
8	Me preocupa lo que los demás piensen de mí.	<input type="radio"/>				
9	Pienso que no gustaré a los demás.	<input type="radio"/>				
10	Me pongo nervioso cuando hablo con gente de mi edad que no conozco bien.	<input type="radio"/>				
11	Mirar la televisión me relaja.	<input type="radio"/>				
12	Me preocupa lo que los demás digan de mí.	<input type="radio"/>				
13	Me pongo nervioso cuando me presentan a personas desconocidas.	<input type="radio"/>				
14	Me preocupa no gustar a los demás.	<input type="radio"/>				
15	Me quedo callado cuando estoy con un grupo de personas.	<input type="radio"/>				
16	Escucho música siempre que tengo oportunidad.	<input type="radio"/>				
17	Creo que los demás se burlan de mí.	<input type="radio"/>				
18	Si en un debate doy mi opinión, me preocupa no gustar a los demás.	<input type="radio"/>				
19	Me da miedo pedir a los demás que hagan cosas conmigo ya que podrían decirme que no.	<input type="radio"/>				
20	Me pongo nervioso cuando estoy con cierta gente.	<input type="radio"/>				
21	Siento vergüenza incluso cuando estoy con gente que conozco bien.	<input type="radio"/>				
22	Me cuesta trabajo pedir a los demás que hagan cosas conmigo.	<input type="radio"/>				

Anexo 5. Cuestionario multidimensional de competencia social para adolescentes (AMSC-Q) (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2019).

A continuación, encontrarás una serie de preguntas relativas a tu forma de ser y a las relaciones que mantienes con los demás. Por favor, responde todas las preguntas teniendo en cuenta que:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Totalmente falso	Bastante falso	Algo falso	Ni falso ni verdadero	Algo verdadero	Bastante verdadero	Totalmente verdadero
1. Cuando me enfrente a una situación estresante, intento pensar en ella de un modo que me ayude a mantener la calma	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2. Cuando quiero incrementar mis emociones positivas, cambio mi manera de pensar sobre la situación	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3. Controlo mis emociones cambiando mi forma de pensar sobre la situación en la que me encuentro	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4. Cuando quiero reducir mis emociones negativas, cambio mi manera de pensar sobre la situación	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
5. Mis compañeros o amigos acuden a mi cuando tienen algún problema	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6. Mis compañeros o amigos me ayudan cuando los necesito	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7. Mis compañeros se interesan por mi	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8. Mis compañeros se sienten a gusto trabajando conmigo	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9. Mis compañeros o amigos cuentan conmigo cuando hay que organizar alguna actividad	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
10. Me uno a las actividades que realizan los demás	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
11. Caigo bien entre mis compañeros	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
12. Siento que tengo amigos	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
13. Si un compañero está muy agobiado y no le da tiempo a terminar el trabajo, lo ayudo	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
14. Reacciono para defender a un compañero del que hacen bromas o se meten con él/ella	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
15. Cuando un compañero o amigo está triste, lo consuelo para que se sienta mejor	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
16. Si veo que un compañero se siente solo, lo ayudo a integrarse a mi grupo de amigos	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
17. Ayudo a los compañeros que tienen algún problema físico (pierna escayolada, silla de ruedas, etc.) en su día a día	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
18. En las relaciones con mis amigos y compañeros de clase, siento que hago las cosas bien (me siento eficaz)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
19. En las relaciones con mis profesores, siento que hago las cosas bien (me siento eficaz)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
20. En las relaciones con mis familiares, siento que hago las cosas bien (me siento eficaz)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
21. En las relaciones con otros adultos o personas mayores, siento que hago las cosas bien (me siento eficaz)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
22. Dejo trabajar a los demás sin molestarlos	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
23. Pido la palabra y espero turno para hablar	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
24. Cumpló las normas	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
25. Respeto la opinión de los demás aunque no la comparto	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
26. Cuido el material y las instalaciones del centro	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Anexo 6. Cuestionario sociométrico Guess Who 4 (GW4) (Losada et al., 2017).

SOCIOGRAMA Guess Who 4 (GW4)
(Alumnado)

Nombre del Alumno/a:	
Curso y grupo del alumno:	
Nombre y fecha de la sesión:	

1. **¿Quiénes son los chicos o chicas de tu clase que más se asemejan a la siguiente descripción?**
“Es elegido por los demás como el/la líder. A los demás les gusta que él o ella esté al mando o sea responsable del grupo”.

2. **¿Quiénes son los chicos o chicas de tu clase que más se asemejan a la siguiente descripción?**
“Esta persona crea problemas o disputas. Se burla de los demás, se mete o se pelea con ellos/as.”

"Esta persona es realmente buena para formar parte de tu grupo, porque es agradable y cooperador/a. Se integra en el grupo, comparte, y le cede a cada uno/a su turno.

4. **¿Quiénes son los chicos o chicas de tu clase que más se asemejan a la siguiente descripción?**

"Esta persona tiene un buen sentido del humor. Hace bromas graciosas y agradables, se ríe a menudo y cae bien a la gente"

¡MUCHAS GRACIAS POR TU COLABORACIÓN!

Anexo 7. Sistema de evaluación de la conducta para niños y adolescentes (BASC-S2) (Reynolds & Kamphaus, 2004).

BASC

S-2

Antes de leer las instrucciones rellena los siguientes datos:

NOMBRE Y APELLIDOS: _____ SEXO: VARDN MUJER

FECHA: / / FECHA NACIMIENTO: / /

CENTRO: _____ CURSO: _____

OTROS DATOS: _____

INSTRUCCIONES

A continuación encontrarás una serie de frases sobre cómo piensas, sienten y se comportan algunos niños y niñas. Nos gustaría saber cuáles son las que te ocurren a ti.

Lee cada frase detenidamente. Si lo que se dice en cada una de ellas te ocurre a ti, marca con un aspa (X) el cuadrado que tiene encima la V de verdadero. Si lo que se dice no te ocurre a ti, marca con un aspa el círculo que tiene encima la F de Falso.

Mira el siguiente ejemplo:

E1

Me gustan los perros

V
 F

La persona ha respondido que le gustan los perros, si no le gustaran habria marcado el círculo. Si te equivocas rellena completamente la respuesta anterior y marca con un aspa la que consideres buena. Mira el siguiente ejemplo:

E1

Me gustan los perros

V
 F

Responde siempre lo que más se ajuste a tu modo de ser. Incluso cuando tengas dudas y no lo tengas claro, responde siempre lo que **MÁS** se ajuste.

Tus respuestas ayudarán a conocerte mejor. Lo importante es que respondas lo que te pasa a ti. No existen respuestas buenas o malas, todas sirven.

RECUERDA: Sé sincero y contesta a todas las frases, sin saltarte ninguna.

SI TIENES ALGUNA DUDA PREGUNTA A LA PERSONA QUE TE HA ENTREGADO ESTE EJEMPLAR

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Anexo 8. Formulario de consentimiento informado para la participación en la investigación educativa.

<p>Fde Facultad de Educación CIUDAD REAL</p>	
<p><u>CONSENTIMIENTO INFORMADO</u></p>	
<p>DECLARACIÓN DEL PADRE/MADRE O TUTOR/A DEL PARTICIPANTE</p>	
<p>Nos dirigimos a ustedes para informarles sobre el proyecto educativo en Educación Deportiva que se va a desarrollar en el centro escolar. Forma parte de una investigación educativa desarrollada por el doctorando Pablo Luna Nogales, personal docente e investigador en el Departamento de Psicología de la Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha (UCLM) en la Facultad de Educación de Ciudad Real, dirigida y supervisada por el Dr. Javier Cejudo Prado, para la implementación de un programa activo basado en el Modelo de Educación Deportiva (MED) durante las horas lectivas de la asignatura de Educación Física. Se realizará una recogida de información a través de unos cuestionarios anónimos y confidenciales que realizará el alumnado en el aula, en horario lectivo, según disponga el Equipo Directivo del centro escolar participante.</p>	
<p>Toda la información obtenida en este estudio será tratada de <u>forma anónima, confidencial y segura</u>, de acuerdo con lo establecido en Reglamento General de Protección de Datos (RGPD) (2018) y consideraciones éticas de la American Psychological Association [APA], 2019).</p>	
<p>Para autorizar la participación de su hijo/a en el estudio de investigación, les rogamos que rellene y entregue el impreso o consentimiento escrito e informado (adjuntado al personal docente encargado).</p>	
<p>Gracias por su colaboración y reciba un cordial saludo. Si desean más información sobre el estudio o tratamiento de los datos, pueden contactar con los responsables de la investigación a través de los correos electrónicos:</p>	
<p>D. Javier Cejudo: ManuelJavier.Cejudo@uclm.es D. Pablo Luna: Pablo.Luna@uclm.es</p>	
<p>✂-----</p>	
<p>Participación en el estudio de investigación educativa desarrollada en el Departamento de Psicología, por la Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha (UCLM) en la Facultad de Educación de Ciudad Real.</p>	
<p>D/Dª</p>	
<p>como padre/madre o tutor/a legal del/a alumno/a.....</p>	
<p>de curso, da su consentimiento para la participación de su hijo/a en el estudio.</p>	
<p>En Ciudad Real, a</p>	
<p>Firma:</p>	

AGRADECIMIENTOS

“Tanto vales cuanto tienes, y tanto tienes cuanto vales. Dos linajes solos hay en el mundo, como decía una abuela mía, que son el tener y el no tener”

(Don quijote de la Mancha)

«... yo quedaré satisfecho y ufano de haber sido el primero que gozó el fruto de sus escritos enteramente, como deseaba, pues no ha sido otro mi deseo que poner en aborrecimiento de los hombres las fingidas y disparatadas historias de los libros de caballerías, que por las de mi verdadero don Quijote, van ya tropezando, y han de caer del todo, sin duda alguna. vale.»

«Don Quijote de la Mancha»

(Miguel de Cervantes Saavedra, 1605)

Es probable que esta parte sea la menos experimental y eficaz empíricamente, no obstante, para mi es clave y de gran riqueza, no solo porque marca el final de este motivador y gratificante camino, sino porque en el puedo dar mi gratitud a todos y todas los que han hecho que cada día creciera significativamente como investigador y mejorara mi calidad docente.

Gracias Javier, por ser mi director, jefe, referente, maestro, guía, y sobre todo un gran AMIGO. Este estimulante proyecto, junto con el camino integral que estamos emprendiendo, ha hecho que vivencemos juntos experiencias buenas y malas, y por supuesto, ha creado un vínculo profesional y personal de calidad, que hará que yo pueda desarrollarme personal y socialmente de forma más positiva. “*Seguimos caminado*” y “*partido a partido*”, frases que han sido de aliento en los momentos más difíciles, así como tu comprensión y consejos han sido mi luz en la oscuridad. ¡Gracias gran amigo! eres grande en todos los sentidos. Del mismo modo, gracias a tu familia que de forma implícita también ha sido un gran apoyo en este recorrido (gracias Marta, ves preparando otro tren).

Gracias a mi mujer, eres mi bastón, mi consejera, mi brújula, mi compañera, eres la persona que ha hecho que todo esto tenga sentido, y la que ha hecho que mi ilusión y motivación crezca significativamente. No se me olvida cuando este plan vital se inició, en nuestro pequeño paraíso costero, y tú me dijiste: “*¿por qué no intentarlo?*”. Mira en que se ha traducido, el proyecto se ha hecho realidad, por eso muchas gracias, nunca podré agradecértelo como tú te mereces. Del mismo modo, una mención especial a mi hijo Álvaro, que nació cuando este proyecto se inició; y a mi hija Paula, que nace con el final de la tesis... que curioso, el círculo se cierra con las dos personas que más quiero en este mundo.

Gracias a mis padres y hermanas, que son los que han sufrido mi ausencia en estos momentos tan difíciles. Gracias por enseñarme a ser quien soy. Papa, eres un luchador y nunca nadie te ha regalado nada, has sabido construir esta familia con tu esfuerzo y constancia. Mama, eres de otra pasta, a pesar de tus nuevas dificultades, nunca has dejado de luchar y de querer, tu corazón es tan grande que desbordas generosidad, por eso, esto es obra tuya.

Gracias Carlos, fuiste como el hermano que no tuve, me enseñaste tanto a seguir mis sueños, como que la constancia y el esfuerzo tiene sus frutos. Gracias querido amigo.

Gracias Mari-Luz, has sido como tu nombre indica, una luz que has guiado sabiamente mis decisiones. Gracias, porque has sido y serás como una madre académica, por eso esto también es obra tuya.

Gracias a todo el profesorado, alumnado, familias y centros educativos participante en la presente tesis doctoral. Gracias, por vuestra hospitalidad y por dejar que mis sueños y motivaciones se hagan realidad.

Gracias David, por ser mi tutor, por tus excelentes, creativos y motivantes procesos de enseñanza y aprendizaje. Asimismo, agradecerte la oportunidad de conocer el maravilloso mundo del MED, y por supuesto, por tus consejos y apoyo en este trayecto educativo.

Gracias al maravilloso y excelente elenco que conforma el profesorado de la Facultad de Educación de Ciudad Real, especialmente a todas y todos los que han estado ahí y me han alentado tanto. Gracias por darme a conocer la verdadera Educación de calidad, y por compartir vuestra sabiduría con tanto cariño y de forma tan eficaz.

Para finalizar, toda mi gratitud hacia los que han colaborado en esta pasión empírica, que se ha convertido en una excelente y motivadora locura.

Gracias, por compartir este camino.